

USAID HESHIMU BAHARI ACTIVITY

Private Sector Seascape Analysis

Submission Date: January 31, 2024

Contract Number: 72062122C00007

Activity Start Date and End Date: August 17, 2022, to August 16, 2027

COR Name: Jason Ko

Submitted by: Chemonics International Inc.

1275 New Jersey Avenue SE St. 200

Washington DC 20003

This document was produced for review by the United States Agency for International Development/Tanzania (USAID/Tanzania).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of Contents.....	i
Acronyms and Abbreviations	ii
SECTION 1: Executive Summary.....	1
1.1 Introduction.....	1
1.2 PSSA Overview.....	1
1.3 Private Sector Analysis.....	1
1.4 Partnership Concepts.....	1
1.5 Next Steps.....	2
SECTION 2: Introduction	3
2.1 Background and Rationale.....	3
2.2 Purpose and Use of PSSA.....	4
SECTION 3: Methodology	5
3.1 Key Research Questions.....	5
3.2 Geographic Scope	5
3.3 Mixed Method Data Collection.....	5
3.4 Partnership Concept Development and Prioritization.....	6
3.5 Implementation Schedule.....	7
SECTION 4: Private Sector Analysis.....	7
4.1 Country and Regional Private Sector Overview	7
4.2 Private Sector Interests and Challenges.....	8
4.3 Stakeholder Segmentation and Mapping	11
SECTION 5: Partnerships Concepts.....	12
5.1 Partnership Concept Prioritization	13
5.2 Quick Win Partnership Concepts.....	16
5.3 High Potential Partnership Concepts.....	28
5.4 Medium-High Potential Partnership Concepts	51
SECTION 6: Other PSE Recommendations	54
6.1 Build Government Capacity to Evaluate Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) for Marine and Tourism Investments.....	54
6.2 Gender and Youth Empowerment.....	55
6.3 Livelihoods and Value Chains.....	55
SECTION 7. Next Steps.....	56
ANNEX 1. Bibliography.....	57
ANNEX 2. Meeting List	60
ANNEX 3. Priority Partner Profiles	66
ANNEX 4. Partnership Concept Prioritization Scorecard.....	117
ANNEX 5. Interview Guide Template.....	118
ANNEX 6. PSE Sector Analyses.....	120

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

BDS	Business Development Services
BMU	Beach Management Unit
C-WEED	C-WEED Corporation
CWF	Chen Woo Fishery
DFC	Development Finance Corporation
DFC-DCA	Development Finance Corporation Development Credit Authority
EACOP	East African Crude Oil Pipeline
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
FETA	Fisheries Education and Training Agency
FRZ	Fish Replenishment Zone
GCF	Green Climate Fund
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GLI	Gender Lens Investing
GFCR	Global Fund for Coral Reefs
HAT	Hotel Association of Tanzania
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IUU	Illegal, Unregulated, Unmonitored Fishing
MBREMP	Mnazi Bay-Ruvuma Estuary Marine Park
MITO	Mafia Island Tourism Organization
MLF	Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries
MMA	Marine Management Area
MNRT	Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism
MoBEF	Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries
MPRU	Marine Parks and Reserves Unit
NEMC	National Environmental Management Council
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
NTZ	No Take Zone
ORRAA	Ocean Risk and Resilience Alliance
PBA	Pemba Beekeeper Association
PECCA	Pemba Channel Conservation Area
PPD	Public-Private Dialogue
PPP	Public-Private Partnership

PSE	Private Sector Engagement
PSSA	Private Sector Seascape Analysis
PSLA	Private Sector Landscape Analysis
SEAF	Small Enterprise Assistance Fund
SEAF-CEED	Small Enterprise Assistance Fund Center for Entrepreneurship and Development
SIDO	Small Industry Development Organization
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TADB	Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank
TANAPA	Tanzania National Parks
TASCO	Tourism Action Coalition for a Sustainable Ocean
TATONA	Tanga Tourism Network Association
TAWA	Tanzania Wildlife Authority
TACMP	Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park
TICCIA	Tanzania Chamber of Commerce, Industries, and Agriculture
TIC	Tanzania Investment Center
TSB	Tanzania Private Sector Foundation
TTB	Tanzania Tourism Board
TOR	Terms of Reference
TZS	Tanzanian Shilling
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
UWAWABIMA	Kipumbwi Fisheries Cooperative Society Ltd
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
WCS	Wildlife Conservation Society
WWF	World Wildlife Fund
WWF SASSI	World Wildlife Fund Southern African Sustainable Seafood Initiative
ZAFARI	Zanzibar Marine Research and Fisheries Institute
ZATI	Zanzibar Association of Tourism Investors
ZIPA	Zanzibar Investment Promotion Authority
ZCT	Zanzibar Commission for Tourism
ZEEA	Zanzibar Economic Empowerment Agency
ZEMA	Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority

SECTION I: EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

I.1 INTRODUCTION

The USAID Heshimu Bahari (“Respect the Ocean”) Activity, a five-year USD \$25 million initiative, is working to enhance the ecological resilience and productivity of high marine biodiversity areas and strengthen the resilience of coastal communities to climate change in Tanzania. The Activity is pursuing partnerships with private sector actors that can play a catalytic role in increasing resources available to support marine management areas (MMAs), sustainable fisheries, value chain improvements, and enhanced livelihoods. Heshimu Bahari designed and conducted a private sector seascape analysis (PSSA) from July – December 2023 to identify actionable private sector engagement (PSE) and partnership opportunities to pursue.

I.2 PSSA OVERVIEW

Adapted from other Private Sector Landscape Analyses (PSLAs), the PSSA team used a staged approach to identify private sector challenges, priorities, and opportunities for engagement:

- **Reviewed over 40 documents, databases, and websites** to understand the barriers and opportunities for private sector investment in marine conservation and key blue economy sectors.
- **Developed a stakeholder map for the 12 seascapes** with key stakeholders in and connected to the private sector to interview.
- **Completed 101 interviews** with a range of key stakeholders over 41 days to understand and validate private sector challenges, interests, and identify initial partnership opportunities.
- **Developed 24 partner profiles and 15 priority partnership concepts** with interested private sector actors that showed potential to advance the Activity’s objectives for further analysis.

I.3 PRIVATE SECTOR ANALYSIS

Through the desk research and interviews, the PSSA team identified the main private sector challenges and barriers to investment of key sectors in target seascapes:

- **Fees, taxes, and regulations for businesses** engaged in coastal tourism and blue economy sectors are major barriers to investment in marine conservation and communities.
- **Environmental impact assessments (EIAs) for tourism investments** in Zanzibar, especially for new small islands, are insufficient or not monitored, leading to negative impacts on critical habitats.
- **Lack of collateral, high interest rates, and perceived risk** is a major barrier for cooperatives and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in blue economy sectors to access formal financing.
- **Low awareness by most tourism investors and hotels of best practices in MMA management** and the business case for investing in conservation and communities.
- **Climate change is impacting the seafood and tourism sectors**, lowering aquaculture and fisheries production in specific regions and seasons, and increasing the cost of operating hotels.
- **Seafood is mainly produced from unorganized, small-scale fishers and farmers** with limited access to finance, processing technology, or markets, leading to low-quality and high post-harvest loss.

I.4 PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTS

The PSSA team developed an initial 18 partnership concepts with the potential to advance both business interests and contribute to Heshimu Bahari’s objectives across the Activity’s 12 seascapes. Using a prioritization scorecard, the PSSA team assessed and compared each concept for its business value,

development value, and implementation feasibility, and selected 15 priority concepts and identified three low priority concepts in following categories:

1. **Quick wins** that require minimal time to initiate and yield positive contribution in Year 2.
2. **High potential** that demonstrates high levels of impact and alignment but requires review with the technical team and additional follow-up.
3. **Medium-high potential** that demonstrates some alignment and possible impact but requires additional analysis and due diligence.
4. **Low potential** that either do not align with Heshimu Bahari objectives and/or have a low chance of demonstrating impact during the life of the project; these should not be explored further.

Concept	
Quick wins	Peer-to-peer capacity building on sustainable tourism and marine conservation for small island investors and eco-resorts.
	Accelerate private sector-led MMA management by partnering with Zanzibar, Tanga, and Pangani investors and eco-resorts to advance marine conservation and build community livelihood resilience.
	Zanzibar small island investor and marine conservation forum.
	Tanga sustainable tourism forum and public-private dialogue (PPD).
High	Engage Miamba Yetu: Sustainable Reef Investments/Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR) to co-invest in marine conservation and sustainable fisheries.
	Build resilient and inclusive seaweed value chains and communities through buyer-linked approach.
	Unlock financing for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives in blue economy sectors.
	Strengthen fishery cooperatives in Tanga and Pangani.
	Scale the Blue Alliance Zanzibar Blue Corridor in Pemba Channel Conservation Area.
	Accelerate private sector-led MMA management by partnering with Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara eco-resorts to advance marine conservation and build community livelihood resilience.
	Strengthen fishers and seaweed farmers cooperatives in Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara.
Med-High	Promote investment in value added global quality seaweed products.
	Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara sustainable tourism and MMA management PPD and forum.
	Expand small-scale fishers access to cold storage solutions.
Low	Promote sustainable aquaculture and improve small-scale fishers access to markets.
	Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) to support the development of cooperatives and SMEs to improve seafood production techniques and technology.
	Engage with South Pole to identify opportunities for the creation of blue carbon credits.
	Participation in the EACOP Tanzania Conservation Trust Fund with a facility for marine conservation.

1.5 NEXT STEPS

The results of the PSSA revealed more potential partners and concepts than are feasible for Heshimu Bahari to pursue within the confines of available funding, staff time, and other commitments. Furthermore, not all partnerships are equal—they vary in potential impact, seascape reach, partner interest, risks, and transaction costs. This report provides immediate next steps for all quick win and priority partnership concepts, and details that the Heshimu Bahari team can use to prioritize partnership opportunities to pursue in Year 2 and beyond, those that do not align to drop, and those that require additional follow-up with partners. This PSSA report will also serve as a resource in developing an overall PSE engagement strategy plan and serve as a framework for identifying partnership opportunities in the expansion seascapes.

SECTION 2: INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the background, process, and results of the PSSA conducted between July and December 2023. It is intended to serve as a resource for the Heshimu Bahari to be strategic and proactive in its engagement of private sector partners.

2.1 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

With a coastline touching approximately 1,424 km of the Indian Ocean,¹ Tanzania is uniquely positioned as a steward over a vast quantity of marine resources. Tanzania's marine and coastal ecosystems host a diverse range of coral reefs, seagrasses, open-ocean pelagic habitats, and mangroves while supporting various livelihoods in the fishing, aquaculture, and tourism sectors. Unfortunately overfishing, pollution, poorly planned infrastructure projects, and the effects of climate change threaten Tanzania's ocean habitats,² along with the livelihoods and food security of the surrounding coastal communities. Ineffective and underfunded fisheries management and marine conservation governance systems and limited private sector investment in conservation and value chains are significant barriers to building resilient marine ecosystems and communities. There is a critical need to increase investment and funding for marine conservation efforts, but with the global marine conservation financing gap estimated at USD \$175 billion annually, Tanzania must find new and creative ways to face these hurdles and meet its marine conservation financing needs.³

To address these challenges, the USAID Heshimu Bahari (“Respect the Ocean”) Activity, a five-year USD \$25 million initiative, is working to enhance the ecological resilience and productivity of high marine biodiversity areas and strengthen the resilience of coastal communities to climate change in Tanzania. To achieve its overall goal of reducing threats to marine and coastal biodiversity, Heshimu Bahari aims to establish an enabling environment and a science-driven framework for sustainable MMAs and fisheries co-management by the government, communities, and the private sector through four integrated objectives.

Heshimu Bahari recognizes the importance of PSE to achieve the desired impact, integrating aspects of it across all Activity objectives and applying it as the foundation of Objective 3. Through these efforts, and in the context of marine conservation and the blue economy, the Activity is focused on engaging private sector actors that have a catalytic role in enhancing the resilience of marine ecosystems and coastal communities to climate change by helping to improve the management of MMAs, as well as increase the productivity of blue economy producers and their associated value chains. This focus is based on the

¹ Review of the state of world marine capture fisheries management: Indian Ocean. (n.d.) <https://www.fao.org/3/a0477e/a0477e13.htm>

² Concept Note: Validation and Launching the Report on the Status and Trends of Coral Reefs in Tanzania 2022

³ Coan, P. (2023, July 6). Closing the financing gap of marine conservation. BlueSeeds. <https://bluseeds.org/en/closing-the-financing-gap-of-marine-conservation/>

definition of PSE as specified in USAID’s Private Sector Engagement Policy, enabling Heshimu Bahari to employ the wide range of PSE tools and strategies offered by USAID to create shared value with the private sector and drive greater impact within marine conservation.⁴

2.2 PURPOSE AND USE OF PSSA

The purpose of the PSSA, as defined under activity no. 3.1.1 in Heshimu Bahari’s FY2023 work plan and activity nos. 3.1.1 and 3.1.3 in Heshimu Bahari’s FY2024 workplan, is to identify partnership opportunities and provide action-oriented recommendations to integrate into a PSE strategy (activity no. 3.1.2 in the FY2024 work plan) in Year 2 and implement throughout the life of the Activity. The analysis will support the Activity to engage the private sector in an informed way, understand their motivations, and identify where shared value can be leveraged to drive more significant project impact, including by mapping the private-sector landscape, identifying opportunities for alignment, and articulating and analyzing Partnership solutions. The full PSSA scope of work can be found in Annex 6.

The intended audience of the PSSA is the Heshimu Bahari Team, USAID/Tanzania, and other external parties engaged in Tanzania’s marine conservation ecosystem. Furthermore, learnings from the PSSA will not be limited to Activity staff leading PSE initiatives, but it will also serve as a resource to support all Heshimu Bahari Team members in identifying partnership opportunities in the private and public sectors across the Activity’s objectives.

⁴ “PRIVATE-SECTOR ENGAGEMENT POLICY,” n.d.

SECTION 3: METHODOLOGY

The Heshimu Bahari PSSA uses a structured methodology adapted from other PSLAs to (1) understand the incentives of the private sector and how they can be leveraged towards positive marine conservation impact; (2) identify key stakeholders both in and connected to the private sector, and; (3) develop priority partnership concepts with the private sector to advance the Activity's objectives. This methodology enables Heshimu Bahari to identify shared value with the private sector and apply it to partnership concept recommendations.

3.1 KEY RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The PSSA Team addressed the following research questions:

1. What private sector stakeholders are the most relevant for and interested in advancing marine conservation and climate resilient communities in the target seascapes?
2. What opportunities exist for creating shared value between Heshimu Bahari and the private sector in the target seascapes to drive impact?
3. What are the key barriers to the private sector effectively investing and engaging in marine conservation, sustainable fisheries, and/or resilient coastal livelihoods?
4. What public-private partnership opportunities exist to advance sustainable investment in marine conservation, sustainable fisheries and/or resilient coastal livelihoods?
5. What institutional knowledge and capacity exists among relevant stakeholders for gender inclusive investments?

3.2 GEOGRAPHIC SCOPE

The PSSA was conducted across Heshimu Bahari's 12 seascapes (see map) between July and December 2023.

3.3 MIXED METHOD DATA COLLECTION

The PSSA applied a mixed methods data collection framework to its research:

1. **Secondary data collection through desk research** using relevant reports on the region's marine conservation and blue economy landscapes. The

reports are primary from international development organizations and implementing partners, such as the United Nations, European Union, World Bank, and USAID, and were sourced via a combination of recommendations from current Heshimu Bahari project staff and targeted internet searches. This data helped frame the PSSA team’s understanding of the marine conservation landscape in the target seascapes, and what partnership opportunities and stakeholders should be explored ahead of the stakeholder interviews.

2. **Primary data collection through stakeholder interviews** taking place both virtually and on-the-ground. The purpose of the primary data collection is twofold: (1) to expand upon and validate information collected through the secondary data collection and; (2) to identify specific stakeholders for partnership opportunities with Heshimu Bahari. A standard interview guide template was used as an organizational tool for each interview and is provided in Annex 5.

Prior to in-person interviews, the PSSA team completed a stakeholder segmentation and mapping exercise to identify relevant stakeholders to include in the primary data collection. Building from the USAID Private Sector Engagement Policy’s definition of the private sector⁵ and incorporating the blue economy context, the PSSA focuses on a range of public and private sector actors that could advance Heshimu Bahari’s objectives in the target seascapes. The stakeholder mapping exercise was informed through a combination of project staff recommendations, desk research, and personal networking.

3.4 PARTNERSHIP CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND PRIORITIZATION

Based on the mixed methods data collection, the PSSA team created partnership concepts with private and public sector actors that show promise and strategic alignment with Heshimu Bahari’s objectives. The concepts include the challenges and opportunities to be addressed, potential partners involved and their roles (including Heshimu Bahari), key actions and strategies, concept justification and impact, and immediate next steps towards implementation.

Not all partnership opportunities are equal - they vary in potential impact, partner interest, risks, and transaction costs, to name a few. In this context, the PSSA team created and applied a prioritization framework to evaluate the priority levels of the partnership concepts. The framework measures the concepts’ potential impact on Heshimu Bahari objectives in three areas:

1. **Business Value:** to what extent does the concept contribute to business goals, remove key bottlenecks of risk, and/or strengthen the reputation of the business or private sector entity?
2. **Development Value:** to what extent does the concept align with Heshimu Bahari’s seascapes, contribute to the Activity’s objectives, and produce sustainable results?

⁵ “PRIVATE-SECTOR ENGAGEMENT POLICY,” n.d.

3. **Feasibility:** how complex is the concept from idea to implementation; what is the level of effort and resources required for successful engagement; and how much time is required before the concept starts to deliver meaningful results?

By measuring each partnership concept against the same criteria, the prioritization framework helps reduce bias from the PSSA team, providing a more objective ranking of the potential impact. Each criterion in the framework receives a grade of low, medium, or high, and a corresponding numeric score is applied of 1, 3, and 5 respectively. The results of the prioritization can be found in Section 5.1 and the full prioritization framework can be found in Annex 4.

3.5 IMPLEMENTATION SCHEDULE

PSSA implementation took place between July 2023 and January 2024, and involved the following key stages:

SECTION 4: PRIVATE SECTOR ANALYSIS

4.1 COUNTRY AND REGIONAL PRIVATE SECTOR OVERVIEW

Although the PSSA focuses on the private sector landscape in specific coastal regions of Tanzania, it is still necessary to provide context from both a country and regional perspective to fully understand the private sector within the target seascapes.

4.1.1 COUNTRY PRIVATE SECTOR OVERVIEW: TANZANIA

- With a rising population of over 67 million people and a medium age of 17, the Tanzanian economy faces a challenge in providing employment opportunities for its young and growing workforce.⁶
- Agriculture is currently the country’s largest employment sector, accounting for 64% of total employment (although it has been on a downward trend since 1995, when it sat at 85% of total employment), followed by the services industry at 28%, and the industry sector at 7%.
- Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita has been trending upwards for nearly 30 years and currently sits at USD \$1,056.9.
- Although Tanzania witnessed a dip in GDP growth in 2020 due to the economic contractions associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, it was relatively mild when compared to the rest of sub-Saharan Africa. In 2020, Tanzania's economy grew by 2% compared to the -2% growth realized by the Sub-Saharan Africa region over the same period, highlighting the country’s relative resilience against economic shocks.⁷

⁶ “Tanzania Demographics 2020 (Population, Age, Sex, Trends) - Worldometer,” n.d.

⁷ World Bank Open Data | Data

- In its National Development Vision of 2025, the Government of Tanzania expressed willingness to engage the private sector as a tool to grow the national economy, recognizing private sector investment as essential to the country’s economic development and its efforts to maintain middle-income status.⁸ Tanzania has several key institutions in place whose aim is to support and protect interests of the private sector, namely the Tanzania Private Sector Foundation (TPSF), Tanzania Chamber of Commerce, Industries, and Agriculture (TCCIA), and other sector associations. For example, recently The Tanzania National Business Council established PPD platform to facilitate discussions between the Government and private sector actors on matters of mutual interests.⁹

4.1.2 REGIONAL PRIVATE SECTOR OVERVIEW: TARGET SEASCAPES

The private sector landscape in and around the target seascapes feature a different economic reality than the rest of the country.

- Tanzania’s capital and largest city, Dar es Salaam, has a population of over 7.5 million people, with estimates showing it will reach over 13 million people by 2035.¹⁰ The city’s percent share contributed to national GDP is 17%, more than twice that of the next closest mainland region. As Dar es Salaam is located within a target seascape, this data shows the city is not only an economic driver of the region, but it also serves as an engine for Tanzania’s entire mainland economy.¹¹
- Zanzibar, the semi-autonomous island region off the coast of mainland Tanzania, as of 2022 has a population of 1.89 million people, GDP of USD \$2.33 billion, and GDP per capita of USD \$1,235.¹² Although Zanzibar produces a variety of agriculture products, such as cloves, and blue economy products, such as seafood and seaweed, it is primarily viewed as a tourist destination, receiving ~400,000 tourists in 2021 at its 683 hotels.¹³
- Other local economics in and around the target seascapes operate in similar economic sectors to that of Dar es Salaam and Zanzibar, but at a smaller scale, with focus on agriculture, the blue economy, the import/export of goods, and tourism. For example, in 2021/2022 Tanga’s port processed 942,000 tons of cargo, Mtwara 592,400 tons, and Kilwa 35,700 tons compared to Dar es Salaam’s 17.85 million tons.¹⁴

4.2 PRIVATE SECTOR INTERESTS AND CHALLENGES

Through a combination of desk research conducted during the pre-trip phase and in the stakeholder interviews, the PSSA team identified some of the key interests and challenges of the private sector in the target seascapes. Understanding the private sector interests and challenges is central to identifying what incentives Heshimu Bahari should consider finding shared value and engage with these stakeholders.

4.2.1 KEY PRIVATE SECTOR INTERESTS

Sector	Interest
Fisheries, Aquaculture,	Increase supply/production of products that meet the requirements of higher-value markets. Consistent across the "production-based" sectors is the need to increase the value and profit created from their production. The two most common methods to achieve

⁸ “DEVELOPMENT VISION 2025 FOREWORD” n.d.
⁹ “TNBC | Mfumo Wa Majadiliano” n.d.
¹⁰ Dar es Salaam, Tanzania Population (2023) - Population Stat
¹¹ National Bureau of Statistics. 2013.
¹² Tanzania in Figure 2022 (nbs.go.tz)
¹³ Zanzibar in Figures, 2021 (ocgs.go.tz)
¹⁴ Bank of Tanzania (BoT) Consolidated Zonal Economic Performance Report for The Year Ending June 2022

Alternative Livelihoods	this goal are (1) supply side, or increasing the total production volume, and (2) product value-addition, usually with the goal of selling to higher-value markets.
Tourism, Finance	Mitigate risk before engaging in new blue economy investments. Tourism investors, hotel operators, and financial institutions face challenges in making blue economy investments, citing risks that include cost of due diligence, lack of capacity, and regulatory barriers. In tourism, hotels feel investing in marine conservation is difficult due to uncertain regulations, lack of incentives, and high fees in marine conservation areas. For financial institutions, hesitancy involves their limited understanding of the blue economy and their ability to adequately measure risks associated with blue economy loans (especially in new geographic areas/asset classes they are not familiar with).
Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture	Streamline regulatory and tax regimes to provide more incentives for conservation. Many stakeholders express the need for tax reform, citing high rates and confusing regulatory systems. They also express interest in engaging in more marine conservation activities if the right combination of tax incentives are made available.
Tourism	<p>Expansion/construction of new hotels. In all target seascapes (but especially those in Unguja and Pemba) a clear interest from the tourism sector is the continued expansion of hotel operators. This is understood not only from PSSA stakeholder interviews, but also through government agencies and associations connected to the tourism sector, who indicate a rapid expansion of hotel operators in those regions, especially in the last few years after strict COVID-19 restrictions were lifted.</p> <p>There is clear interest from the private sector for increased public sector investment in tourism promotion along the mainland coast especially in Kilwa, Mtwara, Pangani, and Tanga. Stakeholders indicated critical absence of tourism activities despite having world recognized attractions such as Kilwa Kisiwani and proximity to Selous Game Reserve UNESCO World heritage sites. The private sector is interested in working with the public sector in tourism promotion. However, they face challenges due to limited resources. To address this, stakeholders emphasized the need for government to invest more in infrastructure development to improve accessibility and connectivity to coastal tourist destinations (e.g., upgrading transportation networks and maintaining well-equipped airports).</p>
Fisheries, Aquaculture, Finance	Increase the overall investment/financing available for the blue economy. The fisheries and aquaculture sectors, along with financial institutions, convey a consistent message around the need for greater investment and financing. For the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, the need involves tailored financing options to meet the specific needs of their operations, without unreasonably high interest rates. For the financial institutions, the need is based in expanding their reach to a new customer base and sourcing the right blue economy investments to include in their loan portfolio.

4.2.2 KEY PRIVATE SECTOR CHALLENGES

Sector	Challenge
Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods	Environmental Impact Assessments for tourism and hotel investment in Zanzibar are either insufficient or not enforced. Based on conversations with the Zanzibar Investment Promotion Authority (ZIPA), it is understood the EIAs required for all tourism investment are generally either not effective or not enforced at all. This means when hotel investors purchase land with the intention to construct a hotel property, there is no accountability to the effect said property might have on the local ecosystem, potentially imposing significant negative implications. Moreover, while the mainland equivalent of ZIPA, the Tanzania Investment Center (TIC), seems to have a slightly stronger process for EIAs, through PSSA stakeholder interviews it is understood they also have much room for improvement.

	<p>Absence or limited SMEs investments in blue economy value addition and located in coastal communities. The PSSA team noted an absence of SMEs located in coastal communities that are engaged in value addition of local livelihood products (e.g., seaweed, fisheries, coconuts, etc.) to produce quality and competitive products for local, regional, and international markets. Apart from a few buyers of, for example, fish and dried seaweed mostly coming from developed urban centers, very few SMEs processors of local products were found in coastal or nearby communities. Considering the role these SMEs can play in providing alternative incomes that can reduce pressure on fisheries, incentives to invest in coastal communities need to be explored.</p>
Fisheries, Aquaculture	<p>Climate Change is lowering overall production of fisheries and aquaculture. While regional and value-chain specific factors do play a significant role in the overall productivity of Tanzania's coastal fishery and aquaculture operations, a more macro factor, climate change, is also starting to play a role in determining production levels. Rising ocean temperatures are directly correlated with lower production levels in fishing and aquaculture,¹⁵ and local stakeholders in these sectors are starting to notice the change. Without considering the role climate change plays in lowering the productivity of the blue economy, fisheries and aquaculture production levels will continue to fall.</p>
Fisheries, Aquaculture	<p>Lack of collateral and organization prevents blue economy enterprises from gaining more standardized access to finance. One of the largest barriers to accessing finance for community-level stakeholders in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors is lack of collateral. Through the PSSA stakeholder interviews, several stakeholders expressed difficulty obtaining reasonable loan terms absence the collateral financing providers seek. Without it, they are forced to accept loans with very unfavorable terms or continue without any financing.</p>
Tourism	<p>Limited investment in tourism facilities, infrastructure, and tourism promotion. During PSSA interviews with both public and private stakeholders, especially in Kilwa and Mtwara, stakeholders indicated a critical absence of investments in tourism despite having world recognized attractions and recognition of the sector's importance in sustainable MMA management. Lindi and Mtwara regional governments cite tourism as a priority sector, and the Marine Parks and Reserves Unit (MPRU) and Tanzania Wildlife Authority (TAWA) wish to see lodges and transport/logistics investments in their parks. However, the private sector cites poor infrastructure and limited public sector interest in tourism promotion and investment in facilities and infrastructure.</p> <p>Understanding of the business case for marine conscience tourism/hotels is limited and not promoted. The PSSA team connected with a wide range of hotel operators, including 'traditional' operators and 'eco-resorts.' While eco-resorts understand how to incorporate marine conservation into their business model, traditional hotel operators generally still do not. Without traditional hotel operators understanding the business case for marine conservation in tourism, there will be significant challenges in scaling marine conservation initiatives within the tourism sector over the long-term.</p>
Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Finance	<p>Tax and regulations provide limited incentives and funds to support conservation and communities. Stakeholders across all sectors indicate challenges around the current tax code and enforcement, how it is limiting business growth, and how there is a lack of incentives for supporting marine conservation and community development.</p>

Moreover, the PSSA team also conducted a more detailed analysis on five key PSE sectors connected to the Heshimu Bahari objectives, namely tourism, seaweed, fisheries, aquaculture, and finance. These PSE sector analyses can be found in Annex 6.

¹⁵ The Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar, 2022. Scoping study on Blue Economy opportunities in Zanzibar. Ministry of Fisheries and Blue Economy Publication 2022.

4.3 STAKEHOLDER SEGMENTATION AND MAPPING

Prior to on-the-ground interviews, the PSSA team conducted a stakeholder segmentation and mapping exercise with the goal of identifying specific and relevant stakeholders engaging with the local private sector to request interviews from as part of the PSSA. The first step in the exercise, the stakeholder segmentation, aims to understand the types of private sector stakeholders currently operating in and around the target seascapes. To identify what types of stakeholders to include in the segmentation, the PSSA team relied on the USAID Private Sector Engagement Policy’s definition of the private sector,¹⁶ as well as local context through recommendations from project staff and desk research. The resulting table supported the framing of stakeholder mapping in the weeks following:

Stakeholder Segmentation

Type of Stakeholder	Why Target?
Tourism Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct stake in marine resources as a function of their business and tour offering. • Extensive knowledge of local context and connections with communities. • Successful MMA partnerships leading to MMA management and strengthening.
Hotels and Eco-resorts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to serve as direct investors in MMA management and conservation efforts. • Already existing high-level of investment and strong presence in target seascapes. • History of successful partnerships globally and in Tanzania in MMA strengthening.
Business Associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power to engage multiple companies to make the case for sustainable practices. • Support policy and regulatory reforms that strengthen the broader industry and/or facilitate investment in marine conservation and sustainable value chains. • Ability to convene private sector stakeholders relevant to MMA management, sustainable fisheries, value chains and resilient livelihoods.
Seafood Buyers and Processors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purchasing power, market incentives, and co-funding ability to implement sustainable, and equitable practices with their suppliers. • Financial resources to co-invest in value chain improvements.
Business Service Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business models for underserved customers in coastal communities that create alternative and diversified livelihoods. • Technical expertise, staff, and co-funding to promote awareness of key services. • Ability to support MMA-adjacent businesses through investment facilitation services.
Businesses Using Major Inputs or Supply Chains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funds and interest to test solutions impacting operations or communities. • Training and extension programs for small suppliers in coastal communities. • Programs and other support designed to benefit communities attached to workforce or supplier in given geographic area.
Financial Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can develop finance vehicles, including blended finance products, that bring private capital to fisheries and other sectors for sustainability and marine conservation efforts. • Ability to provide capital investments, working capital, and credit solutions. • Knowledge and guidance to help SMEs scale in blue economy sectors.
Insurance Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and provide insurance products for small-scale fishers, aquaculture producers, and coastal communities that build resilience against economic and climate shocks.

¹⁶ USAID Private-Sector Engagement Policy, n.d.

Technology Companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to develop solutions for governments, seafood supply chains, and other blue economy producers that can, among others, increase incomes, support fisheries data collection, improve quality and traceability, and combat illegal fishing.
Philanthropic Actors/Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to patient capital/concessional finance to build capacity and de-risk investment. • Outreach and information dissemination channels.

The stakeholder segmentation was then applied to the second step of the exercise, the stakeholder mapping, where the PSSA team created a list of organizations operating within the target seascapes with the potential to strategically align with the Activity’s objectives. This ultimately resulted in a stakeholder mapping tracker tool which helped organize stakeholder outreach efforts in the weeks leading up to on-the-ground stakeholder interviews.

SECTION 5: PARTNERSHIPS CONCEPTS

The PSSA team developed 18 initial partnership concepts and narrowed that to 15 priority concepts as presented in the figure below, which include 25 priority partners presented in detailed in Annex 3. The concepts present the challenge, opportunity, key actions and strategies, partner roles and contributions, selection justification and impact, and immediate next steps. The concepts have been grouped into four themes:

1. **Sustainable tourism and private-led MMA:** partner with eco-resorts, small island investors, and other tourism stakeholders to enhance the resiliency of marine ecosystems. Accelerate private sector involvement and investment in sustainability, MMA co-management, sustainable fisheries, and community resilience and livelihoods.
2. **Finance for SMEs and resilient livelihoods:** build capacity of SMEs, cooperatives, and other businesses to secure financing for investment in marine conservation, sustainable fisheries, value chain improvements, and non-fisheries livelihoods.
3. **Value chains and resilient livelihoods:** leverage the market as a driver of compliance with sustainable fisheries management, build more efficient and equitable fisheries and non-fisheries value chains, and develop more resilient and diversified livelihoods.
4. **Public-private dialogue:** strengthen the enabling environment for tourism and fisheries private sector, supporting engagement and investment in marine conservation, sustainable fisheries, and community livelihoods.

Partnership Concepts

THEMES	PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTS	SEASCAPES	
	Sustainable Tourism and Private-Led MMA	Peer-to-peer capacity building on sustainable tourism and marine conservation for small island investors and eco-resorts	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Partner with eco-resorts to accelerate marine conservation and community livelihood activities	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Scale the Blue Alliance Zanzibar Blue Corridor in Pemba Channel Conservation Area	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Partner with Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara eco-resorts to accelerate marine conservation and community livelihoods	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
	Finance for MMA, SMEs, and Resilient Livelihoods	Engage Miamba Yetu: Sustainable Reef Investments/GFRC to co-invest in marine conservation and sustainable fisheries	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Unlock financing for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives in blue economy sectors	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Strengthen fishery cooperatives in Tanga and Pagani	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Build resilient seaweed value chains and communities through buyer-linked approach	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
	Value Chains and Resilient Livelihoods	Expand small-scale fishers access to cold storage solutions	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Promote sustainable aquaculture and improve small-scale fishers access to markets	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Strengthen fishers and seaweed farmers cooperatives in Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Mtwara, Kilwa, Mafia	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
		Promote domestic production of global quality seaweed products	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12
Public Private Dialogue	Zanzibar small island investor and marine conservation forum	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12	
	Tanga sustainable tourism and public private dialogue forum	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12	
	Mtwara, Kilwa and Mafia sustainable tourism and MMAs forum	1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12	

5.1 PARTNERSHIP CONCEPT PRIORITIZATION

These 18 concepts were initially prioritized based on interest from the potential private sector partner, contribution to Heshimu Bahari objectives, and feasibility to execute. The prioritization was then refined by the PSSA team using the PSE scorecard presented below. Based on the scoring, the PSSA team identified four concept categories:

1. **Quick wins** that require minimal time by Heshimu Bahari and partners to initiate, demonstrate clear shared value, yield positive contribution to Activity outputs in Year 2. They will also serve as a building block for achieving long-term objectives and should be pursued by Heshimu Bahari.
2. **High potential** that demonstrates potential for high levels of impact and alignment between the Heshimu Bahari and partners but requires further review and prioritization with the Heshimu Bahari technical team, and additional refinement with the potential partners.
3. **Medium-high potential** that demonstrate some alignment and possible impact but require additional analysis and due diligence before bringing to the Heshimu Bahari technical team.
4. **Low potential** that either do not align with Heshimu Bahari objectives and/or have a low chance of demonstrating impact during the life of the project; these should not be explored further.

Initial Partnership Concept Prioritization

	Concept	Score	Reasoning
Quick Wins	Peer-to-peer capacity building on sustainable tourism and marine conservation for small island investors and eco-resorts.	36	Chumbe is uniquely positioned to provide training and lead capacity building activities on a range of environmental sustainability, marine conservation, and community development, tailored in a way that works for tourism businesses.
	Accelerate private sector-led MMA management by partnering with Zanzibar, Tanga, and Pangani investors and eco-resorts to advance marine conservation and build community livelihood resilience.	34	Eco-resorts engaging in marine conservation and community livelihoods offer leverage potential and opportunities for quick and sustained success in four seascapes.
	Zanzibar small island investor and marine conservation forum.	31	First meeting already held, and interest from several investors, eco-resorts, and the government in continuing. Offers a venue to engage small island investors, share best practices in MMA management, and build awareness with the Zanzibar government on key issues/topics that tourism sector faces in marine conservation.
	Tanga sustainable tourism forum and PPD.	31	Addresses a key challenge for the tourism sector and private sector involvement in MMA in Tanga and Pangani, and high interest expressed by stakeholders.
High Priority	Engage Miamba Yetu: Sustainable Reef Investments/GFCR to co-invest in marine conservation and sustainable fisheries	30	Managed by partner, the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS), and offers additional grant and private investor resources to co-fund and expand marine conservation with small-island investors, eco-resorts, and other interested private sector partners.
	Build resilient and inclusive seaweed value chains and communities through buyer-linked approach	30	Seaweed has strong potential as an alternative livelihood to the fishing sector and involves many women in the sector. Cargill is one of the largest buyers of seaweed from Tanzania, and C-WEED is largest local supplier. Some concern about the negative impact of seaweed on marine habitats, low incomes, and vulnerability of the farmers.
	Unlock financing for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives in blue economy sectors.	29	Private sector financing could build resilient livelihoods and bolster marine conservation efforts in the targeted seascapes. Three institutions seem highly motivated to expand financing to coastal communities and SMEs but there are some questions about the ability of SMEs and cooperatives to take on commercial financing.
	Strengthen fishery cooperatives in Tanga and Pangani.	28	Fisheries cooperatives can play an important role in product value addition, aggregation, access to market and financing for small scale fishers. Fishery cooperatives have weak business models and limited funding and capacity, so ensuring the sustainability of a partnership with cooperatives in the fisheries sector may be difficult.

High Priority	Accelerate private sector-led MMA management by partnering with Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara eco-resorts to advance marine conservation and build community livelihood resilience.	28	Eco-resorts in the two seascapes are doing a lot in marine conservation and community livelihoods support. Heshimu Bahari can leverage their ongoing activities and plans to scale, replicate, and achieve Activity objectives.
	Strengthen fishers and seaweed farmers cooperatives in Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara.	28	Fishers and seaweed farmers cooperatives add value, aggregate products, access markets, and provide financing. This encourages community involvement in marine conservation, improves economic conditions, and reduces reliance on unsustainable fishing practices. This holistic approach supports coastal communities' well-being and fosters ecological resilience.
	Scale the Blue Alliance Zanzibar Blue Corridor in Pemba Channel Conservation Area.	27	Blue Alliance has a strong background in private sector MMA management and could leverage significant financing from private investors. Does not directly involved a seascape yet, and challenges in developing a viable sea cucumber enterprise involving communities are risks
	Promote investment in value added global quality seaweed products.	27	Mwani Zanzibar manufactures high-end cosmetics and skincare products based on seaweed, which is farmed by women in Paje. A partnership with Mwani Zanzibar could expand their production to benefit more women and youth through employment.
Med-High Priority	Mtwara, Kilwa, and Mafia sustainable tourism and MMA management PPD and forum.	26	Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara seascapes have unique attractions and unique challenges including limited investment in tourism facilities and infrastructure. With the tourism sector being key to sustainable MMAs management, supporting tourism sector PPD and investment forum is recommended.
	Expand small-scale fishers access to cold storage solutions	26	Cold storage is a major issue for small-scale fisheries, and the company focuses on small-scale fishers. The company is just expanding into coastal regions, so more follow-up needed.
	Promote sustainable aquaculture and improve small-scale fishers access to markets	25	Aquaculture could provide alternative livelihoods and reduce pressure on fisheries. Key questions on the viability and negative environmental impacts.
Low Priority	PPP to support the development of cooperatives and SMEs to improve seafood production techniques and technology	24	Addresses a major issue in seafood supply chains and builds on government efforts. Is not a clear private sector partner to provide market access and support the scaling of the technology.
	Engage with South Pole to identify opportunities for the creation of blue carbon credits	23	Blue carbon credit could catalyze funds for communities and conservation, but it is a very new concept globally and in Tanzania with several uncertainties and risks.
	Participation in the EACOP Tanzania Conservation Trust Fund	23	Fund could offer a large amount of leveraged funds for MMA management. However, it is unclear if it will receive government approvals or include a specific focus on marine

	with a set aside grant facility for marine conservation funding	conservation. Also, potential high risks of partnering with a company engaged in fossil fuel extraction.
--	---	--

5.2 QUICK WIN PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTS

The PSSA identified four quick win partnership concepts or opportunities:

1. **PPD:** Zanzibar small island investor and marine conservation forum
2. **Tourism:** Peer-to-peer capacity building on sustainable tourism and marine conservation for small island investors and eco-resorts
3. **Tourism:** Accelerate private sector-led MMA management by partnering with Zanzibar, Tanga, and Pangani investors and eco-resorts to advance marine conservation and build community livelihood resilience
4. **PPD:** Tanga sustainable tourism forum and PPD

5.2.1 PPD: ZANZIBAR SMALL ISLAND INVESTOR AND MARINE CONSERVATION FORUM

Challenge

Several of the small island tourism investors in Zanzibar are interested in engaging in environmental sustainability and marine conservation activities, recognizing the potential business and attraction value of preserving the natural beauty and ecological health of the ecosystems around their existing or planned hotel operations in the long-term. However, most of these new investors in small islands do not have the knowledge or experience in how to engage and invest effectively in marine conservation and community development and have allocated limited budget and resources for these activities. The investors are also unfamiliar with best practices in private-sector and community co-managed MMA, and the different programs and co-funding that is available from government, donors, and impact investors to support marine conservation.

Opportunity

On August 31, 2023, the first ‘Small Island Investors Forum’ meeting was organized in Zanzibar, bringing together investors, conservation organizations, government representatives, and local stakeholders to share best practices on MMAs/fish replenishment zones (FRZs), exchange knowledge on marine ecosystems conservation, promote sustainable fishing practices, and enhance the resilience of coastal communities to climate change. There is an opportunity to build on this momentum and coordinate with ZIPA to establish ongoing ‘Small Island Investors Forum’ meetings. By including operating ‘eco-resorts,’ or those hotel operators who already have a marine conservation focus as part of their operations, the Forum can leverage their experience and share it with the other small island investors to replicate marine conservation best practices, driving even greater impact. In turn, through participation in the Forum, the small island investors are expected to better understand and begin to apply said best practices, comply with current regulations, and support initiatives contributing to the resilience of coastal communities.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
--------------------	-------------------

Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate with ZIPA and other stakeholders for the Forum, facilitate discussions and drive follow-up with small island investors to keep momentum on potential initiatives. • Share the “Best Practice Guide for Private Sector Investment, Development, and Sustainability of MMAs” developed by Heshimu Bahari with Forum to inspire new island investors. • Provide insights on technical aspects of managing and protecting marine ecosystems and coastal resources.
Small Island Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learn best practices on private sector-led MMA/FRZ management and marine ecosystems conservations to apply to their investments. • Collaborate with eco-resorts and other investors to share best practices. • Engage in discussions to better understand regulatory.
Leading Zanzibar Eco-Resorts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share best practices on private sector-led MMA/FRZ management and marine conservation. • Serve as example and mentor for small island investors trying to adopt these practices. • Advise public sector members to improve operations and the regulatory environment to incentivize private sector investment in marine eco-system conservation.
Mainland Eco-resorts and Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate as observers for cross-learning and potential to develop a mainland tourism investors forum in the future.
GFCR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share experiences and models for reef positive private investments. • Provide insights what is needed to attract impact investment, and a regulatory environment that fosters greater investment in marine conservation. • Actively discuss and seek out GFCR investment opportunities with small island investors.
ZIPA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize and coordinate the forum invitations, active participation, discussions, and drive follow-up with small island investors in Zanzibar and include investors from Mainland Tanzania as observers. • Follow-up to maintain momentum on potential initiatives. • Assist investors in navigating the investment process, such as permits and licensing, ensuring all environmental regulations are being followed. • Promote the Forum among local and foreign investors interested in tourism and provide resources and information about investment opportunities and incentives in Zanzibar. • Facilitate networking opportunities for potential investors.
Zanzibar Commission for Tourism (ZCT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote the Forum and encourage tourism-related businesses to participate. • Provide expertise and guidance on tourism policies and regulations. • Facilitate partnerships and collaborations within the tourism sector. • Monitor and report on the impact of the Forum to the tourism industry in Zanzibar.
Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority (ZEMA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide advice on sustainable and environmentally responsible practices in the tourism sector and ensure conservation and environmental protection are integral aspects of any tourism development discussions. • Provide guidance on permits related to environmental impact assessments.
Zanzibar Association of Tourism Investors (ZATI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate with ZIPA to organize and promote the Forum to tourism stakeholders as well as act as a liaison between the ZIPA and tourism investor members that participate. • Share industry-specific insights and challenges with the Forum. • Disseminate tools and best practice guides to members. • Advertise the Forum to its members and mobilize their participation.

Key Actions and Strategies

Convene an initial meeting with ZIPA to inform the establishment of the Small Island Investors Forum and discuss how it will be structured, when it will be organized, and who will be invited. Heshimu Bahari can then communicate with ZIPA and key stakeholders to understand the implementation modality, budget, and other support needed to implement the Forum. This will lead to the development of a Forum action

plan with clearly defined objectives and goals, and a timeline focused on achieving sustainable tourism development in MMAs, biodiversity conservation, and responsible investment.

- **Promotion and Awareness:** Convene ZCT and ZIPA to collaborate in the promotion of the Forum to potential investors and stakeholders. Promotion methods they can explore include existing platforms and campaigns, workshops, and sector events.
- **Sustainable Best-Practices Showcase:** Coordinate with leading eco-resorts, ZIPA, and ZCT to showcase sustainable best-practices and positive environmental impact, serving as an example for other investors.

Justification and Impact

Dialogues between key private and public stakeholders involved in Zanzibar's tourism sector and in environment and MMA management can address several systemic barriers to private investment in marine conservation and communities. First, by connecting the small island investors with leading eco-resorts in Zanzibar, Mnemba Island Lodge, The Manta Resort, and Chumbe Island Lodge, the investors can ask questions and understand best practices specific to hotels engaging in MMA management and marine conservation, which in turn can be replicated in their investments. Second, in the past the public sector stakeholders, such as ZIPA, ZCT, and ZEMA, have struggled to share information on the regulations surrounding environmental compliance for investments, a key component for strengthening marine conservation in MMAs. By directly connecting the public and private sector actors involved in small island investments, the Forum can facilitate the conservations necessary for full compliance with current environmental regulations. Including mainland investors and eco-resorts as observers creates opportunities for cross-learning and could be a model to expand to the mainland in future years.

CASE STUDY

The Tourism Action Coalition for a Sustainable Ocean (TASCO) brings together businesses, financial sector, NGOs, and international donors to promote global investments in sustainable tourism and oceans. Set up in response to the UN High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, TASCO serves as a knowledge hub through the dissemination and development of tools and resources guidelines and encourages policies that build resilient destinations and encourage climate action.

Source: *Tasco website*¹⁷

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Establish working group with representatives to organize the Forum	x					
Follow-up with investors that attended and those invited to the first meeting	x					
Develop forum Terms of Reference (TOR) with goals, objectives, and roles		x				
Schedule the 2 nd Forum meeting and present the best practices guide			x	x		

¹⁷ TASCO website visited on October 30, 2023. <https://oceantourism.org>

5.2.2 TOURISM AND MMA: PEER-TO-PEER CAPACITY BUILDING ON SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND MARINE CONSERVATION FOR SMALL ISLAND INVESTORS AND ECO-RESORTS

Challenge

Engaging investors and hotels in marine conservation and community engagement in Tanzania comes with inherent difficulty as these businesses are focused on profitability and generally lack incentive to invest in conservation. Moreover, as these investors and businesses have limited knowledge of marine resources and fisheries management, it's difficult for them to understand how those initiatives can be leveraged as value-added products that would attract guests and increase revenues and profit. There is also a growing interest by some hotels and restaurants in Zanzibar for sustainable and local seafood sourcing, but it is limited by a lack of knowledge on what constitutes a sustainable fishery and insufficient data on the status of local fish stocks. Chumbe Island Coral Park (Chumbe), an eco-resort that successfully operates private sector-led MMA management, is interested in addressing these issues and has been asked by the government of Zanzibar and other eco-resorts to support sustainability initiatives. Unfortunately, given the scale and attention needed to meet these challenges, Chumbe and other leading eco-resorts in Zanzibar cannot fully support the government and other investors and hotels' sustainability initiatives due to limited staff time and funding.

Opportunity

Zanzibar has several successful private-led or managed MMAs, including Chumbe, Manta Resort/Kwanini Foundation, and Mnemba Island, that can offer peer-to-peer capacity building for other eco-resorts, hotels, and new small island investors both in Zanzibar and on the mainland. In particular, Chumbe has expressed interest in leading training and learning exchanges with other eco-resorts and new investors and has been approached by some of these investors in search of a better understanding of how they might assess the coral reef resources and tourism opportunities around their islands. Peer-to-peer training would bring a business lens to these private sector stakeholders' understanding of marine conservation, to build greater understanding, dedication, and financial support towards sustainable resource management, community development, and MMA management.

Heshimu Bahari can also explore a partnership with the ZATI, to serve as a host and convener of the peer-to-peer learning exchanges and training sessions in partnership with Chumbe and the other leading eco-resorts based on their interest and resources. The goal is to inform small island investors and eco-resorts about private sector-led marine protected areas (MMA).

Moreover, Chumbe is developing an updated sustainable seafood guide to educate hotels and restaurants in Zanzibar on sustainable seafood sourcing. The guide will be part of the government's 'Greener Zanzibar' campaign, an initiative that aims to showcase Zanzibar as a sustainable tourist destination.¹⁸ As interest from tourists and hotels in buying more sustainable and local seafood grows (with Chumbe citing they know of at least 10-15 hotels interested), the guide provides an opportunity for Heshimu Bahari to engage with hotels and restaurants in Zanzibar to raise awareness about making more sustainable seafood buying choices and support local fishers and sustainable fisheries management. The guide can also serve as a starting point to identify key species the tourism industry is currently or is interested in sourcing, which can, in turn, enlighten information-gathering efforts and implementation of fishery management measures.

¹⁸ Greener Zanzibar – Zanzibar Tourism Investment and Travel Exhibition. <https://ztite.zanzibartourism.go.tz/greener-zanzibar/>

Key Actions and Strategies

- **Engage leading eco-resorts in Zanzibar in the Small Island Investors Forum** to share best practices on MMA/FRZ, community engagement, and artificial reef development.
- **Matching grant for Chumbe to lead training and capacity building** for interested small island investors and eco-resorts to conduct assessments, trainings, and other activities, with a focus on environmental sustainability and marine conservation issues unique to small islands,
- **Engage ZATI as a potential convener** to host and co-organize peer-to-peer learning and investor dialogues with Heshimu Bahari, Chumbe, and other leading eco-resorts to share best practices on sustainable island tourism management, marine conservation, and community engagement.
- **Promote a sustainable seafood guide to hotel operators and restaurants in Zanzibar**, in partnership with ZTC, to build awareness and interest among hotels on sustainable and local seafood sourcing. This includes engaging interested hotels and restaurants to encourage them to implement more sustainable and local fish sourcing. Additionally, to inform local sourcing, partner with the government and relevant community-based organizations to conduct assessments to gather better data on the status of key, in-demand fish.
- **Leverage Chumbe and other leading eco-resorts' connections** with ZATI and ZCT to advance the Greener Zanzibar Campaign and expand Heshimu Bahari's network of hotels and tourism operators in Zanzibar.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Chumbe Island Coral Park	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share best practices and train small island investors and eco-resorts in target seascapes on marine conservation, MMA management, and community engagement. • Bring and share experience in successful private sector-led MMA management, supporting scientific research, community engagement, and ranger training. • Leverage funding for training and capacity building activities.
ZATI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize and coordinate the forum for peer-to-peer hotel learning and investors dialogues for sharing best practices on sustainable island tourism management, marine conservation, and community engagement.
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage eco-resorts and ZATI to coordinate peer-to-peer capacity building on sustainable tourism and marine conservation involving eco-resorts and small island investors. • Provide matching grant funds for trainings in target seascapes. • Supply technical expertise, research capacity, and other resources to advance the implementation of sustainable and local fish sourcing connected with the seafood guide.
WCS/GFCR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential GFCR grant (currently under review) to Chumbe to strengthen the eco-resort's business model, including tourism activities offered, to increase revenue and ultimately expand its marine conservation efforts.
Eco-resorts and small island investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in training and capacity building activities. • Share best practices from their own operations and programs. • Adopt the sustainable seafood guide and engage in the sustainable sourcing of marine products.
Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries (MoBEF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide technical assistance, capacity building, and increased awareness related to marine conservation. • Provide regulatory oversight and support for MMA and community activities that involve permitting, licensing, and other government processes. • Participate in and provide technical experts to relevant MMA and activities that involve government roles and functions.

- Provide guidance and develop strong relationships with private sector stakeholders based in mutual trust and respect, and engage in effective collaboration for marine conservation every step of the way.

Justification and Impact

Founded in 1991, Chumbe is one of the most successful and longest running private sector led MPAs in Tanzania and around the world. Although Chumbe is not directly located in a target seascape, they do sit in between Seascapes #4 and # 5 in Unguja.¹⁹ The company’s objectives are non-commercial, with the aim to create a model of financially and ecologically sustainable park management, where ecotourism supports conservation efforts, scientific research, environmental education programs, and other benefits for local communities in Zanzibar.²⁰

Chumbe is positioned to provide effective training and lead capacity building activities on a range of environmental sustainability, marine conservation, and community development efforts, tailored in a way that works for other tourism businesses, such as eco-resorts, hotels, and new small island tourism investors. By engaging Chumbe to lead training and capacity building for these tourism sector stakeholders, Heshimu Bahari can help accelerate marine conservation and community resilience in MMAs.

For the sustainable seafood guide, Chumbe is already in the process of developing the guide and is engaged with ZTC as part of the Green Zanzibar campaign to promote it. By providing a matching grant, Heshimu Bahari will enable the creation more robust and impactful guide, while also leveraging the resources Chumbe contributes towards the guide’s development, along with the company’s connections in the tourism industry, to raise awareness on sustainable fisheries, marine conservation, and other Activity objectives. The guide will help build common understanding among Zanzibar’s hotels and restaurants around what constitutes responsible seafood sourcing. It will also enable greater local sourcing of seafood products that improves ocean health and local fishing communities’ livelihoods. Long-term it can increase demand from hotels and restaurants to buy more local and sustainable fish, incentivizing fishers to adopt and comply with sustainable fishing practices.

Source: WWF²¹ and SASSI websites²²

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Review concept with Heshimu Bahari team	x					
Prepare partnership concept note with Chumbe	x	x				
Explore inclusion of ZATI in the delivery of the partnership		x	x			
Draft and sign memorandum of understandings (MOUs)			x	x		

¹⁹ Jev-Mm. (2023, March 17). *A Review of the National Fisheries Management Plans For Tanzania*. EEOFISH Programme. <https://ecofish-programme.org/a-review-of-the-national-fisheries-management-plans-for-tanzania/>

²⁰ Chumbe Island Coral Park. (2023, August 10). *Chumbe Island Coral Park Zanzibar, private nature reserve & ecolodge*. Chumbe Island Coral Park - Zanzibar Ecobungalows. <https://chumbeisland.com/>

²¹ “A Sustainable Route from the Reef to the Plate” n.d.

²² “Business and Sustainable Seafood” n.d.

Develop detailed partnership workplan				x	x	
Determine and issue co-funding mechanism (matching grant)				x	x	
Support the rollout of the Sustainable Seafood Guide				x	x	x
Identify and launch other peer-to-peer capacity building activities for small island investors and eco-resorts					x	x

5.2.3 TOURISM AND MMA: ACCELERATE PRIVATE SECTOR-LED MMA MANAGEMENT BY PARTNERING WITH ZANZIBAR, TANGA AND PANGANI INVESTORS AND ECO-RESORTS TO ADVANCE MARINE CONSERVATION AND BUILD COMMUNITY LIVELIHOOD RESILIENCE.

Challenge

Many small independent eco-resorts operating in coastal areas and on islands in Tanzania, who are leaders in marine conservation and community development, find it difficult to expand these efforts and increase profitability. These eco-resorts identified several key barriers in the PSSA interviews:

- Limited ability to increase funding and staff capacity for marine conservation and communities, especially as these expenditures are treated as taxable income.
- Understanding of marine conservation beyond communities around the eco-resorts is low and requires significant effort to educate them on proper conservation activities.
- Monitoring and surveillance of fishing, FRZ and seasonal closures, and other marine activities is challenging and expensive.
- Government fees for entry to marine parks, reserves, and conservation areas are too low to fund adequate surveillance and management services.
- IUU fishing, the destruction of mangroves and other critical marine habitats are issues in most MMAs.
- Informal nature of livelihoods makes it difficult to source products from local communities, and the reluctance by fishers to pursue alternative livelihood makes it difficult to implement FRZs and closures.

Certain challenges are specific seascapes, such as in Pangani and Tanga, where there is limited financing available for conservation and community engagement due to the hotels struggling financially from low occupancy rates. Similarly, in mainland Tanzania, the MPRU, the government agency that was established under Marine Parks and Reserves Act No. 29 of 1994 for the management and administration of marine parks and reserves wants to convert all MMAs into marine parks, which would deprive communities a source of fishing and livelihoods.

Opportunity

Building on 5.2.1 above, Heshimu Bahari will start engaging Zanzibar small island investors located in target seascapes such as Bawe, Changuu, Kwata, Matumbini, Misali, and Pungume to identify interest and opportunities to build partnerships that will lead to the development and/or strengthening of private sector led FRZs and MMAs, and build community incentive and compliance mechanisms. In year 2, Heshimu Bahari will also engage already active eco-resorts located in target seascapes to explore partnerships for implementation in Year 3 and beyond that can develop and strengthen community-

supported, private sector co-managed FRZs in four Heshimu Bahari seascapes in **Bagamoyo (#3), Eastern Unguja (#9), Pangani (#2) and Tanga (#1)**.

Bagamoyo (#3)

A 12-room boutique hotel outside of Bagamoyo on a small peninsula Lazy Lagoon Island Lodge is part of the Foxes Safari Camps group, which operates other boutique safari lodges in or near national parks in Tanzania.²³ The lodge supports local communities through community development activities, engages with a BMU and government authorities to support beach cleanups and prevent dynamite fishing. The lodge fosters a healthy marine environment as a tourist attraction.

Eastern Unguja (#9)

Parent company &Beyond operates a 12-room Mnemba Island Lodge, a luxury eco-resort located in the Eastern Unguja seascape.²⁴ The lodge recently signed an agreement with MoBEF to manage an MMA located around Mnemba Island. &Beyond expressed interest in support to bolster its MMA management including its ranger program, training local boat captains (such as dolphin boats operating around the lodge on conservation) and support its "hustle economy" program that will provide small grants to SMEs in the surrounding communities.

Pangani (#2)

Located 15 km South of Pangani, this nature tourism-based lodge offers a variety of services including accommodation, marine sports, conservation tourism, and marine and nature tours. The lodge implements nature protection activities, including: the relocation of turtle nests for safety; coral reef restoration/plantation; marine patrols for nearby Maziwe island; monitoring of the local MMA and enforcement of fishing regulations; and mangrove planting and protection. The lodge also supports community livelihood initiatives, especially those involving products which can be supplied to the lodge.

Tanga (#1)

Established in 2009 and built amongst 10 acres of its own protected forest, this family run lodge is located 50 km north of Tanga City in the Mkinga district.²⁵ The owners are passionate about conservation and supporting community-based social and livelihood initiatives around the lodge, including restoring reefs; providing safe turtle nesting habitats; funding marine research and conservation projects; resorting and protecting mangroves; and facilitating marine patrols to monitor and enforce fishing and environmental regulations.

Launched in 2014 and located in Tanga Coelacanth Marine Park (TACMP), 30 km south of Tanga, the hotel provides beach cottage accommodations and other facilities, all built using traditional local materials. The hotel organizes marine tours and marine sports for guests; supports various conservation activities by working closely with the MPRU, such as sea turtle nest relocating for protection; and engages in community social and livelihood activities, including purchasing locally sourced supplies for their operations, such as food, flowers, and furniture.

Key Actions and Strategies

²³ "Lazy Lagoon Island Lodge by Foxes Safari Camps Tanzania" n.d.

²⁴ "AndBeyond Mnemba Island | Luxury Private Island in Zanzibar | Official Site" n.d.

²⁵ Fish Eagle Point Website, 2023. <https://www.fisheaglepoint.com>

Actions and strategies will vary based on each eco-resort, but the overall, Heshimu Bahari will provide targeted technical assistance, co-design and co-fund marine conservation and community livelihood activities tailored to the needs of each partner and eco-system. Other actions and strategies can include:

- **Document and share models on sustainable tourism and MMA management best practices** from these resorts and connect them to the Zanzibar Small Island Investor Forum.
- **Engage small island investors** managing or developing new hotels and resorts in Heshimu Bahari seascapes to build interest and engagement in developing and strengthening FRZs, implementing other MMA management measures, and supporting community incentives for FRZ compliance and building livelihood resilience.
- **Support interested eco-resorts to establish community co-management foundations** with formal offices and build their capacity to institutionalize the hotels' efforts for sustained conservation activities.
- **Engage women and youth in MMA management.** Building from Chumbe's and &Beyond's experience in training women for ranger and coral restoration roles, expand women's and youth's involvement in marine conservation activities connected to the eco-resorts.
- **Build capacity for community engagement**, including developing community benefit and incentive mechanisms for FRZ compliance.
- **Build capacity to enforce FRZ compliance**, including connecting to potential stakeholders such as WildAid assignment – adopting community approach where appropriate (building on the Maziwe model).
- **Provide technical support to biophysical monitoring**, especially fish biomass and benthic cover in FRZ associated with the eco-resort.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding in the form of grants to support marine conservation and community livelihood actions. • Connection to eco-resort peer-to-peer capacity building concept and engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihood initiatives. • Technical support to set up a foundation or fund for marine conservation.
Zanzibar Small island investors: Bawe, Changuu, Kwata, Matumbini, Misali, Pungume	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement in establishment of FRZ, co-management, and women and youth inclusion. • Community mobilization, local knowledge, and experience in marine conservation. • Co-funding marine conservation, restoration, and community livelihood initiatives in Heshimu Bahari seascapes, either via the business entity or associated foundations. • Participate in eco-resort peer-to-peer exchange to build greater capacity in marine conservation and share best practices with small new island investors. • Purchase products from local communities to support alternative and diversified livelihoods, and more sustainable, locally sourced marine products.
Established eco resorts: Fish Eagle Point, Emayan, Capricorn Beach Cottages, &Beyond, Lazy Lagoon Island Lodge, Thanda Island, Fanjove Island	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community mobilization, local knowledge, and experience in marine conservation. • Fund marine conservation including establishment of FRZ, restoration, and community livelihood initiatives in Heshimu Bahari seascapes, either via the business entity or associated foundations. • Participate in eco-resort peer-to-peer exchange to build greater capacity in marine conservation and share best practices with small new island investors. • Purchase products from local communities to support alternative and diversified livelihoods, and more sustainable, locally sourced marine products.

Chumbe Island Coral Park	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share best practices and train small island investors and eco-resorts in target seascapes on marine conservation, MMA management, and community livelihood/engagement.
WCS/GFCR and Blue Financing program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore viability and interest in financing the eco-resorts. • Provide financing and small loans for community livelihood initiatives and community-level fishers connected with the eco-resorts.
Government Agencies: MPRU and Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries (MLF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide regulatory oversight and support for MMA and community activities that involve permitting, licensing and other government processes. • Participate in and provide technical experts to relevant MMA trainings and activities that involve government roles and functions. • Provide equipment and physical infrastructure for community livelihoods activities (e.g., boats and equipment; shared service facility, etc.).

Justification and Impact

Partnering with eco-resorts has the potential to accelerate marine conservation and community resilience in four target seascapes: Bagamoyo (#3), Eastern Unguja (#9), Tanga (#1), and Pangani (#2). Each of the businesses focuses on nature-based tourism, has a history of supporting conservation and community development, and works closely with community institutions and government. Each eco-resort can provide matching funds and resources to advance shared goals with the Activity around building marine biodiversity and community reliance, further leveraging the impact of their partnership. Moreover, engaging eco-resorts can be a stepping stone to working with additional interested small island investors in Zanzibar, with the goal of developing similar partnerships to advance private sector investment in marine conservation and community resilience in other seascapes in Pemba and Unguja.

CASE STUDY

In 2019, the **USAID PROTECT project partnered with the Kwanini Foundation** (the organization that operates the Manta Resort) to expand the marine protection of 5,000 hectares in Northern Pemba through marine patrols, community education and awareness, coral reef and fish surveys, and beach cleanups. Kwanini also funded community development projects, leveraging guest and USAID funds to support priority community water and school infrastructure projects. USAID PROTECT provided a grant to the foundation, paving the way for the launch of a public-private community partnership through Blue Alliance.

Source: Kwanini Foundation website²⁶

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Determine which eco-resort partners to move forward with, and refine the list of potential activities and resource allocation	x					
Conduct follow-up meetings with each prioritized eco-resort to discuss potential activities and roles	x					

²⁶ Kwanini Foundation Website 2023, <http://kwaninifoundation.org/2020/07/07/usaaid-protect-update/#:~:text=On%20September%209th%2C%202019%2C%20the,year%20starting%20in%20July%202019.>

Develop final partnership concepts and secure internal approval		x				
Draft and sign MOUs with partners			x	x	x	
Co-develop detailed Year 1 partnership workplan					x	x

5.2.4 PPD: TANGA SUSTAINABLE TOURISM FORUM AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE DIALOGUE

Challenge

Located along the north coast of Tanzania, Tanga and Pangani are home to beautiful marine nature, resources, and scenery. Unfortunately, obstacles limit the growth potential of the tourism sector in these coastal areas:

- Limited effort by the government to promote and support Tanga’s tourism sector in coastal and marine areas when compared to inland regions in mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar.
- Comparatively high cost for tourists to visit the region because of limited flights, expensive hotels and transportation, and unfavorable government policies.
- Poor infrastructure of marine parks, communication networks, and transportation networks create hurdles for tourism-focused businesses to improve their services.
- Business closures by many tourism investors and hotel operators due to the COVID-19 economic downturn and generally burdensome government fees.

Moreover, inadequate marine conservation efforts have resulted in the destruction of mangrove forests, depletion of fisheries from IUU and overfishing, and lowering the overall attraction value of coastal and marine sites. While there have been a few instances of the private sector supporting marine conservation efforts, without more involvement from the fisheries department and MPRU, it will be extremely difficult for the situation to improve.

Opportunity

The Tanga Tourism Network Association (TATONA) is an umbrella organization representing key tourism businesses in the Tanga and Pangani regions, with 20+ active members, including hotel operators, tour operators, restaurant owners, transporters, and local craftspeople. TATONA has a tourism promotion office with an information center located in Tanga city, which is a focal point of activities and source of tourism information, online promotion, connection for other tourism operators with TATONA members, etc. The Association also regularly engages with MPRU and local government to advocate on issues relevant to members and other tourism businesses. Given TATONA’s focus on developing a culturally sensitive, socially responsible, and environmentally sustainable tourism sector, there is an opportunity for Heshimu Bahari to work with TATONA to promote increased involvement of investors in supporting effective MMA management in TACMP.

Key Actions and Strategies

Partner with TATONA to expand its advocacy and policy efforts among its members and key government stakeholders to develop an enabling environment for increasing regional private sector investment in tourism and marine conservation. Specific strategies include:

- **Facilitate PPD** that will involve TATONA, investors, the Hotel Association of Tanzania (HAT), MPRU, Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism (MNRT), Tanzania Tourism Board (TTB), MLF, WCS, and others to discuss and establish the enabling environment to agree on protocols for private sector involvement in TACMP and MIMP, for example including direct management of FRZs, blast-fishing and/or IUU surveillance, with corresponding tax/fee-related financial incentives to investors.

- **Engage with ongoing** European Union (EU) Blue Economy Program Sustainable Coastal Tourism Project to identify complementarity and synergy on improving the business environment in Tanzania coastal tourism sector.

Based on momentum and outcomes of the dialogues, Heshimu Bahari will engage TATONA and HAT to explore additional strategies and actions to mobilize resources from private sector, public sector, and other institutions to support tourism promotion, investment and tourism, and MMA management.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role and Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore potential collaboration opportunities with USAID Tuhifadhi Maliasili to support TATONA in advancing its advocacy including initiatives that promote gender inclusion. • Support in convening association meetings for advocacy and policy engagement on MMA investment and the tourism promotion forum. • Potential grant to TATONA for PPD and strengthen engagement of tourism investors in MMA management.
TATONA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-organize policy dialogues and tourism promotion forum for Tanga and Pangani. • Mobilize members for marine conservation, dialogues, tourism investments and promotion activities. • Bring on-the-ground experience and tourism sector knowledge.
HAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocacy and lobbying at the national level. • Source of expertise and information of mainland tourism sector. • Networking and outreach to members for participation in activities in Tanga and Pangani.
Government Agencies (MPRU, TTB, MNRT, and MLF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate and provide leadership in PPD and tourism promotion. • Co-funding for tourism promotion activities. • Support reforms to the fee and regulatory environment for marine parks, MMA and tourism investment, and involvement in MMAs in Tanga and Pangani regions.

Justification and Impact

TATONA is an umbrella organization representing key tourism businesses in the Tanga and Pangani region with keen interest in sustainable MMAs for hotels' seafood supply, recreational fisheries and other marine sports, and eco-tourism activities (e.g., scuba diving, snorkeling, and boat tours). Its members are involved in an important economic sector for the region, which generates substantial tax revenue and employment, and supports other local livelihoods such as horticulture, furniture production, and construction. The policy dialogues and tourism promotion forum can address the critical barriers limiting the growth of tourism in the region and private sector investment in marine conservation.

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Prepare partnership concept note			x			
Secure Heshimu Bahari management approval				x		
Draft and sign MOU					x	
Develop detailed partnership work plan					x	x

Determine and issues co-funding mechanism (matching grant)						x
Organize and carry-out a PPD with TATONA, members and key government partners						x

5.3 HIGH POTENTIAL PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTS

In addition to the quick win partnership concepts, the PSSA team identified several high potential partnership opportunities that require more development and review from the Heshimu Bahari technical team as part of an additional prioritization exercise. These opportunities offer high impact potential, close alignment with the Activity’s objectives, and strong interest from the prospective private sector partners. However, they will all require significant time and effort from Heshimu Bahari and potential partners to design and transition to implementation, with several requiring substantial resource allocation by the Activity. These factors will need careful consideration and assessment of level of effort required and anticipated impact compared to other PSE partnership opportunities.

5.3.1 VALUE CHAINS: STRENGTHEN FISHER COOPERATIVES IN TANGA AND PANGANI

Challenge

Small-scale fishers in Tanga and Pangani face significant barriers to earning a living income from their livelihood alone. Key challenges include:

- Limited ownership of boats forces small-scale fishers to pay for daily boat rentals. Moreover, lack of formal financing results in them taking informal loans with unfavorable terms for boat rentals and other fishing equipment and inputs.
- Poor and inefficient processing methods leads to lower-quality and high post-harvest loss, especially for dagaa fish (Swahili for “anchovy”), a key species for the region, which artisanal processors dry using firewood collected from mangroves and local forests leading to deforestation.
- Poor or non-existent post-harvest value chain infrastructure, such as cold chain storage, ice production, and transportation services, limits access to more higher value markets, causes greater post-harvest loss, and leads low prices paid to small-scale fishers.

Opportunity

The PSSA team identified two fisher cooperatives in the Tanga and Pangani region that expressed interest in helping its small-scale fisher members to increase access to markets, finance, and value addition inputs, as well as engage in sustainable fishing practices and the prevention of IUU fishing in NTZs.

1. **Kipumbwi Fisheries Cooperative Society Ltd (UWAWABIMA)** based in the Kipumbwi and Pangani Districts, has members in the fishing and processing of dagaa, selling up to 50 tons of each week. They sell mainly to Congo via traders and, to a more limited extent, Zambia via local agents.
2. **Deep-Sea Cooperative Society** based in Tanga City, whose members rent small boats for local small-scale fishers and sell the fish landed to several traders in Deep Sea fish market (who then in turn sell to the Tanga market and Dar es Salaam ferry market).

Key Actions and Strategies

Heshimu Bahari will strengthen the cooperatives and facilitate partnerships to support its members to reduce post-harvest loss and increase incomes through improved fish handling and processing practices, access to cold storage and processing technologies, and improved access to higher value markets. The

Activity will also work with the cooperatives to engage its members in adopting more sustainable fishing practices, compliance with NTZs, and other key co-management measures with BMUs. Moreover, Heshimu Bahari can demonstrate the successful partnerships with these two cooperatives and expand engagement to cooperatives in other seascapes. Specific means of support include:

- **Business Development Services (BDS) support** for fisher cooperative management and members on financial management and literacy, business planning, proper fish handling and processing, and other relevant practices.
- **Connect cooperatives with cost-effective financing** from several sources including the Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank (TADB), WCS Blue Financing Association/Groups program, and commercial finance partners like CRDB and Equity Bank.
- **Increase access to better markets** through value chain inputs, such as inputs to improve product quality and cold storage linkages, and by connecting cooperatives to companies that offer said inputs, such as YP Investments and Alphakrust Ltd.
- **Engage cooperatives in sustainable fisheries management** and NTZ initiatives to protect local fish stocks and reduce IUU fishing, with the long-term goal of increasing buy-in for these interventions by demonstrating the resulting increased incomes.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide grant funding, capacity building, and partnership facilitation to improve post-harvest handling, improve quality and increase access to markets. • Connect cooperatives to the Activity's other initiatives involving government and other donor/NGO fisheries management and support them for long-term behavior change initiatives around sustainable fisheries and NTZ management.
UWAWABIMA and Deep-Sea cooperatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage cooperative members in partnership activities with Heshimu Bahari and build commitment and buy-in from members to support sustainable fisheries. • Bring expertise and knowledge of local fishing sector context. • Contribute co-funding and resources (staff time, facilities, etc.) to capacity building activities for members.
Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank, WCS Blue Financing Groups program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide financing to cooperatives and members for actions that grow fisher operations and expand marine conservation efforts. • Potentially provide financial literacy and capacity building support to cooperative and its members.
Government Agencies (MPRU and MLF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance around the regulatory landscape for fisher cooperatives. • Assets such as physical infrastructure (e.g., boats and equipment) and shared service facilities to support fisher and processing operations. • Support during initiative roll-out and implementation.
Cold chain and processing firms (e.g., YP Investment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide technology and cold storage services appropriate to small-scale fishers. • Expertise growing a business in the mainland Tanzania fisheries sector. • Support cooperatives and fishers to improve market access.
Alphakrust Ltd	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential offtaker of cooperative member fish products.

Justification and Impact

The two cooperatives are key private sector stakeholders in the Tanga and Pangani seascapes' fisheries sector, offering Heshimu Bahari engagement with over 80 small-scale fisher and trader members. Strong

cooperatives with functioning management are important to support value addition, access to finance, and sustainable fisheries as working with individual small-scale fishers can be complicated, expensive, and ineffective. These cooperatives can play a key role in building awareness and buy-in from local fishers for adopting sustainable fishing practices and engaging with fisheries officers, MPRU and BMUs in monitoring, and compliance activities including reporting IUU fishing.

CASE STUDY

In 2020/2021, Bukasiga Fishery Cooperative Society in the Ukerewe Isles of Lake Victoria in Mwanza region set up two facilities that serve as key processing centers for local-micro and small-scale fishermen and traders. With a loan of TZS 200 million from **TADB** and a TZS 20 million grant from the **United Nations Development Program (UNDP)**, the cooperative was able to install (1) an anchovy solar-drying facility at a cost of TZS 130 million and (2) an ice production facility for preserving Nile perch fishes at a cost of TZS 90 million. The business plan was developed by a local BDS provider.

The main challenges the facilities addressed for anchovy fishers were high post-harvest loss and low-quality product due to ineffective drying techniques and difficulty drying anchovies during the rainy seasons. It also lowered the cost of inputs, highlighted by the ice production facility lowering the local cost of a 50kg bag of ice from TZS 90,000 to TZS 20, 000. Still, the five tons of ice per day the facility provides is not enough to meet local demand of 20 tons, promoting plans for the cooperative to further increase ice production.

Source: Republic of Tanzania Ministry of Livestock and Fisheries website²⁷

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Conduct follow-up meetings with cooperatives and prepare detailed partnership concept notes with each cooperative.		x	x			
Secure internal approval of the concept and partnership agreements.			x			
Draft and sign MOU with each cooperative and develop detailed partnership workplans.				x		

5.3.2 VALUE CHAINS: BUILD RESILIENT SEAWEED VALUE CHAINS AND COMMUNITIES THROUGH BUYER-LINKED APPROACH

Challenge

Production of red seaweed is declining in Tanzania despite ongoing investment by the government and private sector. This is due to several factors including inefficient farming and harvesting practices, post-harvest loss, and impacts of diseases caused by rapidly warming water and is compounded by the fact that seaweed biosecurity policies are lacking in Tanzania, responses to disease and pest outbreaks are not well

²⁷ Mtanzania. June 2020. <https://www.mifugouvuvuvi.go.tz/uploads/publications/swl591600998-Magazeti%20ya%20tarehe%2002-06-2020..pdf>

coordinated, and any existing control measures are in most cases not practiced by farmers.²⁸ With income-levels of most seaweed farmers already being low, and many seaweed farming communities having high economic, social, and climate vulnerability, these additional challenges only magnify the issues they face.

Moreover, seaweed is often produced in important marine areas with high biodiversity, such as coral reefs and seagrass beds, which has led to environmental degradation and loss of biodiversity.²⁹ Without proper zoning and management, the expansion of seaweed production, including the potential transition to deeper water production to adapt to warming seas, could have negative impacts on coral reef systems. Examples of harmful seaweed farming practices include the use of mangrove trees as wooden stakes, which impacts critical mangrove systems, and waste from farms, like nylon ropes, which can contribute to ocean plastic pollution and impact marine mammals.

Opportunity

Seaweed is among the most environmentally productive plants on the planet, capturing carbon more efficiently than tropical forests, reversing ocean acidification and eutrophication, and helping to build up depleted fish stocks.³⁰ With marine resources declining, seaweed farming can provide coastal communities with alternative sources of income to complement traditional livelihoods such as fishing, without damaging natural resources. As the Tanzanian seaweed industry employs over 25,000 farmers, most of whom are women, the opportunity to capture these benefits also exists in Heshimu Bahari seascapes.³¹

Cargill, the global industrial food conglomerate, is currently the largest buyer of red seaweed produced in Tanzania. They process the seaweed for its carrageenan, a naturally occurring substance the seaweed produces, which is then used as an additive for over 300 ingredient products in food, beverage, and pharmaceuticals. In 2019, Cargill launched the ‘Red Seaweed Promise’ program to address key sustainability challenges for harvesting red seaweed while also enhancing producer livelihoods, supporting local communities, and conserving the marine environment. The company is committed to sourcing 60 percent sustainable red seaweed by 2025, and is interested in improving the marine habitats where seaweed grows, along with promoting plastic circularity in the production of seaweed.³² Its Tanzanian partner, C-WEED Corporation (C-WEED), has a network of over 5,000 seaweed farmers in Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania and invests in them to produce quality red seaweed.³³ There is an opportunity to partner with these two organizations to further develop and strengthen the seaweed sector in the target seascapes while promoting the livelihood and climate aspects associated with it to drive impact.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise from staff and implementing partners, and co-funding to conduct marine conservation, restoration, and climate vulnerability studies. • Co-financing of value chain and livelihood resilience activities. • Capacity building for C-WEED on marine conservation and restoration.

²⁸ Charisiadou, Stefania, Christina Halling, Narriman Jiddawi, Kristina von Schreeb, Martin Gullström, Terése Larsson, and Lina Mtwana Nordlund. 2022. “Coastal Aquaculture in Zanzibar, Tanzania.” *Aquaculture* 546 (January): 737331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737331>.

²⁹ Hehre, E. James, and Jessica J. Meeuwig. 2016. “A Global Analysis of the Relationship between Farmed Seaweed Production and Herbivorous Fish Catch.” Edited by Konstantinos I Stergiou. *PLOS ONE* 11 (2): e0148250. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148250>.

³⁰ Cargill Red Seaweed Promise Progress Report 2021. <https://www.cargill.com/doc/1432198890865/sustainable-seaweed-red-seaweed-promise-progress-report.pdf>

³¹ “The Promise of Restorative Aquaculture Solutions.” n.d. The Nature Conservancy. <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-insights/perspectives/restorative-aquaculture-seaweed-farms-tanzania/>.

³² *Sustainable Seaweed | Cargill*. (n.d.). <https://www.cargill.com/sustainability/sustainable-seaweed>

³³ “About Us – Tanzania C-Weed Corporation.” n.d. Accessed October 30, 2023. <https://cweed.com/about-us/>.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging government partners to support private sector-led investment in seaweed communities and value chains.
Cargill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buyer commitment to sourcing sustainable seaweed. Global technical expertise in seaweed production and sourcing. Co-investment in enhancing seaweed value chains, building resilient community livelihoods, and strengthening marine conservation and restoration efforts.
C-WEED Corporation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access to its network of up to 205,000 seaweed producers. Provide equipment, production inputs, and training to seaweed producers to improve productivity and quality. Co-investment in building diversified and resilient livelihoods.
MoBEF, Ministry of Livestock & Fisheries, local governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide incentives or assurances for C-WEED and other companies to invest in seaweed-producing communities. Support marine spatial planning and zoning for the exploration of deep-water seaweed production. Participate in the design and implementation of climate adaptation and resilience programs for vulnerable communities.

Key Actions and Strategies

The overall strategy is to work jointly with Cargill and C-WEED to engage with seaweed producing communities in Zanzibar (and potentially mainland Tanzania) to improve productivity, increase access to technology and financing, and conserve/restore marine resources. Specific actions include:

- **Build on Cargill's socio-economic and vulnerability research** in seaweed producing communities in Tanzania to identify highly vulnerable seaweed farmers in Heshimu Bahari seascapes. Use data to develop and co-invest in resilient livelihood and value chain enhancement initiatives for these communities.
- **Conduct marine conservation and restoration research** to identify the impacts of seaweed production on critical marine habitats in the seascapes. Based on research and in partnership with local communities, implement initiatives to protect and restore seagrass meadows, coral beds, and mangroves forests within the cultivation areas.
- **Increase seaweed quality and productivity** by providing seaweed farmers with inputs such as quality equipment for production and capacity building on good cultivation and drying practices.
- **Assess the climate vulnerability risks** of rising water temperatures and diseases on shallow water production in target seascapes, develop seaweed management and climate adaptation plans for major growing areas, and identify the adaptation and resilience activities and investments needed to support seaweed farmers and communities.
- **Engage C-WEED Corporation and the governments of Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania in dialogue** to explore the potential of them providing protections and incentives for C-WEED and other seaweed companies that are making positive investments in seaweed producing communities and marine conservation.

Justification and Impact

Considering the strong geographic alignment between the companies' seaweed producing communities and Activity's target seascapes both in Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania, along with the fact that seaweed aquaculture can serve as an alternative livelihood to the fishing sector to reduce pressure on fish stocks while also providing employment opportunities for women, this partnership concept offers high impact potential and alignment with Heshimu Bahari Objectives. The partnership focuses on addressing climate

vulnerability and building resilient value chains and communities, a major component of the expanded Heshimu Bahari scope.

Moreover, both Cargill and C-WEED have expressed interested in marine conservation, addressing climate change, and strengthening livelihoods. Cargill is committed to source 60 percent sustainable red seaweed by 2025³⁴, and is interested in improving the marine habitats where its seaweed is sourced, including promoting plastic circularity in the production of seaweed. C-WEED is committed to minimizing the environmental impact around its seaweed production, including shifting to more sustainable inputs to help curb the depletion of mangroves and preventing seaweed farming materials from drifting into the ocean. Cargill already provides grants to C-WEED and has expressed interest in scaling this work to other seascapes and communities in partnership with Heshimu Bahari.

CASE STUDY

USAID/Madagascar partnered with Ocean Farmers and Indian Ocean Trepang to create sustainable blue economies through scalable market-based aquaculture of seaweed and sea cucumber. The initiative supports farmers' efforts to adopt strategies that both generate high financial returns and contribute to coastal and marine ecosystem conservation. USAID contributed USD \$2.5 million to the USD \$6.5 million partnership. Oceans Farmers supply seaweed to Cargill and committed to The Red Seaweed Promise™.

Source: USAID/Madagascar factsheet ³⁵

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Share information on Heshimu Bahari seascapes with Cargill to identify overlap between the key communities in their supply chains and the Activity's target seascapes.	x					
Conduct a follow-up meeting with C-WEED to discuss their role and priorities to refine the partnership concept.	x					
Set up a call with Ocean Farmers to learn and incorporate lessons from the USAID partnership in Madagascar.		x				
Coordinate Heshimu Bahari's socio-economic baseline studies with Cargill's social assessments.			x			
Develop detailed partnership concept note, and review with the technical team as part of the prioritization workshop/exercise.		x	x			
Move forward with MOU process if prioritized.				x		

5.3.3 FINANCE: PARTNER WITH GFCR TO CO-INVESTMENT IN MARINE CONSERVATION AND SUSTAINABLE FISHERIES

Challenge

³⁴ Sustainable Seaweed | Cargill. (n.d.). <https://www.cargill.com/sustainability/sustainable-seaweed>

³⁵ USAID/Madagascar Nosy Manga Factsheet. February 2022. https://ocean-farmers.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Final-Fact-Sheet_Nosy-Manga-February-2022_English_03_07_2022.pdf

Sustainable financing is a major barrier to coral reef conservation and restoration. The GFRC meets this challenge through their blended finance instrument used to mobilize action and resources to protect and restore coral reef ecosystems. Run by WCS, the fund’s global footprint and flexible financing options make it an effective investment vehicle for funding innovative business models that increase the resilience of coral reefs and their surrounding communities³⁶. Although the fund currently has presence in Tanzania, it has faced challenges finding deal pipeline of bankable reef-positive projects to invest in, limiting its ability to deploy capital in the country. Additionally, GFCR’s mandate ensures they are focused on revenue generating businesses that must have a direct impact on coral reef conservation and/or restoration. This narrow lens makes it even more difficult to find businesses who can meaningfully affect coral reef conservation and are willing to take steps towards scaling greater coral reef conservation.

Opportunity

GFCR offers USD \$250 million in blended finance to mobilize resources to protect and restore coral reef ecosystems, and regionally, WCS manages the GFCR ‘Miamba Yetu’ program that aims to deploy USD six million grant support for businesses in Tanzania and to mobilize co-investments of over USD \$40 million in the next eight to ten years. The types of revenue-generating businesses and investments GFCR pursues include (1) eco-tourism; (2) sustainable fisheries and aquaculture; (3) MPAs with user fees; (4) blue carbon; (5) recycling; (6) water treatment; and (7) alternative activities for subsistence and income. GFCR offers a dual fund structure:

1. **USD \$125 million grant facility** that supports (1) financial structuring; (2) technical assistance; (3) capacity development; (4) development of policy; (5) background research; (6) monitoring and evaluation; (7) recoverable grants; and (8) “blue” stimulus packages.
2. **USD \$125 million investment fund** with combination of concessionary capital (guarantees, concessionary loans, and early equity investments) to de-risk the overall investment, and impact capital (debt, equity, and bonds) for SMEs and start-ups used to fill gaps in the capital stack.

Given the significant alignment in GFCR’s mission and Heshimu Bahari objectives, there is opportunity to source co-funding for grants and investments for businesses addressing coral reef conservation.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect small island tourism investors in Zanzibar and GFCR/Miamba Yetu. • Develop a pipeline of potential businesses and investors in the tourism and/or fisheries sectors in target seascapes that meet GFCR’s reef positive criteria. • Capacity building and technical assessments to support businesses in preparation for GFCR investment, and de-risking grants for co-investment with GFCR in specific opportunities that support marine conservation.
GFCR/WCS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Up to USD \$40 million in coral reef financing through Miamba Yetu program and potential to leverage additional funding from GFRC across a wide range of financing tools to invest in marine conservation in target seascapes. • Technical expertise in marine and coral reef conservation. • Support due diligence process to better understand the viability of specific marine conservation investment opportunities.

Key Actions and Strategies

³⁶ Home | Global Funds for Coral Reefs. (2023, May 8). Global Funds for Coral Reefs. <https://globalfundcoralreefs.org/>

The overall strategy is for Heshimu Bahari to partner with the regional Miamba Yetu program to build a pipeline of investable businesses interested in coral reef conservation and restoration, as well as provide technical assistance and catalytic grants to enable further investment by GFCR in the target seascapes. Specific actions within this strategy include:

- **Engage GFCR in the Zanzibar Small Island Investors Forum:** GFCR already participated in the initial Zanzibar Small Island Investors Forum and has been included in the subsequent working group established following the meeting with ZIPA, MoBEF, and Heshimu Bahari. Engage GFCR through the Forum and associated activities, as well as develop a process to share potential investment opportunities between Heshimu Bahari and GFCR.
- **Identify and evaluate investment opportunities in mainland Tanzania** that met GFCR reef positive criteria, are in the target seascapes, and are aligned with Heshimu Bahari's objectives.
- **Provide technical assistance and investment preparation** for potential businesses.
- **Co-finance marine conservation investments** through a combination of GFCR financing and Heshimu Bahari grants to de-risk and catalyze additional investment from other private investors.
- **Work with GFCR and WCS** on the voluntary carbon credit scheme they are currently working on in the Northern Tanga region involving mangroves.

Justification and Impact

GFCR is closely aligned to Heshimu Bahari's objectives and their regional grants facility, Miamba Yetu, is managed by WCS, an implementing partner/subcontractor on the Activity. WCS has already expressed willingness to collaborate with the Activity through their GFCR work, including utilizing a large pool of grant and concessionary finance that the Activity could leverage for its marine conservation programming. By working together, the Activity is uniquely positioned to fill gaps in GFCR's current Tanzania-based operations, leveraging the resources between the two projects to create even greater impact for marine conservation in the target seascapes.

Examples of previous GFCR investments in Tanzania which the Activity should seek to replicate include:

- USD \$350,000 for Blue Finance to support the North Pemba Channel Conservation Area (PECCA) MMA in the development of a second underwater room operated by the Manta Resort. The investment also funded MPA scientific and surveillance equipment for their Blue Alliance private sector-led MMA management program.
- A pending grant to Chumbe Island Coral Park to identify ways to strengthen its business model and generate more revenue to support its marine conservation efforts, along with additional community development activities.

CASE STUDY

Marine Change, a consultancy engaged in the **USAID/Indonesia Ber-IKAN project**, introduced **Mirova-Althelia Sustainable Oceans Fund (SOF)** to a successful tuna exporter, Chen Woo Fishery (CWF), guiding an investment process spanning 15 months. SOF is a USD \$125 million impact investment vehicle supporting sustainable oceans and fisheries resources. Based in France, SOF had little knowledge of Indonesia. Meanwhile, Indonesian fisheries companies are accustomed to interacting with local banks rather than foreign investors. As result, SOF invested USD \$10 million in CWF to build a tuna processing facility increasing export market access for small-scale fishers. Marine Change recently brokered a partnership between USAID Ber-IKAN and CWF to support sustainable fisheries management and marine biodiversity.

Sourced from PSSA Team Lead and USAID Ber-IKAN Communication Specialist³⁷

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Develop a partnership concept note to identify roles, resource contribution, focus seascapes and joint activities for Year 2.	x					
Engage GFCR in the Zanzibar Small Island Investors Forum.		x	x	x	x	x
Share information on small island investors that express interest in marine conservation and identify potential areas of alignment with the GFCR impact and investment requirements.			x	x		
Build a joint pipeline of businesses with potential positive coral reef conservation and restoration impacts, including the small island investors, existing eco resorts, and fisheries related companies.				x	x	x

5.3.4 TOURISM/MMA: SCALE THE BLUE ALLIANCE ZANZIBAR BLUE ECONOMY CORRIDOR IN PEMBA CHANNEL CONSERVATION AREA

Challenge

MMA's are a proven tool to build marine ecosystem resilience, while also boosting fishing incomes for coastal communities; however, globally 70 percent of MMA's struggle to meet minimum management standards due to insufficient and short-term funding, which is largely provided by governments, NGOs and other donors.³⁸ In PECCA, intrusion of illegal fishers, weak enforcement of regulations, limited community support, lack of enforcement facilities, and generally scarce community knowledge about marine conservation is prevalent. Major barriers to successful management of PECCA include lack of sustainable financing, capacity of patrols, enforcement of existing management regulation and plans, and provision of incentives to communities.

Opportunity

In August 2023, Blue Finance, a social enterprise that manages MPAs for governments around the world, launched a collaborative arrangement with the MoBEF in Zanzibar called the 'Blue Alliance' to manage the northern part of the PECCA, with the aim to protect 17,000 ha of marine ecosystems and improve the livelihoods and food security of an estimated 8,000 households. Their planned management and operations in PECCA include community development through employment, micro-enterprise development, and empowerment; wildlife monitoring and conservation through robust science; revenue stream development through sustainable eco-tourism and responsible aquaculture; and compliance through patrolling, community engagement and awareness campaigns.

With the support of the GFCR, Ocean Risk and Resilience Alliance (ORRAA), several impact investors and donors, Blue Finance has established an MMA blended finance facility that will provide up-front, and

³⁷ Tjiptohandono, D. A. (2023, September 26). https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dwiaryotjiptohandono_sustainablefisheries-indonesia-usaidberikan-activity-7112322989026676736-Rwyg?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

³⁸ Establishing a blended finance facility for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) - Blue Finance - ORRAA. (2023, June 23). ORRAA. <https://oceanriskalliance.org/project/establishing-a-blended-finance-facility-for-marine-protected-areas-mpas/>

early-stage blended capital for Blue Alliance Zanzibar. The revenues generated from a range of sustainable sources, such as eco-tourism fees and sustainable artisanal aquaculture, will create tangible returns for investors and demonstrable impact for donors. Blue Alliance is also investing in a new fisheries company, Samaki Bluu, which will engage small-scale fishers in Pemba to source and supply high-quality and more sustainable fish to hotels in Zanzibar.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grant funds that could potentially be used as catalytic grant funding to unlock impact investing funds for Blue Alliance enterprises. Ability to act as a convening party to bring together relevant stakeholders that can potentially support Blue Alliance MMA and livelihoods/enterprise activities. Connect interested communities in East Pemba (#8) and Misali and Matumbini Islands (#7) seascapes to the sea cucumber hatchery/enterprise.
Blue Finance/Alliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proven private sector led MMA management and formal agreement with the MoBEF. Inhouse technical expertise in developing sustainable blue economy enterprises. Network of interest impact investors willing to invest capital in marine conservation and community development. Willingness to expand to other seascapes in Tanzania.
Manta Resort /Kwanini Foundation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate as a private sector member of Blue Alliance. Share best practices with small new island investors. Support enterprise and microfinance solutions to community members.
Samaki Bluu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging artisanal fishers to implement better management practices, provide training and equipment, and secure a higher price by supplying hotels in Zanzibar.

Key Actions and Strategies

- **Catalytic grant to Blue Alliance to support the sea cucumber enterprise rollout.** They are seeking a USD \$750,000 grant, which can mobilize 3x investment from impact investors, or Heshimu Bahari can contribute partial funding and request additional co-funding from other partners. A successful sea cucumber hatchery could support communities in Heshimu Bahari seascapes in East Pemba (#8), Misali and/or Matumbini Islands in PECCA (#7).
- **Include Blue Alliance in the Zanzibar Small Island Investor Forum** and conduct exchanges with inventors and other stakeholders operating in target seascapes in Zanzibar to share Blue Alliance's experiences in MMA management and enterprise development in North PECCA.

Other actions to consider include to (1) co-invest in other enterprises connected to Blue Alliance, such as Samaki Bluu and; (2) explore expanding the Blue Alliance management area to South PECCA and East Pemba in collaboration with the MoBEF, local government and communities, WCS, and relevant small island investors.

Justification and Impact

Blue Alliance is interested in working with Heshimu Bahari and can bring up to a 3x leverage ratio from private sector investors to a partnership. Blue Finance is a social enterprise that develops solutions for the effective management and sustainable financing of MMAs and has forged strong partnerships with Governments and more than 30 international conservation partners and financial institutions globally.

While North PECCA is not an official target seascape, the sea-cucumber enterprise Blue Alliance is developing can benefit all communities in Pemba, including those in Heshimu Bahari seascapes. Moreover, Blue Alliance brings a unique and sustainable model to financing MMAs via private investors and nature-based enterprises. By investing in this immediate opportunity in North PECCA, Heshimu Bahari can help shape future expansion plans to other MMAs in Pemba. Additionally, while they are not ready to partner yet, Samaki Bluu also has the potential to provide multiple benefits to fisher communities in Pemba through access to higher value markets and improved fisheries management.

Case Study

In 2020, Blue Finance, in collaboration with the Department of Environment and Natural Resources in the Philippines, created **Blue Alliance Philippines** to manage the MMA network in North Oriental Mindoro with local authorities. The network comprises 12 MMAs, which together protect some 70 km of coastline and 52km² of coastal marine ecosystems, including a UNESCO biosphere reserve. Through a Philippines-based coalition of local and international actors, Blue Alliance Philippines is working to facilitate management concessions for MMAs, develop tangible sustainable revenue models, and secure up-front financing by attracting blended finance capital to address the traditional MMA funding gap.

UBS Optimus Foundation recently invested in the MMA network to provide up-front, and early-stage blended capital to implement several blue economy revenue-generating initiatives, while focusing on protecting and regenerating coral reefs, increasing marine biodiversity, and enhancing livelihoods. Initial revenue models include MMA nature fees, a visitor center, and sales of blue carbon credits. Further, the program will unlock finance for reef-positive business models (e.g., eco-resorts, coastal aquaculture, etc.) that will, in return, ensure synergies with conservation objectives and contribute to financing for MMA management cost.

Sources: Blue Alliance website³⁹ and Carbon Pulse⁴⁰

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Review concept with Heshimu Bahari technical team on alignment and determine if there is interest in moving forward.	x	x				
<i>If prioritized to move forward</i> , sign a nondisclosure agreement (NDA) with Blue Alliance to receive the investment thesis for the sea cucumber hatchery business and other relevant enterprises.			x			
<i>If prioritized to move forward</i> , explore with Blue Alliance other co-founding partners to match Heshimu Bahari's funds.				X	x	
<i>If prioritized to move forward</i> , develop a detailed partnership concept note and appropriate agreement.					x	x

³⁹ In The News | Blue Alliance. (2023, October 26). Blue Alliance. <https://bluealliance.earth/in-the-news/>

⁴⁰ Impact loan to set Philippines MPAs on track to economic independence « Carbon Pulse. (n.d.). <https://carbonpulse.com/222458/>

5.3.5 FINANCE: UNLOCK FINANCING FOR SMEs AND COOPERATIVES IN BLUE ECONOMY SECTORS

Challenge

SMEs in fisheries and non-fisheries value chains in the target seascapes lack the financing and investment needed for growth, with many small-scale producers not having access to commercial financial services at all due to low credit needs, volatile income streams, and lack of traditional collateral. This is partially due to commercial financial institutions having limited internal capacity and knowledge to issue loans for SMEs in blue economy sectors like aquaculture and fisheries. Without this knowledge, it increases risk and makes them less likely to deploy these funds to SMEs in the sector. Additionally, commercial banks are not currently conducting feasibility or baseline studies on most blue economy sectors in the communities they operate in, adding another layer of risk and making them even more hesitant to deploy these funds. While CRDB and Equity Bank have provided loans to some businesses in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, these are generally for larger businesses with traditional assets available to use as collateral.

Opportunity

Heshimu Bahari can assist SMEs in the target seascapes gain access to commercial financial services to help scale their businesses. By doing so, SMEs can bolster the efficiency of fisheries and non-fisheries value chains, build more resilient livelihoods in coastal communities, and reduce pressure on marine resources. Several financial institutions and funds have been identified that are interested in deploying capital towards blue economy SMEs (and potentially cooperatives) including:

- **CRDB Bank** is developing a USD \$200 million blue economy climate adaptation fund with an anticipated USD \$100 million contribution from the UN Green Climate Fund (GCF).
- **Equity Bank** recently started providing loans for SMEs and cooperatives in blue economy sectors and has an extensive agent model to reach coastal communities.
- **Small Enterprise Assistance Fund (SEAF)** operates a revolving fund and provides conditional loans targeting SMEs with positive impact on women and youth.

These financial institutions are motivated to provide financing and partner with Heshimu Bahari to expand access to finance in coastal communities. More detail is included in the Annex 3 partner profiles.

Key Actions and Strategies

- **Engage with financial institutions** to understand how Heshimu Bahari resources can best be leveraged to unlock more marine conservation-conscience blue economy financing (i.e., Development Finance Corporation Development Credit Authority (DFC-DCA) first-loss guarantee, blue economy capacity training for bank staff, and/or feasibility studies).
- **Develop specific blue economy loan products** to ensure the type of financing the financial institutions provide drives impact for coastal community SME development, livelihoods, marine conservation, and sustainability. Support the banks and funds to conduct several different types of assessments for loans, namely EIAs, feasibility studies, and landscape analyses.
- **Identify a pipeline of blue economy SMEs** operating in Heshimu Bahari seascapes that require debt financing and provide them with BDS and/or financial support to prepare them for commercial financing.
- **Provide financial institutions with capacity training and technical assistance** on the blue economy, both from a corporate and local branch perspective, to increase their familiarity with the space and reduce the associated risks.

- **Create incentives and mechanisms** to tie SME financing with sustainable fisheries and marine conservation (including NTZs) to ensure funds leveraged for the blue economy also have a positive effect on marine conservation.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building for financial institutions' staff on marine conservation and BDS to prepare cooperatives and SMEs to receive bank financing. • Conduct and share marine conservation baseline surveys. • Connection with DFC for potential loan guarantee products, and co-financing/de-risking via grants.
CRDB, Equity Bank	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing and commercial loan products for fisher cooperatives and SMEs connected with Heshimu Bahari. • Financial literacy and capacity training for cooperatives and SMEs. • Coverage across most of mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar • Potential climate adaptation financing via a new GCF climate adaptation fund.
SEAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catalytic funding (grants/loans) for blue economy SMEs. • Post investment technical assistance. • Expertise in setting up and running a fund in Tanzania (offshore). • Support SME growth connected to youth and women livelihoods.
GCF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant facility and climate financing to de-risk financing to SMEs and support climate adaptation and resilience solutions.

Justification and Impact

Private sector financing leveraged for the blue economy with a marine conservation-lens can grow the blue economy for local communities, build resilient livelihoods, and bolster marine conservation efforts in the targeted seascapes. Developing more blue economy financing builds capacity and track record with these finance providers, increasing the likelihood they will continue these types of investments in the future. The three institutions included in this concept seem highly motivated to expand financing to coastal communities and blue economy SMEs, an untapped market and emphasis for the government (especially in Zanzibar), while also having a focus on environmental sustainability and empowering communities:

- **SEAF** is implementing a new 5-year Daraja Impact program, in partnership with AlphaMundi Foundation, which supports enterprises through the provision of capital and technical assistance to advance economic inclusion and empowerment for women and youth.
- **CRDB Bank** is accredited with the UN GCF as a financial intermediary and executing entity for green projects that reduce or limit greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to the challenges of climate change and its impact. USAID and DCF have partnered with CRDB already (see case study below).
- **Equity Bank's** philosophy is to transform the lives and livelihoods of people socially and economically by availing them modern, inclusive financial services that maximize their opportunities. The bank works with the Zanzibar government to finance seaweed farming and provides financing to community-level savings groups.

Case Study

USAID/Tanzania and DFC partnered with CRDB Bank to facilitate TZS 100 billion in loans to expand access to finance for women and youth borrowers, the education and health sectors, MSMEs, and the informal sector. The types of loan products include the following areas: financial support for working capital, equipment procurement, construction, and restructuring of commercial properties for business.

CRDB Bank signed an agreement with GCF to launch a climate adaptation lending facility for smallholder farmers and agribusinesses in Tanzania. Using concessional resources from GCF, CRDB Bank launched three new financial products to support local agribusiness: (1) a dedicated credit line for climate adaptation technologies and practices; (2) a credit guarantee facility to expand access to new borrowers; and; (3) a weather-indexed insurance product to help protect against losses from climate-related events.

Sourced from the USAID and Green Climate Fund websites.⁴¹⁴²

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Conduct follow-up meetings with each financial institution to better understand interests and alignment with Heshimu Bahari's target stakeholders and communities	x	x				
Identify the financing needs and readiness for SMEs, cooperatives, and value chains in target seascapes and communities		x	x			
Review concepts and stakeholder financing needs in the prioritization workshop to determine fit with Activity objectives, understand the seascapes/locations, and identify target stakeholders.			x	x		

5.3.6 TOURISM AND MMA: ACCELERATE PRIVATE SECTOR-LED MMA MANAGEMENT BY PARTNERING WITH KILWA, MAFIA, AND MTWARA ECO-RESORTS TO ADVANCE MARINE CONSERVATION AND BUILD COMMUNITY LIVELIHOOD RESILIENCE

Challenge

Insufficient government funding has made it difficult to effectively manage MMAs, including marine parks and reserves under the MPRU and TAWA portfolio. Despite the leading role played by Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara eco-resorts in supporting marine patrols, several challenges have made it difficult for small independent eco-resorts to expand their efforts. Limited government support for coastal tourism in Tanzania has resulted in low tourism activities and poor income to coastal eco-lodges in Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara compared to those under Tanzania National Parks (TANAPA) and ZCT. Moreover, the ongoing conflict in northern Mozambique has caused tourism to the southern coast of Tanzania to come to a halt, particularly in the Lindi and Mtwara regions.

⁴¹ CRDB Bank, USAID, and DFC unlock TZS 100BN in Tanzania for education, health, Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) and the informal sectors | Tanzania | Press release | U.S. Agency for International Development. (2022, June 30). U.S. Agency For International Development. <https://www.usaid.gov/tanzania/>

⁴² Fund, G. C. (2022, June 26). GCF and CRDB Bank Plc. sign agreement to boost access to climate. Green Climate Fund. [https://www.greenclimate.fund/news/gcf-and-crdb-bank-plc-sign-agreement-boost-access-climate-adaptation-technologies#:~:text=The%20Green%20Climate%20Fund%20\(GCF,CHOGM\)%20in%20Kigali%2C%20Rwanda.](https://www.greenclimate.fund/news/gcf-and-crdb-bank-plc-sign-agreement-boost-access-climate-adaptation-technologies#:~:text=The%20Green%20Climate%20Fund%20(GCF,CHOGM)%20in%20Kigali%2C%20Rwanda.)

The COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the situation for the tourism industry, leading to the closure of many businesses and halting marine conservation activities. The increasing tax burden and inflation have impacted the profitability and financial support for conservation and community livelihoods. The limited tourism activities require higher revenue from marine park fees to fund surveillance and management services, posing a challenge for eco-lodges to increase their funding and staff capacity. Surveillance of marine activities is expensive and challenging, with significant issues of IUU fishing, destruction of critical habitats, and low understanding of marine conservation.

Opportunity

Accelerate private sector-led MMA management in partnership with leading eco-resorts in two Heshimu Bahari seascapes in Mafia -Kilwa(#11) and Mtwara (#12).

Mafia (#11)	
	Chole Mjini TreeHouse Lodge was established in 1993 in Chole Island located in the Mafia Island Marine Park (MIMP) and offers marine and cultural tourism including unique accommodation using seven tree houses (cholemjini.com). The lodge employs mostly local community members and has its own extensive conservation projects including community and youth conservation education, scientific research, and support to coral reef protection and restoration.
	Kinasi Lodge is a boutique hotel on Mafia Island with 15 suites and two double story villas. The lodge overlooks Chole Bay within the Mafia Island Marine Park and offers panoramic views of Chole, Juani and Jibondo islands. Kinasi Lodge supports marine conservation, social and livelihood projects, and collaborates with MPRU and NGOs for marine conservation and sustainable fishing programs. (kinasilodge.com)
	Thanda Island is a private island with exclusive villa accommodation and a variety of water and marine activities. The island supports extensive marine conservation and social and livelihood projects for the surrounding communities. Thanda Island partners with MPRU and other NGOs for marine conservation programs and educational projects, including the Star for Life program, which is taught in six primary and two secondary schools in the Mafia Island. They also manage the MPRU patrol outpost. (thanda-island)
Kilwa (#11)	
	Fanjove Private Island, owned by Selous Safari Company, is located in the Songo Islands archipelago. The island features an enormous lagoon and 11 km of coral reef, and the lodge provides 10 eco-friendly villas for guests. They actively support marine conservation and livelihood activities and have successfully implemented projects that provide social services support, seaweed farming support, and coral reef protection and restoration for the local community (fanjove-island).
Mtwara (#12)	
	The lodge is a small retreat on the Western Indian Ocean in Mikindani, Tanzania. It offers comfortable accommodation with views of Mikindani Bay. The lodge also owns eco2 diving, a marine center that offers diving activities and exploration of the coral reefs. Additionally, the lodge runs various marine conservation and community projects and

	partners with the MPRU for conservation activities in and around Mnazi Bay-Ruvuma Estuary Marine Park (MBREMP) (tendegreessouth.com).
--	--

Key Actions and Strategies

Actions and strategies will vary based on each eco-resort, but overall, Heshimu Bahari will provide targeted technical assistance, co-design, and co-fund marine conservation and community livelihood activities tailored to the needs of each partner and ecosystem. Other actions and strategies can include:

- **Facilitate the establishment of FRZ** or strengthening of existing FRZ in areas managed by one of the eco-hotels.
- **Support interested eco-resorts to establish community foundations** with formal offices and build their capacity to institutionalize the hotels' efforts for sustained conservation activities. A seascape tourism association or NGO such as Mafia Island Tourism Organization (MITO) can be ideal to bring together efforts from all tourism stakeholders.
- **Engage women and youth in MMA management.** Building from existing experiences in Mafia and elsewhere in training women for ranger and coral restoration roles, train and involve women and youth in marine conservation activities connected to the eco-resorts.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to funding grants to support marine conservation and community livelihood initiatives. • Technical support to establish a foundation or fund for marine conservation and connection to eco-resort peer-to-peer capacity building concept to engage other partners for conservation and community livelihood initiatives.
Chole Mjini Tree House Lodge, Kinasi Lodge, Thanda Island, Fanjove Private Island, and Ten Degrees South lodge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilize the community and leverage local knowledge and experience to promote marine conservation efforts. • Co-fund marine conservation, restoration, and community livelihood initiatives in the Heshimu Bahari seascapes through the business entity or associated foundations. • Participate in eco-resort peer-to-peer exchange programs to enhance capacity in marine conservation and share best practices with small island investors. • Support alternative and diversified livelihoods in local communities by purchasing their products, including more sustainable, locally sourced marine goods.
Chumbe Island Coral Park	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share best practices and train small island investors and eco-resorts on marine conservation, MMA management, and community livelihood/engagement in target seascapes.
WCS/GFCR and Blue Financing program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore viability and interest in financing the eco-resorts. • Provide financing and small loans for community livelihood initiatives and community-level fishers connected with the eco-resorts.
Government Agencies: MPRU and MLF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide regulatory oversight and support for MMA and community activities that involve permitting, licensing, and other government processes. • Participate in and provide technical experts to relevant MMA training and activities that involve government roles and functions. • Provide equipment and physical infrastructure for community livelihood activities (e.g., boats and equipment, shared service facility, etc.).

Justification and Impact

Partnering with eco-resorts has the potential to accelerate marine conservation and community resilience in two target seascapes: Mafia-Kilwa (#11) and Mtwara (#12). Each business focuses on nature-based tourism, has a history of supporting conservation and community development, and works closely with community institutions and government. Each eco-resort can also provide matching funds and resources to advance shared goals with the Activity around building marine biodiversity and community reliance, further leveraging the impact of their partnership.

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Determine which eco-resort partners to move forward with, and refine the list of potential activities and resource allocation	x					
Conduct follow-up meetings with each prioritized eco-resort to discuss potential activities and roles	x					
Develop final partnership concepts and secure internal approval		x				
Draft and sign MOUs with partners			x	x	x	
Co-develop detailed Year 1 partnership work plan					x	x

5.3.7 VALUE CHAINS: STRENGTHEN FISHERS AND SEAWEED FARMERS COOPERATIVES IN BAGAMOYO, DAR ES SALAAM, KILWA, MAFIA, AND MTWARA

Challenge

Small-scale fishers and seaweed farmers in Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara have been depending on unsustainable seaweed farming and small-scale fishing as means of their livelihoods. Seaweed is produced in marine areas with high biodiversity, such as coral reefs and seagrass beds, which has led to environmental degradation and loss of mangrove and biodiversity. The expansion of seaweed production, including the transition to deeper water production to adapt to warming seas, could have negative impacts on coral reef systems. The fishers and seaweed farmers face key challenges as outlined below.

Fishers	Seaweed Farmers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited ownership of boats forces small-scale fishers to pay for daily boat rentals. Moreover, lack of formal financing results in them taking informal loans with unfavorable terms for boat rentals and other fishing equipment and inputs. Poor and inefficient processing methods leads to lower-quality and high post-harvest loss, especially for daga fish (Swahili for “anchovy”), a key species for the region, which artisanal processors dry using firewood collected from mangroves and local forests leading to deforestation. Poor or non-existent post-harvest value chain infrastructure, such as cold chain storage, ice production, and transportation services, limits access to higher value markets, causes greater post-harvest loss, and leads to low prices paid to small-scale fishers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The market access facilitation is insufficient for unreliable buyers in Mtwara, where there is only one buyer dictating prices. There were previously other buyers, but they moved out due to unfair competition. Poor seaweed drying methods resulting in low quality and huge losses during the rainy season. Even just a brief contact with rainfall causes seaweed to lose its value and it cannot be sold. Lack of reliable financing for operations lead farmers to take inadequate and insufficient inputs advances from buyers and forced to sell seaweed to a buyer that gives lower prices and results in losses. Key inputs and equipment include ropes, tai-tai, seed, pegs and harvesting bags and boats.

Opportunity

The PSSA team identified five fisher cooperatives and four seaweed farmer cooperatives in Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara that expressed interest in helping its small-scale fisher and seaweed farmer members to increase access to improved technologies for fishing and seaweed farming (boats, fishing gear, storage equipment, seaweed farming and drying), markets, finance, and value addition inputs, as well as engage in sustainable fishing and seaweed farming practices and the prevention of IUU fishing in FRZs.

- Msanga Mkuu Fisheries Cooperative Society Ltd.**, based in Msanga Mkuu fish market in Mtwara district and near Mtwara town, has members in fishing, primary fish processing (including sorting and storage), and selling mainly at Mtwara Ferry fish market and Dar es Salaam Ferry fish market. Members fish near shore using small wooden boats and ice blocks for fish storage and transportation.
- Ushirika na Wavuvi na Wachakataji wa Mazao ya Bahari (WAMABA)**, a cooperative established in 2019 based in Sinda, Msanga Mkuu, Mtwara district and near Mtwara town, has 55 members engaged in fishing, processing, and selling at ferry market in Mtwara. These members are all women. The cooperative has a modern aquaculture project with four ponds, with capacity of 24,000 tilapia fish, and engages in seaweed farming. They sell fish products at Mtwara Ferry fish market. The main seaweed buyer is Mwani Mariculture Ltd., which is reported to exercise a monopoly on the market, often unreliable and not supporting any farming inputs. The project has an opportunity to facilitate linkages to the market and farming inputs such as contract farming arrangement facilitation, replicating the Mwani Zanzibar models.
- Naumbu Seaweed Farmers Cooperative Society**, based in Mkungu and Naumbu villages in Mtwara district, has mostly women members and engages in seaweed farming, harvesting, drying,

storage, and selling. The cooperative has a small facility for production of seaweed value added products and currently produces soap and seaweed-based body oil, selling to nearby communities and in Mtwara municipality. The main seaweed buyer is Mwani Mariculture Ltd.

4. **Kilwa Fisheries Association**, based in Kilwa Kivinje, Kilwa district and the largest fishing port in Lindi region, has 678 members and includes 60 women fishers, fish traders/buyers, and boat owners who operate in the Kilwa Kivinje and Kilwa Masoko fish markets and landing. Members' main activity is fishing, primary fish processing (including sorting and storage), and selling fish mainly at Dar es Salaam Ferry fish market. About 10 - 20 tons of fish are traded and shipped through the two ports per day during peak season.
5. **Seaweed Farmer Cooperative of Kilwa Kivinje**, based in Kilwa district, has 250 members (90% women) engaged in seaweed farming, harvesting, drying, storage and selling. Members harvest and sell about 5 - 7 tons of dried seaweed per month and their main buyer is Red Biashara Company.
6. **Jibondo Marine Farmers** is a women's seaweed farmers' cooperative based on Jibondo Island in Mafia District, comprising 24 members. The cooperative is involved in various activities such as seaweed farming, harvesting, drying, storage, and selling. The dried seaweed is primarily sold to individual buyers, mainly from Zanzibar.
7. **The Ferry Market Stakeholders Committee**, based in the Dar es Salaam Ferry Fish Market in the city, is a legally recognized representative committee. Its members include two cooperatives and 12 groups, collectively comprising over 2,000 individual members engaged in fishing, fish trading, primary fish processing (such as frying, cold storage, and ice making), and selling fish primarily in the Dar es Salaam Ferry Fish Market. In addition to sourcing fish from hundreds of small fishers, the market also receives fish from all over the country and neighboring countries like Kenya and Mozambique.
8. **Chama cha Wavuvi Wadogo Bagamoyo**, based in Bagamoyo town, is an association of about 275 small fishers, fish processors and traders and boat owners operating mainly in Bagamoyo Dunda fish market and fishing communities in Bagamoyo district. This association includes 202 women and is the only active fishers lobbying and advocacy organ in Bagamoyo. They established and supported 20 VSLAs in 20 Bagamoyo fishing communities.

Key Actions and Strategies

Heshimu Bahari will strengthen cooperatives and support members to reduce post-harvest loss and increase incomes. This will be achieved through improved fish and seaweed processing practices, access to better technology, and higher value markets. The organization will also encourage sustainable fishing practices and compliance with co-management measures. Specific capacity building strategies include:

- **Strengthen the cooperatives and facilitate partnerships** to support its members to reduce post-harvest loss and increase incomes through access to improved fishing equipment, fish handling and processing practices, access to cold storage and processing technologies, and improved access to higher value markets.
- **Strengthen seaweed cooperatives** and support members access efficient and sustainable farming tools, drying and storage technologies to improve quality and reduce post-harvest loss especially

during the rainy season. Key inputs and equipment include ropes, tai-tai, seed, pegs, drying facilities, harvesting bags and boats.

Heshimu Bahari will also partner with and connect with financing opportunities like WCS Blue Financing Association and Groups program to increase access to finance via several strategies:

- **BDS support** for fisher cooperative management and members on financial management and literacy, business planning, proper fish and seaweed farming and processing, and other relevant practices.
- **Connect cooperatives with cost-effective financing** from several sources including the Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank (TADB), replicate WCS Blue Financing Association/Groups program, and commercial finance partners like CRDB, NMB, and Equity Bank.
- **Increase access to better markets through value chain inputs**, such as inputs to improve fish and dried seaweed quality such as fish cold storage linkages and seaweed efficient drying technologies access; by connecting cooperatives to companies that offer said inputs, such as Fisheries Education and Training Agency (FETA), YP Investments and Alphakrust Ltd; and by connecting to better market such as established seaweed buyers with contract farming possibilities.
- **Engage cooperatives in sustainable fisheries management and FRZ initiatives** to protect local fish stocks and reduce IUU fishing, with the long-term goal of increasing buy-in for these interventions by demonstrating the resulting increased incomes.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide grant funding, capacity building, and partnership facilitation to improve post-harvest handling, improve quality and increase access to markets. • Connect cooperatives to the Activity's other initiatives involving government and other donor/NGO fisheries management and support them for long-term behavior change initiatives around sustainable fisheries and FRZ management.
Eight cooperatives and associations from Mtwara, Kilwa, Mafia, Bagamoyo and Dar es Salaam,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage cooperative members in partnership activities with Heshimu Bahari and build commitment and buy-in from members to support sustainable fisheries and seaweed production. • Bring expertise and knowledge of the local fishing sector and seaweed farming context. • Contribute resources (staff time, facilities, etc.) to capacity building activities for members.
Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank, WCS Blue Financing Groups program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide financing to cooperatives and members for actions that grow fisher operations and expand marine conservation efforts. • Potentially provide financial literacy and capacity building support to the cooperative and its members.
Government Agencies (FETA, MPRU and MLF)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance around the regulatory landscape for fisher cooperatives. • Assets such as physical infrastructure (e.g., boats and equipment) and shared service facilities to support fisher and processing operations. • Support during initiative roll-out and implementation.
Cold chain and processing firms (e.g., FETA, YP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide technology and cold storage services appropriate to small-scale fishers. • Expertise growing a business in the mainland Tanzania fisheries sector. • Support cooperatives and fishers to improve market access. • FETA has a long experience in training and providing improved technologies in fisheries and in seaweed farming, processing, and value addition products.

Investment, Alphakrust Ltd)	
Alphakrust Ltd	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential off taker of cooperative member fish products. • Potential to avail its excess capacity facilities to fishers in Mtwara, Kilwa Kivinje and Mafia include cold rooms and ice making facilities

Justification and Impact

The eight cooperatives are key private sector stakeholders in the Bagamoyo, Dar es Salaam, Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara seascapes fisheries sector and seaweed farming, offering Heshimu Bahari engagement with over 1,500 small-scale fisher/trader members and seaweed producers in Mtwara, Kilwa, Mafia and Bagamoyo and about 2,000 Dar es Salaam ferry market-based small-scale fishers, fish processors and traders. Strong cooperatives with functioning management are essential to support value addition, access to finance, and sustainable fisheries and seaweed production as working with individual small-scale fishers and seaweed farmers can be complicated, expensive, and ineffective. These cooperatives can play a key role in building awareness and buy-in from local fishers and seaweed farmers for adopting sustainable practices and engaging with fisheries officers (also oversee seaweed farming and business), MPRU and BMUs in monitoring, and compliance activities, including reporting IUU fishing.

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Conduct follow-up meetings with cooperatives and prepare detailed partnership concept notes with each cooperative.				x	x	
Secure internal approval of concept and partnership agreements.					x	
Draft and sign MOU with each cooperative and develop detailed partnership work plans.						x

5.3.8 VALUE CHAINS: PROMOTE INVESTMENT IN VALUE ADDED GLOBAL QUALITY SEAWEED PRODUCTS

Challenge

Limited production and marketing of value-added products from coastal communities' livelihood value chains, such as fisheries products, seaweed, and coconut, are homemade with poor packaging and branding. This results in challenges in accessing local markets. Due to the lack of investments in cottage and SME industries, pressure on unsustainable marine resources persists. Production facilities located far from coastal communities deny them employment and access to supplies and services. Most fish processing and packaging factories are in Dar es Salaam (e.g., Alpha Group, Bahari Food, etc).

Investment in value-addition businesses located in coastal areas is important, especially for vulnerable seaweed farming communities. Mwani Zanzibar Ltd. is an SME that manufactures seaweed-based premium skincare products, but faces challenges such as heavy power outages, sourcing production inputs, lack of resources for quality seaweed production, limited access to affordable financial services, and no established framework for seaweed production and selling. Mwani Zanzibar pays nine times the average income of a seaweed farmer and employs former seaweed farmers to ensure quality inputs. The government's role

and support in seaweed business is limited, which makes it difficult for SME's such as Mwani Zanzibar to expand their operations and contribute further to the local economy.

Opportunity

Mwani Zanzibar is based in Paje, East Unguja that specializes in producing premium skincare products. Their target markets include Tanzania, the United States, and other international skincare markets. The company manufactures high-end cosmetics and skincare products based on seaweed, which is farmed by women in Paje. Mwani Zanzibar sells its products locally and worldwide and has gained a reputation as an official carbon-neutral company, certified by Climate Partner. The company works with ten seaweed farmers who receive over 900% more than regular seaweed farmers around the island. These farmers are employed full-time and have full benefits. The company farms within an area of approximately 5,000 square kilometers. Mwani Zanzibar also invests in an exclusive network of 180 input suppliers in and outside the island.

Heshimu Bahari can collaborate with and support the operations of Mwani Zanzibar to promote investment in local businesses that process and produce quality seaweed-based products, along with supporting the livelihoods of coastal communities. Involving SME investors in coastal communities to share best practices is possible. The partnership can also be a model for empowering women and youth. Furthermore, there is a scope to support the employment of seaweed farmers in Zanzibar by establishing local supply networks of raw materials and providing training to the local communities.

Partners and Roles

Potential Partners	Role/Contribution
Heshimu Bahari	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical expertise from staff and implementing partners, and co-funding to conduct marine conservation, restoration, and climate vulnerability studies. • Co-financing of seaweed value chain and livelihood resilience activities. • Engaging government partners to support private sector-led investment in seaweed value chains. • Access to finance support - network/connection of potential financiers/investors and support institutions.
Mwani Zanzibar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buyer commitment to sourcing sustainable seaweed and coastal value chain products. • Global technical expertise in seaweed-based products research, production, markets, and inputs sourcing. • Co-investment in enhancing seaweed and other alternative coastal value chains such as coconuts, mangrove beekeeping; building resilient community livelihoods, providing employment opportunities, and supporting marine conservation and restoration efforts.
CRDB Bank, Equity Bank, WCS -GFCR SEAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CRDB Bank, Equity Bank, GFCR, and SEAF have shown interest in deploying capital towards blue economy SMEs. • GFCR focus on coral reef ecosystems protection and restoration – Mwani Zanzibar can benefit in its finance to revenue-generating businesses and investments in coastal alternative activities for subsistence and income.

<p>Zanzibar Economic Empowerment Agency (ZEEA), ZIPA, TIC, Zanzibar Marine Research and Fisheries Institute, MoBEF and FETA.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide incentives or assurances for Mwani Zanzibar and other companies to invest in seaweed and other value chain end products. • Support in products research and development, inputs sourcing arrangements, access to technologies and BDS for global competitive products (quality, packing, branding, etc). • Engage to unlock potential public and donor funding for coastal livelihoods and blue economy SMEs that can address climate adaptation and resilience for vulnerable communities.
---	---

Key Actions and Strategies

The overall strategy is to work with Mwani Zanzibar to implement its plan to improve productivity, increase access to technology and financing, expand production, engage/employ more seaweed farmers in East Unguja and build a reliable network of input suppliers especially sourced from coastal communities of Zanzibar and Mainland Tanzania. Mwani Zanzibar is seeking USD \$450,000 financing in 2024 and expects to expand production and sales by 100% and employment by 50% (they currently employ 24 people).

Mwani Zanzibar is looking for Heshimu Bahari to contribute USD \$150,000 funding and this can assist Mwani Zanzibar gain access to commercial financial services to help scale their business. By doing so, Mwani Zanzibar can bolster the efficiency of seaweed value chains, coastal non-seaweed input value chains (e.g. coconut, honey), build more resilient livelihoods in coastal communities, and reduce pressure on marine resources. In earlier PSSA meetings, several financial institutions and funds have been identified that are interested in deploying capital towards blue economy SMEs including CRDB Bank, Equity Bank, GFCR (financing for alternative activities for subsistence and income), and SEAF. Other actions could include:

- **Co-financing and research on more seaweed products** and sustainable production inputs to compete with brands worldwide.
- **Support access to finance to invest in new production equipment** and solar energy to expand production and benefit local communities through seaweed incomes and employment. Heshimu Bahari could provide technical assistance to leverage/unlock other sources of finance.
- **Support the market expansion** through local promotion campaigns and international expos to benefit the expansion of women seaweed farming workforce and a wider impact on Mwani Zanzibar supply chain, and potential positive spillover effects on tourism.
- **Use Mwani Zanzibar operations as a model to promote investment** in local quality seaweed final products processing facilities/businesses. Specifically, use Mwani Zanzibar Model to help informal home-based value-added productions to move to formal cottage industries meeting regulatory requirements (TBS, TMDA) in quality and packaging to access wider local and regional markets.
- **Support Mwani Zanzibar in development of local sourcing of inputs** especially those available in coastal communities (e.g., coconut oil by working with the communities to achieve quality and quantities needs of the company).
- **Document Mwani Zanzibar experience** in community livelihoods value additions as a learning tool for other entrepreneurs.
- **Collaborate with Mwani Zanzibar and public institutions to promote SMEs investments in coastal community value chains** in Zanzibar and Tanzania mainland. Involve institutions of trade and economic empowerment in a dialogue and investment forum to identify and implement specific

opportunities to replicate the Mwani Zanzibar model (or similar). Target institutions include ZEEA, ZIPA, TIC, Zanzibar Marine Research and Fisheries Institute, MoBEF and FETA.

Justification and Impact

Heshimu Bahari activity objectives (specifically around enhancing livelihoods in coastal communities) are well aligned with Mwani Zanzibar’s focus on local production and employment of Paje and Zanzibar residents. They are committed to increasing their impact and a partnership that expands their production could enhance livelihoods while reducing pressure on fisheries. Further, there are limited opportunities in East Unguja so partnering with Mwani Zanzibar could offer Heshimu Bahari private sector engagement opportunities in that seascape.

Immediate Next Steps

Actions	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Conduct follow-up meetings with Mwani Zanzibar to discuss their role and priorities to refine the partnership concept.	x					
Develop detailed partnership concept note, and review with the technical team as part of the SA/SO/IR adoption exercise.		x				
Secure internal approval of the concept for development of partnership agreements.		x				
Draft and sign an MOU with Mwani Zanzibar and develop detailed partnership work plan.			x			
Partnership launch forum.				x		

5.4 MEDIUM-HIGH POTENTIAL PARTNERSHIP CONCEPTS

The PSSA team ranked two partnership concepts as medium-high, as outlined below. These two partnership concepts have the potential to address key issues in seafood value chains but involve risks and uncertainties that require additional investigation by Heshimu Bahari before moving forward.

5.4.1 VALUE CHAIN: PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE AND SMALL-SCALE FISHERS’ ACCESS TO MARKETS

Challenge

Tanga’s fisheries sector faces systemic challenges that limit its overall productivity including:

- Lack of working equipment and fishing gear, including boats, which leads many small-scale fishers to seek daily boat rentals to continue operations, a cost that significantly cuts into their income potential.
- Insufficient enforcement of fishing regulations resulting in fishing in FRZs and the use of banned fishing equipment and methods.
- Illegal smuggling of seafood products to Kenya where there is no stringent enforcement of fishing regulations and no additional levy charged on harvest compared to Tanzania. This results in a lower supply of seafood products to domestic processing plants and large fish traders.

Opportunity

Alphakrust Ltd, based in Tanga, is a subsidiary of Alpha Group Ltd, the largest seafood company in Tanzania that processes and exports a variety of fresh and frozen fish to over 50 destinations worldwide. The Alpha Group has three seafood processing facilities in Dar es Salaam, Tanga and Mafia respectively, and the company was the first in East Africa to build and operate a 100-hectare black tiger prawn aquaculture farm in Mafia Island, with hatcheries for shrimp and tilapia, that has been successfully certified by the Aquaculture Stewardship Council. Moreover, Alphakrust's processing facility in Tanga city has a ten ton per day processing capacity, but the company has difficulties meeting these levels despite supporting local fishers.

Potential Partnership

Partner with Alphakrust Ltd, Tanga to support community engagement and co-financing of aquaculture in coastal communities. Heshimu Bahari can also co-finance Alphakrust and fishers' cooperatives for improved fishing technologies, including cold storage and transportation. Alphakrust Ltd's input can include market access, investment in cold chain storage, and aquaculture supplies and technical support.

Justification and Next Steps

Alpha Group is a key stakeholder in Tanzania's fisheries, aquaculture, and seafood processing space, and has opportunities to support fisheries and aquaculture sector-based coastal livelihoods. Heshimu Bahari needs to conduct additional due diligence on the environmental sustainability and potential impacts of the shrimp aquaculture production before considering it as a potential diversified livelihood opportunity.

5.4.2 VALUE CHAIN: EXPAND SMALL-SCALE FISHERS ACCESS TO COLD STORAGE SOLUTIONS

Challenge

A significant share of fish landed in Tanzania is lost due to spoilage or sold at a sub-optimal price due to seasonal abundance. Most artisanal fishers in Tanzania lack access to appropriate cold storage infrastructure, leading to fish loss, lost income, and limited market access.

Opportunity

YP Investment Ltd is a cold storage company founded in 2019 near Lake Victoria that provides both ice flakes and cold storage facilities to small-scale fishers, enabling them to reduce post-harvest loss and sell to more distant markets. The company is expanding to Dar es Salaam and has also shown interest in providing cold storage solutions to small-scale fishers and cooperatives in other coastal areas of mainland Tanzania. These cold chain linkages can raise income levels of artisanal fish value chains while simultaneously improving livelihoods and reducing pressure on marine ecosystems in mainland Tanzania seascapes. Moreover, cold chain improvements also create opportunities for value addition in processing, such as frozen or chilled semi-processed pre-packaged seafood.

Potential Partnership

Connect and socialize YP Investment to fisher cooperatives along the coast in mainland Tanzania in need of cold storage solutions and provide training and capacity for these fishers to improve product quality. Support YP Investment to connect with more affordable financing options to expand the cold storage solutions, for example SEAF, which could provide a grant to support further expansion.

Justification and Next Steps

The company is already expanding to Dar es Salaam and followed-up with the project to conduct site visits to meet with fisher cooperatives in the Tanga region. Cold-storage solutions are a major issue for small-scale fishers and cooperatives along the coast, and YP Investment seems to be one of the only companies looking to provide solutions to small-scale fishers that is not a larger seafood buyer that would lock fishers into low prices. As the company is only just expanding into coastal regions, Heshimu Bahari should conduct follow-up and due diligence on the company's products and expansion plans.

5.4.3 TOURISM AND MMA: KILWA, MAFICA, AND MTWARA SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND MMAS PPD AND FORUM

Challenge

Limited government support for promoting coastal tourism in mainland Tanzania, compared to TANAPA parks and Zanzibar, has resulted in very low tourism activities in coastal destinations, which in turn has led to poor income for coastal eco-lodges. Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara compete with other beach destinations worldwide, including Zanzibar. The ongoing war in northern Mozambique has caused negative travel advisories to southern regions and the coast of Tanzania, resulting in very low tourism activities, especially in Lindi and Mtwara regions, despite the generally peaceful situation on the Tanzanian side. The high cost for tourists to visit the southern region is a result of limited flights, expensive hotels and transportation, and unfavorable government policies. Eco-lodges in Kilwa, Lindi, and Mtwara regions have limited ability to raise funds for tourism promotion individually, as there is no formal vehicle to unite tourism stakeholders and support marine conservation and protection of other unique attractions.

Opportunity

Collaborate with the MITO, a network of hotels and lodges in Kilwa led by Fanjove Island Lodge, PEC Hotel, Kilwa Beach Lodge, and Mafia Dreams Lodge, and a network of hotels and lodges in Mtwara led by Ten Degrees South Lodge and Old Boma Hotel to promote tourism and investment in the Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara as a vehicle for sustainable marine conservation and the region's economic development. Work with the private sector in collaboration with MPRU, TAWA, and HAT to support the Tourism Expo and Investment Forum for Kilwa, Mafia, and Mtwara. There is an opportunity for Heshimu Bahari to support the private sector to contribute to marine conservation efforts and tourism promotion.

Potential Partnership

Collaborating with MITO and tourism stakeholders in the Mtwara and Lindi regions can be beneficial to expand advocacy and policy efforts among members and key government stakeholders. This partnership could help develop an enabling environment that fosters tourism growth in these regions, attracting more investment in the sector, and increase private sector involvement in actively supporting effective MMA management.

Justification and Next Steps

Tourism organizations in Mafia, Kilwa, and Mtwara are essential for the region's economy. They generate tax revenue and support livelihoods, and they are interested in sustainable MMAs, seafood supply, marine sports, and eco-tourism. To identify and discuss barriers to tourism growth and private investment in marine conservation in the Mafia, Kilwa, and Mtwara seascapes, policy dialogues can be held. However, Heshimu Bahari needs to conduct further engagement with the associations, investors, and government to identify additional shared activities and outcomes that can increase private investors' involvement in actively supporting effective MMA management and boost sustainable tourism in the region. Additionally,

the activity should explore the feasibility and appropriateness of combining these dialogues with the Tanga region forums and PPDs.

SECTION 6: OTHER PSE RECOMMENDATIONS

In addition to the partnership concepts, the PSSA team identified several strategies and activities that Heshimu Bahari can pursue to support and enable more environmentally sound investments in tourism, gender empowerment, and resilient livelihoods.

6.1 BUILD GOVERNMENT CAPACITY TO EVALUATE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENTS (EIA) FOR MARINE AND TOURISM INVESTMENTS

Before any project or investment that may have significant impacts on environment or social conditions can start, it must undergo an EIA, this includes construction like building or expanding hotels.⁴³ The EIA must be completed by authorized expert or company to identify the potential environmental and social impacts of the project and to provide mechanisms to minimize impacts. The EIAs are reviewed and approved by ZEMA in Zanzibar and the National Environmental Management Council (NEMC). As highlighted in PSSA interviews with public and private sector stakeholders, EIAs for most projects in coastal and marine areas in Tanzania are either not effective or enforced, this is especially true for the recent small island investments in Zanzibar. Specific challenges include:

- **Lack of capacity in evaluating EIAs in the coastal and marine context.** ZIPA, ZEMA, NEMC and TIC staff have varying levels of expertise in evaluating the environmental and social impacts of investments and projects in the coastal and marine areas, which impacts the quality of their assessments, decision making and recommendations for mitigation measures.
- **Limited financial resources.** ZEMA and NEMC have limited financial and human resources hindering their ability to effectively review and monitor EIAs.
- **Data and information gaps:** Access to accurate and up-to-date environmental data specific to marine ecosystems is difficult for both the private sector and government, which impacts the accuracy of potential impacts in the EIA.
- **Coordination Issues:** Effective coordination among institutions is hindered by differing priorities, communication barriers, and resource allocation disputes.

Heshimu Bahari can provide trainings to ZIPA, ZEMA, NEMC and TIC to enhance their understanding of EIA processes, methodologies, and regulatory requirements connected to coastal and marine ecosystems to ensure the impact of future tourism investments are addressed and mitigated more effectively. Heshimu Bahari should also develop best practice guidelines for evaluating EIAs in the coastal and marine sectors, ensuring that they align with international best practices, and provide technical assistance to enhance the knowledge and skills of the government staff. To support the compliance of ongoing investments, Heshimu Bahari can provide guidance on developing and implementing a monitoring and reporting system to track the compliance and effectiveness of EIA recommendations. Finally, Heshimu Bahari should leverage the Greener Zanzibar campaign and the Zanzibar Small Island Investors Forum to create public awareness campaigns to educate the public about the importance of EIAs in marine investments and the roles of ZIPA, ZEMA, NEMC and TIC in safeguarding environmental interests.

⁴³ Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority-ZEMA-. (n.d.). *ZEMA-Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority* .<https://www.zema.go.tz/envImpact.php>

6.2 GENDER AND YOUTH EMPOWERMENT

The PSSA team identified several opportunities for gender and youth empowerment through stakeholder interviews, some of which are included in the partnership concepts, such as building the gender lens investing (GLI) capacity of private sector investment enabling organizations like ZIPA and TIC. Other opportunities include:

- **Promote and expand efforts by &Beyond, Chumbe Island, and other private sector stakeholders**, to engage women and youth in marine conservation and other sustainability activities. These eco-resorts are actively training women and youth as marine rangers, as well as in engaging them in other conservation activities. They can also provide learning exchanges and peer-to-peer training for other eco-resorts and investors on youth and women empowerment.
- **Increase access to capital for youth and women SMEs** in target seascapes in collaboration with eco-resorts and their foundations, like &Beyond, Manta Resort, Emanayi Lodge, and others, which are offering financial support to women and young entrepreneurs looking to start or expand businesses in local communities. Co-funding grants and technical assistance can help remove financial barriers that often hinder women and youth participation in entrepreneurship, while also supporting diversified livelihoods to reduce pressure off fisheries and other marine resources.
- **Engage the Tanzania Women Commerce of Chamber** to create and disseminate gender policies for the private sector, such as GLI adapted to the Tanzanian context, and include them a coalition for promoting women in blue economy businesses.
- **Build on the Small Industry Development Organization's (SIDO's)** internal gender policy to incorporate GLI, and its youth entrepreneurship in ICT program to support women and youth SME development in blue economy sectors within target seascapes along the coast of mainland Tanzania.
- **Build partnerships between private sector partners, educational institutions, and vocational training centers** to provide specialized training programs for women and youth interested in marine-related careers.

6.3 LIVELIHOODS AND VALUE CHAINS

Heshimu Bahari should include PSE as an element of the socio-economic baseline assessments being conducted in all target seascapes. Although the PSSA explored and identified potential partners and partnership concepts that can contribute to improving value chains and building more resilient livelihoods, it did not do so in each sector/seascape at the community level. The socio-economic assessments can help identify communities involved in specific value chains and livelihoods that connect with the partnership concepts presented in the PSSA and identify other priority non-fishery value chains where a private sector partner may be engaged. Additionally, Heshimu Bahari should engage those eco-resorts actively working with communities in the target seascapes to identify priorities and co-funding opportunities for livelihood development, and community empowerment and outreach.

Moreover, the PSSA team met with several companies and cooperatives that, although not included in specific partnership concepts, could still offer opportunities to connect with future livelihoods activities:

- **Coastal Biotech:** This local start-up is developing innovative biochar and bio-stimulants for use in agricultural production derived from seaweed sourced from small-scale farms and communities in Zanzibar.⁴⁴ Seaweed bio stimulants demand is expected to grow approximately 13 percent per year, which offers a potential new market opportunity, though additional interventions are needed to increase

⁴⁴ Coastal Biotech. (2023, September 8). *Home 3 - Coastal Biotech*. <https://coastalbiotech.co.tz/>

efficiencies and improve the value chain to bring down the cost of production.⁴⁵ The company is partnered with the Zanzibar Marine Research and Fisheries Institute, and the MoBEF to conduct joint research and production initiatives. Additionally, the company is currently exploring blue carbon credit opportunities as an alternative source of revenue. Moreover, given the fact that seaweed bio stimulants are an emergent product, before Heshimu Bahari considers a partnership with the company, it should conduct additional due diligence and explore if there is alignment with livelihoods in target seascapes as part of the socio-economic baselines.

- **Pemba Beekeeper Association (PBA):** There is potential to engage PBA to support beekeeping and mangrove honey production as an alternative livelihood in Pemba, and support mangrove protection; however, PBA is more focused on the technical assistance, outreach, and engagement with beekeepers, and doesn't demonstrate strong capacity or funding to develop the logistics and market access. Heshimu Bahari could explore private sector and market-led opportunities in honey in Pemba if the communities in the target seascapes with show interest in this livelihood, and leverage PBA's community connections and membership.
- **Daya Cooperative:** Based in Pemba, and connected to communities in Heshimu Bahari seascapes, there may be potential to engage the cooperative as stakeholders in the blue economy enterprise and alternative livelihoods initiatives. Their members are involved in several different livelihoods, including sea cucumber ranching, seaweed production, fishing, and spice farming, and they also support informal fisher and farmer groups to engage with the government, NGOs, and donors.

SECTION 7. NEXT STEPS

For the quick win partnership concepts, Heshimu Bahari should move forward with the immediate next steps outlined in each concept, with the goal of formalizing partnerships with key partners and implementing activities that contribute initial results in Year 2.

Heshimu Bahari should also conduct an in-depth prioritization workshop/exercise with the Activity leadership, technical team, and relevant consortium partners (as needed) to review and prioritize the high-potential partnership concepts. As input to this prioritization process, prior to the workshop, the Activity's private sector lead will conduct follow-up meetings and calls with prospective partners included in each concept to further refine and develop the concepts. This will help to maintain momentum among interested partners that were interviewed through the PSSA's primary data collection efforts, and provide sufficient information for the Heshimu Bahari team to evaluate the concepts.

This PSSA report and the prioritization workshop/exercise will also serve as a resource in developing Heshimu Bahari's overall PSE strategy. As the project goes on, Heshimu Bahari staff will likely come across additional potential partnership opportunities. These will be prioritized on an as needed or annual basis, with the aid of the partnership concept scorecard.

⁴⁵ Bain & Company and TNC. (September 2023). *Analysis of Farmed Seaweed Carbon Crediting and Novel Markets to Help Decarbonize Supply Chains*
<https://www.nature.org/content/dam/tnc/nature/en/documents/SeaweedMarketsAnalysis.pdf>

ANNEX I. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- &Beyond. Mnemba Island Zanzibar. Accessed October 30, 2023.
<https://www.andbeyond.com/our-lodges/indian-ocean-islands/zanzibar/andbeyond-mnemba-island/>
- Bain & Company and The Nature Conservancy (TNC). Analysis of Farmed Seaweed Carbon Crediting and Novel Markets to Help Decarbonize Supply Chains. September 2023.
<https://www.nature.org/content/dam/tnc/nature/en/documents/SeaweedMarketsAnalysis.pdf>
- Bank of Tanzania (BoT). Consolidated Zonal Economic Performance Report for the Year Ending June 2022. Volume 7 No. 2. ISSN 2546-2008.
<https://www.bot.go.tz/Publications/Regular/Consolidated%20Zonal%20Economic%20Report/en/2022110112140532.pdf>
- Blue Alliance. In The News, Blue Alliance. October 26, 2023. Blue Alliance.
<https://bluealliance.earth/in-the-news/>
- BlueSeeds. “Closing the financing gap of marine conservation.” January 25, 2021.
<https://bluseeds.org/en/closing-the-financing-gap-of-marine-conservation/>
- Carbon Pulse. Impact loan to set Philippines MPAs on track to economic independence. (n.d.).
<https://carbon-pulse.com/222458/>
- Cargill. The Red Seaweed Promise Progress Report 2021. 2021.
<https://www.cargill.com/doc/1432198890865/sustainable-seaweed-red-seaweed-promise-progress-report.pdf>
- Charisiadou, Stefania, Christina Halling, Narriman Jiddawi, Kristina von Schreeb, Martin Gullström, Terése Larsson, and Lina Mtwana Nordlund. “Coastal Aquaculture in Zanzibar, Tanzania.” 2022. Aquaculture Volume 546 (January): 737331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2021.737331>
- Chumbe Island Coral Park. Chumbe Island Coral Park Zanzibar, private nature reserve & ecolodge. August 10, 2023. Accessed October 25, 2023. <https://chumbeisland.com/>
- Coastal Biotech. Home 3 - Coastal Biotech. September 8, 2023. <https://coastalbiotech.co.tz/>
- Concept Note: Validation and Launching the Report on the Status and Trends of Coral Reefs in Tanzania 2022. 2023. Dodoma: National Environment Management Council (NEMC).
- Dar es Salaam, Tanzania Population (2023) - Population Stat. (n.d.).
<https://populationstat.com/tanzania/dar-es-salaam>
- “DEVELOPMENT VISION 2025 FOREWORD.” n.d. Accessed November 2, 2023.
<https://hssrc.tamisemi.go.tz/storage/app/uploads/public/5ac/f22/c6d/5ac/f22c6d2216284886624.pdf>
- Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR). <https://globalfundcoralreefs.org/>

- Greener Zanzibar. The Zanzibar Tourism Investment & Travel Exhibition. (n.d.).
<https://ztite.zanzibartourism.go.tz/greener-zanzibar/>
- Hehre, E. James, and Jessica J. Meeuwig. "A Global Analysis of the Relationship between Farmed Seaweed Production and Herbivorous Fish Catch." Edited by Konstantinos I Stergiou. 2016. PLOS ONE 11 (2): e0148250. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148250>
- Kwanini Foundation. (n.d.). An update on our USAID project partnership. July 7, 2020. Accessed October 25, 2023.
<http://kwaninifoundation.org/2020/07/07/usaid-protect-update/#:~:text=On%20September%209th%2C%202019%2C%20the.year%20starting%20in%20July%202019>
- Lazy Lagoon Island. (n.d.). Lazy Lagoon Island Lodge by Foxes Safari Camps Tanzania.
<https://www.lazylagoonisland.com/>
- Magembe, Lucy. "The Promise of Restorative Aquaculture Solutions." The Nature Conservancy (TNC). July 14, 2020. Updated October 11, 2023. <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-insights/perspectives/restorative-aquaculture-seaweed-farms-tanzania/>
- Mairi, Julius and Mgawe, Yahya. "A Review of the National Fisheries Management Plans for Tanzania." Ecofish Integrated Programme Management Unit. December 2021.
<https://ecofish-programme.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/ECO-2022-40-Fisheries-Mgmt-TANZANIA.pdf>
- Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries, Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar. Study on Blue Economy Opportunities in Zanzibar. 2022.
- Ministry of Finance and Planning. The United Republic of Tanzania. The National Development Vision (2025). <https://repository.mof.go.tz/handle/123456789/127>
- Mngulwi, Baraka S. "Fisheries Division, Ministry of Natural Resources and Tourism, United Republic of Tanzania." FAO Fisheries Technical Paper 488. December 2003.
<https://www.fao.org/3/a0477e/a0477e13.htm>
- Mtanzania. June 2020. <https://www.mifugouvuvu.go.tz/uploads/publications/sw1591600998-Magazeti%20ya%20tarehe%2002-06-2020.pdf>
- National Bureau of Statistics. The United Republic of Tanzania. 2019 Tanzania in Figures. June 2020.
https://www.nbs.go.tz/nbs/takwimu/references/Tanzania_in_Figures_2019.pdf
- National Bureau of Statistics. The United Republic of Tanzania. 2022 Tanzania in Figures. 2023.
https://www.nbs.go.tz/nbs/takwimu/references/2022_Tanzania_in_Figure_English.pdf
- National Environment Management Council (NEMC). Environmental Research Coordination Section. The United Republic of Tanzania. National Integrated Coastal Environmental Management Strategy (NICEMS) Concept Note. 2023. www.nemc.or.tz
- Office of the Chief Government Statistician. The Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar. Zanzibar in

- Figures 2021. <https://www.ocgs.go.tz/ReportOCGS/1665577844.pdf>
- ORRAA. “Establishing a Blended Finance Facility for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) - Blue Finance – ORRAA,” June 23, 2023. <https://oceanriskalliance.org/project/establishing-a-blended-finance-facility-for-marine-protected-areas-mpas/>
- “PRIVATE-SECTOR ENGAGEMENT POLICY.” n.d. https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/2022-05/usaid_psepolicy_final.pdf.
- Tanzania C-Weed Corporation LTD. (n.d.). <https://cweed.com/about-us/>
- Tjiptohandono, Dwi Aryo. LinkedIn. Accessed September 26, 2023. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dwiaryotjiptohandono_sustainablefisheries-indonesia-usaidberikan-activity-7112322989026676736-Rwyg?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- “TNBC | Mfumo Wa Majadiliano.” n.d. [Wwww.tnbc.go.tz](http://www.tnbc.go.tz). Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://www.tnbc.go.tz/index.php/pages/ppd-framework>.
- Tourism Action Coalition for a Sustainable Ocean (TASCO). Ocean Tourism. January 19, 2023. <https://oceantourism.org/>
- U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID). Nosy Manga Marine Ecosystems and Community. https://ocean-farmers.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Final-Fact-Sheet_Nosy-Manga-February-2022_English_03_07_2022.pdf
- U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID). Private-Sector Engagement Policy. May 2022. https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/2022-05/usaid_psepolicy_final.pdf
- United Nations (UN). “Blue Economy: oceans as the next great economic frontier.” March 14, 2022. <https://unric.org/en/blue-economy-oceans-as-the-next-great-economic-frontier/>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). World Bank Open Data. <https://data.worldbank.org>
- Worldometer. Tanzania Demographics 2023 (population, age, sex, trends). (n.d.) <https://www.worldometers.info/demographics/tanzania-demographics/>
- World Wildlife Fund (WWF). “Bringing sustainable seafood from fishers to hotels.” July 10, 2015. https://wwf.panda.org/wwf_news/?249114/Bringing-sustainable-seafood-from-fishers-to-hotels
- World Wildlife Fund (WWF). Business and Sustainable Seafood, A guide to addressing sustainability in seafood operations. https://wwfsassi.co.za/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/WWF_SASSI_Business_Guide_to_Sustainable_Seafood.pdf
- Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority-ZEMA-. Accessed October 30, 2023. ZEMA-Zanzibar Environmental Management Authority. <https://www.zema.go.tz/envImpact.php>

ANNEX 2. MEETING LIST

	Organization/Location	Organization Type	Organization Sector	Seascape Alignment	Activity Private Sector Alignment
1	Fishwise	Consulting Firm	Public Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture
2	Abalobi	Consulting Firm	Private Sector	#7, #8	Fisheries, Aquaculture
3	Tanzania Women Commerce of Chamber/ Dar es Salaam	Association	Association	# 1,# 2, # 3, # 10, # 11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
4	Tanzania Startup Association/Dar es Salaam	Association	Association	# 1, # 2, # 3, # 10	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
5	CRDB Bank/Dar es Salaam	Financial Institution	Private Sector	# 10 #1, #2, #3, # 4,# 5, # 6, # 7	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
6	Hatch	Consulting Firm	Private Sector	All	Fisheries, Aquaculture
7	Aqua Farm Organization/Dar es Salaam	NGO	Public Sector	# 1, # 2, # 3, # 10# 1A # 10I	Fisheries, Aquaculture
8	Bahari Foods/ Dar es Salaam	Business	Private Sector	# 1, # 2, # 3, # 10	Fisheries
9	Equity Bank/Dar es Salaam	Financial Institution	Private Sector	# 1, # 2,# 3,,3 4,# 5, # 6 , # 7	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
10	Hotel Association of Tanzania/Dar es Salaam	Association	Association	# 10	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture
11	Association of Tanzania Insurers/Dar es Salaam	Association	Association	# 10	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
12	TNC/Dar es Salaam	NGO	Public Sector	# 10	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
13	Steve McCormick (representing EACOP)/Dar es Salaam	Independent Consultant	Private Sector	# 10	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
14	Lazy Lagoon Island Resort/Bagamoyo	Hotel	Private Sector	#3	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
15	WIOMSA (Western Indian Ocean Marine Science Association)	Association	Association	All	Fisheries, Aquaculture
16	Zanzibar Commission of Tourism (ZCT)	Government	Public Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Tourism, Fisheries

17	Zanzibar Association of Tourist Investors (ZATI)	Association	Association	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Tourism
18	Zanzibar Economic Empowerment Agency (ZEEA)	Government	Public Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
19	Blue Alliance & Finance	Business	Private Sector	#7, #8	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
20	ZIPA	Government	Public Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
21	Mwambao	NGO	Public Sector	#1, #2, #4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
22	&Beyond (Mnemba Resort)	Hotel	Private Sector	#9	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
23	C-weed Corporation Ltd	Business	Private Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Aquaculture
24	SMIDA	Government	Public Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
25	Chumbe Island	Hotel	Private Sector	#5	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
26	Coastal Biotech	Business	Private Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
27	Indesso Tanzania	Business	Private Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Alternative Livelihoods
28	AZSEE	NGO	Public Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
29	Pemba Beekeeper Association	Association	Association	#7, #8	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
30	Daya Cooperative	Cooperative	Private Sector	#7	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
31	Manta Resort/Kwanini Foundation	Hotel	Private Sector	#7	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
32	Tanzania Investment Center (TIC)	Government	Public Sector	#1, #2, #3, #10, #11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture,

					Alternative Livelihoods
33	SEAF-CEED	NGO	Public Sector	All	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
34	SIDO	Government	Public Sector	#1, #2, #3, #10, #11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
35	Deloitte	Consulting Firm	Private Sector	#1, #2, #3, #10, #11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
36	Arena Recycling	Business	Private Sector	#3, #10	Alternative Livelihoods
37	Libe Green Innovation	Business	Private Sector	#10	Alternative Livelihoods
38	South Pole	Business	Private Sector	All	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
39	National Insurance Corporation	Business	Private Sector	All	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
40	Istdar Seafood	Business	Private Sector	#11	Fisheries
41	Samaki Bluu	Business	Private Sector	#7, #8	Fisheries
42	Tullia Pamunda	Hotel	Private Sector	#4	Tourism
43	Sally Beck - Mizizi	Hotel	Private Sector	#7	Tourism
44	GFCR	Development Fund	Private Sector	All	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods, Finance
45	YP Investment	Business	Private Sector	#10	Fisheries
46	Cargill	Business	Private Sector	#4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9	Alternative Livelihoods, Aquaculture
47	MPRU - Tanga Centre	Government	Public Sector	#2,	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
48	Karibu Pangani Coast Cultural Tourism	NGO	Public Sector	#2	Tourism
49	Emayani Beach Lodge/Pangani	Hotel	Private Sector	#2	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
50	Umoja Ushongo Ltd/Pangani	Business	Private Sector	#2	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
51	Mike's Beach Cottages/Pangani	Hotel	Private Sector	#2	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods

52	UWAWABIMA - Kipumbwi	Cooperative	Private Sector	#2	Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
53	Foundation for Trees/Pangani	NGO	Public Sector	#2	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
54	Panori Hotel Ltd/Tanga	Hotel	Private Sector	#1	Tourism, Alternative Livelihoods
55	Fish Eagle Point/Mkinga	Hotel	Private Sector	#1	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
56	Tanga Tourism Network Association/ Tanga	Association	Association	#1, #2	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture
57	Tanga Yacht Club	Business	Private Sector	#1	Tourism, Fisheries
58	Mkonge Hotel/Tanga	Hotel	Private Sector	#1	Tourism, Alternative Livelihoods
59	Alphakrust Ltd/Alpha Group/Tanga	Business	Private Sector	#1	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
60	Tanga RC Office	Government	Public Sector	#1, #2	Fisheries, Tourism, Aquaculture
61	Deep See Cooperative Society Ltd/ Tanga	Cooperative	Private Sector	#1	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
62	WCS Tanga Office	Consulting Firm	Private Sector	#1, #2	Fisheries, Tourism, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
63	Capricorn Beach Cottages/Kigombe, Muheza	Hotel	Private Sector	#1	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
64	MPRU Head Office/Dar es Salaam	Government	Public Sector	1, #2, #3, #10, #11, #12	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
65	Ten Degrees South Lodge/ Mikindani Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
66	Regional Commissioner Office/Mtwara	Government	Public Sector	#12	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
67	Naumbu Seaweed Cooperative/ Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Fisheries, Aquaculture
68	Ushirika na Wavuvi na Wachataji wa Mazao ya Bahari (WAMABA) - Msanga Mkuu, Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods

69	Msanga Mkuu Fishers Cooperative/Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Fisheries, Aquaculture
70	Alphakrust Ltd/Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Fisheries, Aquaculture
71	MPRU/Mtwara	Government	Public Sector	#12	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
72	FETA/Mtwara	Government	Public Sector	#1, #2, #3, #10, #11, #12	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
73	MSOAPO/Mtwara	NGO	Public Sector	#12	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
74	Old Boma Hotel/Mikindani Mtwara	Business	Private Sector	#12	Tourism
75	TAWA/Kilwa	Government	Public Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
76	Fisheries Officer/Kilwa District Council	Government	Public Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
77	PEC Hotel/Kilwa	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism
78	Kilwa Dreams Resort/Kilwa	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism
79	Kilwa Fishers Association/Kilwa Kivinje	Association	Association	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
80	Seaweed Farmer Cooperative of Kilwa Kivinje	Business	Private Sector	#11	Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
81	Alphakrust Ltd/Kilwa Kivinje	Business	Private Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture
82	Chole Mjini Tree House Lodge/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
83	MPRU/Mafia	Government	Public Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
84	Alphakrust Ltd/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture
85	Thanda Island Lodge/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
86	Kinasi Lodge/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
87	Mpogo Ocean Ranching Ltd/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture

88	Jibondo Marine Farmers Cooperative/Mafia	Business	Private Sector	#11	Fisheries, Aquaculture
89	Mafia Island Tourism Organisation /Mafia	NGO	Public Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
90	Nungwi Mnarani Aquarium/ Zanzibar	Business	Private Sector	#6	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
91	Baraka Aquarium/Zanzibar	Business	Private Sector	#6	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
92	Zanzibar Kilosas Conservation	Business	Private Sector	#6	Tourism, Alternative Livelihoods
93	Filao Beach by Sansi/Zanzibar	Business	Private Sector	#9	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
94	Mwani Zanzibar	Business	Private Sector	#9	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
95	Dar Es Salaam Ferry Fish Market	Government	Public Sector	#10	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
96	Ferry Market Stakeholders Committee/Dar es Salaam	Business	Private Sector	#10	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
97	Boat Building and Training Cooperative	Business	Private Sector	#3	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
98	Bagamoyo Fishers Association	Association	Public Sector	#3	Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods
99	Fanjove Island Resort/Songosongo	Business	Private Sector	#11	Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods
100	EU Blue Economy Program: Sustainable Coastal Tourism Project Development Team	Government	Public Sector	All	Tourism
101	Primetime Promotions/Dar es Salaam	Business	Private Sector	#10	Tourism

ANNEX 3. PRIORITY PARTNER PROFILES

<p>Alphakrust Ltd</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: East Africa, Worldwide</p>
<p>Seascope Focus: #1 Tanga; #11 Mafia-Kilwa</p>	<p>Website: www.alphaafrica.com</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Alpha Group is a global fish and seafood supplier with international operations in a wide range of frozen fish, seafood, and fresh products from more than 20 countries of origin to over 50 destinations worldwide. Buy fish and have own vessels, process and market sea food to local and export markets and main products include Nile perch from Lake Victoria, the largest freshwater lake in world and octopus, squid, lobster, prawn, crab, and other species in the Indian Ocean.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alfa includes a number of fish processing facilities including (1) modern trawlers with onboard freezing facilities in the Indian Ocean for harvesting the wild tiger and banana prawns, deep sea lobster and crab which are processed and frozen on-board; four Nile Perch processing facilities in Mwanza & Musoma in Tanzania, Entebe in Uganda, and Kisumu in Kenya and produces chilled & frozen filets and headless & gutted fish; and three seafood processing facilities in Dar es Salaam, Tanga and Mafia in Tanzania, and Mombasa in Kenya. • The Group is the first in East Africa to build and operate a 100-hectare black tiger prawn aquaculture farm in Mafia Island off the coast of Tanzania with hatchery for shrimp and tilapia that has been successfully certified by the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC). This standard advocates for responsible shrimp farming. • The Group imports fish - mainly tilapia, mackerel, and herrings, from various parts of the globe into East Africa and the imported fish are marketed widely which is a cheap source of protein compared to other local fish and meat which are very expensive for the population. Many small-scale traders and household populations get employment in dealing with these imported fish varieties. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Exports to many seafood buyers worldwide, sells regionally in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania market through shops, supermarkets in major cities and the ferry fish market in Dar es Salaam.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tanga has few fishermen and harvest is limited - fail to meet the processing capacity of 10 tons per day. • Dynamite fishing is still a challenge though not rampant as few years ago. • Most fishermen come from Pemba displacing Tanga local fishermen and the community's livelihoods • In Kenya there's no stringent regulations as in Tanzania include no levy while in Tanga the levy for harvested fish is 100 per kilograms. This results in smuggling of fish especially octopus to Kenya. • The lack of enforcement on regulations especially fishing in the Fishery Replenishment Zones (FRZ) and use banned fishing equipment and methods. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p>	

- Alpha Group is committed to supporting global seafood sustainability and supplying products that are fully traceable from sustainable sources. Most of their products and facilities have approval and are certified by local competent authority and the European Union.
- The Group is keen to promote and support small to large scale aquaculture where they provide technology, extension services and larval from its Mafia hatchery. The shrimp farming project in Mafia Island, Tanzania has been successfully Certified by the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC). This standard advocates for responsible shrimp farming, addresses the potential environmental and social impact of farming such as loss of biodiversity, use of feed and water resources, disease management, and effects on local communities.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

Medium-High: Key stakeholder in sustainable fisheries with extensive market operations of importance for Tanzania fishing industries and coastal livelihoods. Buys from local fishers and have opportunity in supporting aquaculture and so community livelihoods. Put as medium high, as Heshimu Bahari needs to conduct additional due diligence on the environmental sustainability and potential impacts of the shrimp aquaculture production before considering as a diversified livelihood opportunity in Activity seascapes.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Support to Tanga fishers in increasing their fishing capacity and in sustainable way include fishing equipment (boats, gears, financing etc.) and services (cold storage and ice plant).
- Support fisheries department and marine parks in enforcement on regulations especially in patrols to prevent illegal fishing and fish smuggling to Kenya.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Market access and investment in cold chain.
- Aquaculture inputs supplies and technical support.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Community engagement and co-financing of aquaculture in coastal communities.
- Co-financing for improved fishing technologies including cold storage and transportation.

Point of Contact: Jagdip S. Dhadke,
Manager - Tanga Operations

Email: jagdipdhadke@gmail.com

<p>Chole Mjini Tree House Lodge</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Pwani region</p>
<p>Seascope Focus: #11 Mafia-Kilwa</p>	<p>Website: www.cholemjini.com</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Chole Mjini Tree House Lodge was established in 1993 on Chole Island, located in the Mafia Island Marine Park (MIMP) in southern Tanzania, about 125 km south of Dar es Salaam. A family-run lodge offers marine and cultural tourism, including unique accommodations with tree houses built with local labor and materials. The lodge owner is a PADI Master SCUBA Diver Trainer and a biologist with a Ph.D. in molecular biology, and his wife is also a biologist with a Master's, a PADI Divemaster, and accomplished underwater photographer and researches the beauty of microscopic invertebrates.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Treehouse accommodation starts at \$480 shared per day. • Tourism activities include swimming with whale sharks, sunset sailing and boat trips, scuba diving and snorkeling, day trips to the “Funguni” sandbank, paddle boarding, and Chole village tours. • Chole Mjini employs primarily local community members. • Involved in extensive conservation projects: work with other partners and providers of conservation education to the community and youth; scientific research including evaluating and monitoring coral health and assessing marine biodiversity; and coral restoration and plantations. • Established a Chole project in 1994 that directly benefited and empowered the Chole community and was financed by Chole Mjini Trust Fund, a UK-registered charity. Built schools and a hospital, supporting many Chole Island youth to receive education and employment. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Tourists from the USA and Europe.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust and lodge income have been severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Mafia Island tourism has been struggling with some hotels closing since the COVID-19 pandemic, and hotels find contributing to marine conservation and community livelihood support difficult. • Plastic ropes and bottles in seaweed farming affect coral restoration efforts. • Marine resources use conflicts between seaweed farmers, fishers, and boat operators due to a lack of land and marine spatial planning. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Environmental conservation is at the core of the lodge’s business operations and offering, given its location in the marine park and tree houses built in a dense natural forest restored and managed by the lodge since 1993. Actively protects the beach area of Chole Island, protecting and restoring reefs, facilitating conservation education and school conservation clubs, and contributing to coral reef health and marine biodiversity monitoring and research.</p>	

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: The lodge actively engages in marine conservation and community engagement in Mafia Island and can partner with Heshimu Bahari on marine research and conservation, and community livelihoods projects. They actively raise funds through their trust fund and other sources and employ local staff while sourcing materials locally to support the local community.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Expand Chole Mjini's reef restoration and community education activities to include the creation of coral nurseries and coral plantations on other islands, such as Jibondo Island.
- Support the establishment of a restoration plan for FRZs and work with Chole Mjini to help island communities create closures, no-take zones, patrols, and other marine conservation activities.
- Provide technical and financial support for a community beekeeping project in the mangrove forest, which would benefit conservation efforts and local livelihoods.
- Support seaweed farmers in accessing sustainable farming tools and inputs, such as biodegradable materials, instead of nylon rope and plastic bottles. Explore connecting Mafia seaweed farmers with C-WEED for better prices and extension and inputs support.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Technical support already has a framework of ongoing projects, and with its long experience in several marine conservation activities (coral reefs, mangroves, sea turtle nesting, etc) and community support,
- Funding networks/financing include own trust fund.
- Local knowledge and community mobilization.
- Sharing experiences and best practices.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Grant to fund marine conservation and community livelihood activities.
- Capacity to engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods (e.g. investors in processing and marketing of community products, financing partners, etc.).
- Technical support to design a sustainable financing approach for community's livelihood activities.

Point of Contact: Dr. Jean De Villiers, Director

Email: 2chole@gmail.com

<p>Blue Finance (Blue Alliance in Zanzibar)</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Marine conservation, fisheries, and aquaculture</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Pemba, Zanzibar</p>
<p>Seascape Focus # 7 Misali/Matumbini Islands, # 8 PECCA</p>	<p>Website: https://blue-finance.org</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Blue Finance is a social enterprise that manages Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) for governments around the world, regenerating 1,000,000 ha of high-biodiversity coral reefs, protecting 40 endangered species, and improving the livelihoods of >20,000 coastal community members. Established Blue Alliance Zanzibar as a local sister entity of Blue Finance.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blue Alliance signed a long-term collaborative management agreement with the Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries of the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar for the northern part of the Pemba Channel Conservation Area (PECCA), which aims to protect 17,000 ha of marine ecosystems and improve the livelihoods and food security of an estimated 8,000 households. • Four fields of operation include: (1) community development; (2) wildlife monitoring and conservation; (3) revenue stream development through sustainable eco-tourism, blue-carbon, and responsible aquaculture and (4) compliance through patrolling, community engagement and awareness campaigns. • With the support of the Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR), Ocean Risk and Resilience Alliance (ORRAA), impact investors and donors, Blue Finance has established an MPA blended finance facility that will provide up-front, and early-stage blended capital for Blue Alliance – Zanzibar. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Blue Finance has a global footprint, working directly with local communities, governments, and other stakeholders to provide MPA management services in Belize, Philippines, Indonesia, and Zanzibar. In Zanzibar, established a local NGO Blue Alliance, with Manta Resort/Kawanini Foundation, and partnered with the MoBEF.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <p>In Zanzibar, the main challenge they face is to ensure the success of the conservation enterprises, especially the sea cucumber hatchery/businesses, and source a sufficient mix of financing to build the conservation enterprises and implement the MMA Management. This includes seeking catalytic grants to complete the capital stack for their enterprise development activities.</p>	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Business model involves directly engaging with governments and the private sector in MPA management. Additionally, as they are a social enterprise, an impact-focused mindset for marine conservation is linked to their core mission.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>Medium-High: Held several meetings with representatives of Blue Finance/Blue Alliance, specifically around providing catalytic grants as co-financing the sea cucumber conservation enterprise, and</p>	

potentially supporting marine conservation activities. They are very interested in a partnership that could bring a 3x leverage ratio and expressed interest in expanding to other MMAs in the Activity-defined seascape areas.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Provide catalytic grant to support the sea cucumber enterprise (hatchery and grow out) under their North PECCA agreement. They are seeking a USD \$750,000 grant, which would then immediately mobilize 3x in investment from impact investors that are already ready to invest in the enterprise, or the project could put partial funding forward and request additional co-funding from other partners. A successful sea cucumber hatchery could support communities in Heshimu Bahari seascapes in Pemba.
- Include Blue Alliance in dialogues set up between eco-resorts, small island tourism investors, and government agencies as an example of private sector MMA management.
- Over the long-term, opportunities for investing in other enterprises connected to Blue Alliance, such as Samaki Bluu, a start-up company investing in building out high-quality fishery value chains from artisanal fishers in Pemba to supply hotels in Unguja. While they are not ready to partner, and requested Heshimu Bahari to follow-up in 6 months, Samaki Bluu has the potential to provide multiple benefits to fisher communities in Pemba, through increased quality, access to higher value markets and improved fisheries management.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Proven private sector-led MMA management.
- Blue economy technical capacity.
- Impact investors willing to invest capital after catalytic grant funding is provided.
- Willingness to expand to other seascapes in Tanzania.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Grant funds that could potentially be used as catalytic grant funding to unlock impact investing funds for “Blue Alliance” enterprises.
- Ability to act as a convening party to bring together relevant stakeholders that can potentially support Blue Finance’s activities.
- Technical expertise in blue economy.

Point of Contact: Nicolas Pascal, Executive Director & Co-Founder

Email: npascal@blue-finance.org

Capricorn Beach Cottages	
Sector Focus: Tourism, Alternative Livelihood, Fisheries	Geographic Focus: Tanga Region
Seascape Focus: #1 Tanga (TACMP)	Website: https://capricornbeachcottages.com/
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Capricorn Beach Cottages is in TACPM at Kigombe village – Muheza district, 30 Km south of Tanga. The hotel started business in 2014 and provides beach cottages and other facilities.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The hotel provides beach cottages accommodation and other related facilities. Offers a range of tours and activities to guests and other visits including marine tours and marine sports; fishing with local fishermen; Pangani river cruise through coconut groves and mangrove forests; cycling tour on the beaches of Ushongo; swimming, snorkeling, and diving at Maziwe Island, a submerged island; and visit to a Swahili family's home. • Supports conservation activities working closely with MPRU Tanga Centre Head Office, and a range of community social and livelihoods activities. Almost all permanent and temporary workers come from Kigombe village including builders and provide education to staff. • Buy most hotel supplies include food stuff (poultry products, vegetables, and fish), flowers, and furniture (chairs, table, beds, etc. with repairs) from the communities. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>USA and Europe tourists, and Kigombe and Muheza communities.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tanga coastal attractions are not promoted well by the government and tourism institutions. • COVID 19 pandemic had a major impact on the hotel's revenue with a large drop in visitors, which hasn't rebounded like other areas of Tanzania and Zanzibar. Many local businesses are closed or are limiting options for tourists who do visit. • Dynamite fishing and overfishing in waters souring the hotel. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports various conservation activities by working closely with the MPRU, such as sea turtle nest relocation, and with the community on beach cleaning. • Works with government and community Sea turtle nest relocating for protection – activity done with MPRU. 	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: The hotel is located in target seascape, the Tanga Marine Park, and it works actively with the government and communities to advance marine conservation and community social and livelihoods support activities. It employs a large number of permanent and temporary workers come from Kigombe village and buy most hotel supplies include food stuff (poultry products, vegetables, and fish), flowers, and furniture (chairs, table, beds, etc. with repairs) from the communities.</p>	
<p>Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advance marine conservation in the Tanga marine park. • Co-fund skills training for community members in alternative and diversified livelihoods including seaweed farming, other aquaculture production and spices processing. • Support market creation for community members. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buy community developed products like spices, seafood and other items and connect community members to other hotels in the area. • Local knowledge and community mobilization as a trusted neighbor. • Technical support with experience in several marine conservation activities (coral reefs, mangroves, sea-turtle nesting, octopus' closures, etc.). 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matching grant to support marine conservation and community livelihoods activities. • Engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods e.g., investors in processing and marketing of communities' products, financing partners (FIs), etc. • Develop and connect with the Tanga tourism promotion forum and policy dialogues with associations to improve the business and regulatory environment.
<p>Point of Contact: Ashok Pattni, Director and Owner</p>	<p>Email: najua52@gmail.com</p>

<p>Cargill and C-Weed Corporation</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Seaweed Aquaculture</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Kilwa, Mafia, Tanga, Pemba and Unguja</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Tanga, #11 Mafia-Kilwa, Zanzibar Seascapes</p>	<p>Website: https://www.cargill.com, https://cweed.com</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargill is one of the largest global food and agriculture companies, and a major buyer of seaweed. • C-WEED is largest Tanzania seaweed producer. 	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargill is a major buyer of red seaweed from Tanzania to process into carrageenan that they use in over 300 ingredient products for thickening, stabilizing, and gelling to use in food, beverage, and pharmaceuticals. • C-WEED invests in an exclusive network of over 205205,000 seaweed farmers in Zanzibar and now mainland Tanzania to produce quality red seaweed. Provides farming support from research development, seeding and engineering, training programs, to community livelihood. Supplier of dried seaweed to Cargill and other global manufacturers. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargill manufactures and supplies global food, beverage, and pharmaceutical manufacturers. • C-WEED supplies Cargill, Dupont and other carrageenan manufacturers in EU and USA. 	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Red seaweed production is declining in Tanzania despite investment, because of limited modern agronomy practices, low productivity, and climate change. • Limited licensing or contract farming limits investment. • Increasing the incomes of seaweed producers and building resilience to climate change. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargill launched the Red Seaweed Promise program in 2019 to address key sustainability challenges for harvesting red seaweed, while enhancing producer livelihoods, supporting local communities, and conserving the marine environment. • Cargill is committed to source 60 percent sustainable red seaweed by 2025, and interested in improving the marine habitats where seaweed is sourced and promoting plastic circularity in the production of seaweed. • C-WEED committed to minimizing environmental impact including shifting to more sustainable inputs to help curb the depletion of mangroves and ensuring proper disposal and keeping farming materials from drifting into the ocean. 	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: Strong alignment in geography covering several seascapes, engaged in seaweed aquaculture, an important sector, and livelihoods for coastal communities and women. Cargill and C-WEED are both interested in marine conservation and restoration, addressing climate change, and strengthening</p>	

livelihoods. Cargill already provides grants to C-WEED and is interested in scaling this work to other seascapes and communities with the project.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Leverage Cargill’s two year socio-economic and vulnerability research in seaweed producing communities to rapidly identify socio-economic vulnerability and livelihood options for seaweed producers and co-invest in strengthening resilient livelihoods.
- Conduct joint research to identify the impacts of seaweed production on critical habitats and develop mitigation measures to increase marine conservation and habitat restoration.
- Engage women seaweed producers and communities in Zanzibar and mainland Tanzania to improve productivity, increase access to technology and financing, and conserve and restore marine resources.
- Assess the climate change impacts of shallow water seaweed production in target seascapes and identify adaptation and resilience activities to continue to produce seaweed, train farmers and restore critical marine habitats.
- Engage C-WEED and the Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries in Zanzibar in dialogue to explore and potentially provide protections and incentives for C-WEED and other seaweed companies to invest in seaweed communities.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Market access
- Co-financing
- Socio-economic baselines in key communities
- Technical expertise

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Marine conservation baselines and expertise.
- Co-financing livelihoods and environmental improvement activities.

Point of Contact: Valeria Montalescot, Seaweed Specialist (Cargill); Hamil Soud, GM, C-WEED

Email: Valeria_Montalescot@cargill.com and morty@fazal.com

<p>Chumbe Island Coral Park</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Zanzibar</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: Unguja and Pemba, Zanzibar</p>	<p>Website: https://chumbeisland.com/</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Chumbe Island Coral Park (Chumbe Island) private nature reserve that was developed from 1991 for the conservation and sustainable management of uninhabited Chumbe Island off Zanzibar. The reserve includes a fully protected Coral Reef Sanctuary, Forest Reserve, Visitor and Education center, small eco-resort, nature walks, and historical monuments. All buildings and operations are based on eco-technology aiming at zero impact on the environment.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main driver of revenue is the eco-resort, which anchors its conservation activities. It also includes a fully protected Coral Reef Sanctuary (i.e., private sector led MMA management), Forest Reserve, Visitor and Education center, small eco-resort, nature walks, and historical monuments. • Other operations (which are more aligned to the operations of an NGO) include: (1) community engagement (ex. swimming lessons for women to create greater economic opportunity); (2) free educational excursions for local public schools; (3) MMA ranger training, connected to the private sector-led MMA management conducted; (4) empowerment of scientific research on the island; (4) engagement with other MMA-positive actions outside of the island, including the creation of a sustainable seafood guide. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>International and domestic tourist as guests and day visitors; and community members, scientists/researchers, local government, and other stakeholders connected to the local MMA.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private sector-led MMA management is inherently challenging, as there is a constant need to monitor the local reef systems for IUU fishing, which is logistically difficult and expensive. • While Chumbe is registered as a traditional private business, they are more closely related to a social enterprise. The only reason they are not officially a social enterprise is the Zanzibar government took away that official designation as an option for business registration. • Chumbe is currently successfully operating private sector-led MMA management within their footprint around Chumbe Island, but they lack the funding to expand their efforts, whether that be from a geographic or capacity building standpoint. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The company's objectives are non-commercial (in line with that of a social business), with the aim to create a model of financially and ecologically sustainable park management, where ecotourism supports conservation, research and comprehensive environmental education programs for local schools and other benefits for local people. • They are directly participating in private sector-led MMA management and have a direct connection to marine conservation as part of their business model. Moreover, the other actions Chumbe takes, 	

such as community engagement, scientific research, and sustainable seafood guide development, all have, in some way, a connection with marine conservation.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: Not only does the mission of Chumbe have direct alignment with Heshimu Bahari objectives, but based on initial conversations, they are very open to working with the Activity. Although Chumbe is not directly in a Heshimu Bahari seascape, they are located in between Changu-Bawe Marine Conservation Area (CHABAMCA) and Menai Bay Conservation Area. Also, they are interested and have unique expertise in private sector led training and capacity building for new small island investors and resorts.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Collaborate in the dissemination of sustainable seafood guide to hotel operators and restaurants in Zanzibar in partnership with the Zanzibar Tourism Commission and engage in the development and implementation of follow activities to work with interested operators on implementing more local sustainable sourcing.
- Include Chumbe in the Small Island Tourism Investors Forum and Eco-Resort peer-to-peer dialogues for sharing of sustainable island tourism management and private sector support for marine conservation and community development.
- Engage Chumbe to lead training and capacity building for small investors in Zanzibar, and other eco-resorts like lazy lagoon to conduct trainings and assessments on native plant conservation, solid waste management, proper mooring placement, and other aspects of environmental and marine conservation.
- Use Chumbe connections in ZATI and ZCT to effectively engage those organizations and connect with other sustainability minded hotels and tourism operators in Zanzibar.
- Opportunity for providing Chumbe with direct grants to further develop their private sector-led MMA management.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Experience in successful private sector-led MMA management in Zanzibar, including the infrastructure necessary to maintain their operations for long periods of time.
- Experience in other areas outside of Heshimu Bahari’s objective 3, such as supporting scientific research, community engagement and ranger training.
- Leverage funding and already partially developed initiatives, such as the sustainable seafood guide.
- Willingness to engage with both the Activity and other stakeholders in the target seascapes to share their best practices.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Ability to act as a convening partner for those currently operating or prospective small island tourism investors interested in engaging in private sector-led MMA management.
- Matching grant funds to support peer to peer training and capacity building for other island investors and hotel operators on environment sustainability, marine conservation, and other ecotourism activities.
- Technical expertise and capacity to help finish and publish a more robust sustainable seafood guide.

Point of Contact: [Richard Linney, General Manager](#); [Ben Taylor, Manager](#) Eleanor Carter, [Co-Director](#)

Email: manager@chumbeisland.com; ecarter.conservation@gmail.com

<p style="text-align: center;">Emayani Beach Lodge</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Tanga region</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Tanga, #2 Pangani</p>	<p>Website: https://www.emayanilodge.com/</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Emayani Beach Lodge is located 15 km South of Pangani and offers a unique beach facing the Indian Ocean that has 12 ensuite coastal bandas built and furnished using traditional style and materials, all within 50 meters of the beach, and have a spacious dining and lounge, bar, and gift shop. There is the Kwajoni airstrip about 1 km from the lodge.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <p>The lodge offers a variety of services including water sports, scuba diving, speedboat shuttle service to and from Kendwa, Zanzibar, marine and nature tours in the mangroves and surrounding coastal forest and boating/dhow cruises/tours.</p>	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Tourists from USA and Europe</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Destruction of planted mangroves, and education and conservation activities needed beyond Ushongo beach. • Limited financing as most members of Friends of Maziwe and especially hotels along Pangani and Tanga coast areas are closed since COVID-19 pandemic and the remaining few are struggling. Only Emayani lodge and Dorobo are active in financing conservation activities at Ushongo. • Key challenges in community livelihood support include: no EFD receipts for local suppliers; and villagers are reluctant in getting involved in alternative livelihood activities other than fishing to supply the hotels as they are content with fishing. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports nature protection activities including relocation of turtle nests for safety, coral reefs restoration, facilitate marine patrols for Maziwe island protection and enforcement fishing regulations, and mangrove planting and protection. • Support neighboring communities social and livelihood activities. 	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: Very committed to marine conservation with activities that aligns well with HB project. Extensive support to protect Maziwe Island (6 km offshore) biodiversity and mangrove planting and protection as these are the key areas of activities for Ushongo and lodge visitors. Promotes the lodge and Ushongo as a nature and ecotourism destination. They facilitate community livelihood activities esp. those of which the lodge can provide a market i.e., buys and facilitate selling of product from the community as key to conservation of coastal and marine resources.</p>	
<p>Objective 3: Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p>	

- Expand the lodges conservation activities to more communities and areas in the Pangani region
- Build capacity of Friends of Maziwe to be a private and community foundation with formal office for sustainability of conservation activities.
- Support to document as a best model and replication of the Emayani/Ushongo communities' activities to other nearby Pangani hotels and communities for private sector MMA management.

- What they bring to a potential partnership:**
- Experience sharing and learning.
 - Market access for local products and support to market creation.
 - Additional funding mobilization – through Friends of Maziwe and other sources.

- What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:**
- Provide matching grant funding and build partnerships to support marine conservation and community livelihood development.
 - Technical expertise and capacity to help set a sustainable ideal vehicle for Ushongo and Maziwe Island conservation.

Point of Contact: John Lawrane, Lodge Manager

Email: Jonsmath03@gmail.com

Equity Bank	
Sector Focus: Finance	Geographic Focus: Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, and Tanzania
Seascope Focus: All	Website: https://equitygroupholdings.com/
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Opening its doors in Tanzania in 2012, Equity Bank is a commercial bank that has eight total branches in Tanzania; six in Dar es Salaam, one in Arusha, and one in Mwanza. It is a member of the Equity Bank Group, headquartered in Nairobi, Kenya, which maintains financial services subsidiaries in Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Tanzania, and South Sudan. The Bank’s philosophy is to transform the lives and livelihoods of our people socially and economically by availing them modern, inclusive financial services that maximize their opportunities.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional bank financing (i.e., personal loans) and functions (i.e., deposits); small Business Loans, including two types of agriculture loans (one small-business agriculture loan and one equipment loan). • Utilize a bank agent model to reach customers that are further away from the physical branches. • New 5-year strategy plan focusing on: (1) food, agriculture, and extractives; (2) manufacturing and logistics; (3) investments. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eight total branches in Tanzania; six in Dar es Salaam, one in Arusha, and one in Mwanza. Parent company financial service subsidiaries are in Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Tanzania, and South Sudan. • Originally started with a customer base of 15 million people in 2012. By the end of the current five-year plan, Equity wants to expand that to 100 million people, with a focus on women and youth. 	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to mobilize different groups as potential customers; fluctuating and raising interest rates pricing out certain customers and the government’s slow bureaucratic processes. • From the perspective of the blue economy, the main challenge Equity faces is a lack of track record and capacity in this space, from both their corporate office and local branches. While the bank has provided loans for cold storage equipment in the past, it has not executed any other debt products within the blue economy space, such as financing for fisher and aquaculture inputs. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in marine conservation mainly falls within their “agriculture” pillar under their current five-year plan. They would like to expand to include different types of blue economy financing within this portfolio, to include fishers, aquaculture farmers, etc. Equity aims to have agriculture to constitute 5% of their loan portfolio, and expansion into the blue economy is essential to meeting that goal. Moreover, through this expansion into the blue economy lending, Equity can also bolster their goal of reaching 100 million customers by 2028. • Working with the government in Zanzibar to finance seaweed farming. Also providing financing to groups (i.e., savings groups) and SMEs, getting a guarantee from the Tanzania agricultural development bank, and providing them with business training. 	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (low/medium/high):</p> <p>High: As Equity Bank is already motivated to expand into the blue economy, with a focus on climate, into the areas where Heshimu Bahari is operating, there is great opportunity for synergy and for the</p>	

Activity to drive impact towards marine conservation by helping to expand and shape Equity’s blue economy strategy.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Support the development of specific blue economy loan products with Equity to ensure the type of financing they provide drives impact in the space.
- Help identify blue economy SMEs that require debt financing that Equity provides and explore technical and/or financial support to help SMEs to obtain the proper insurance policies.
- Building on their cold storage financing in agriculture to support cold storage companies or the expansion of cold storage in the blue economy as a key value improvement activity
- Support Equity in conducting/development several different types of assessments for loans, namely environmental assessments, feasibility studies, and landscape analyses.
- Provide Equity with capacity training and technical assistance on the blue economy, both from a corporate and local branch perspective, to increase their familiarity with the space and reduce the associated risks.
- Build off the already existing efforts Equity has for further engagement with the blue economy, namely seaweed financing and cold storage financing.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Debt financing to Heshimu Bahari stakeholders, likely SMEs, to make expand and invest in.
- Extension bank agent model to reach customers that are further away from the physical branches.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Technical assistance around structuring blue economy debt products.
- Ability to provide various studies and assessments to reduce risk of expansion into a new sector.
- Connection with blue economy stakeholders who may need debt financing (i.e., potential customers)
- Capacity building for bank staff to increase familiarity with the blue economy and decrease risk.

Fish Eagle Point

Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods	Geographic Focus: Tanga region
Seascape Focus: #1 Tanga (TACMP)	Website: www.fisheaglepoint.com
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>A family run lodge located 50 km north of Tanga City in Mkinga district, was established in 2009 and offers marine tourism including traditional cottages accommodation, boat rides and fishing and camping sites. However, the family started marine and forest conservation around the lodge and supporting the community's social and livelihood projects since 2008.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lodge offers marine and nature tourism including traditional cottages accommodation, boat rides and fishing and camping sites. Provides diving and snorkeling, kayaking, birding bird watching tours in the mangroves and surrounding coastal forest and boating/dhow cruises/tours. • Provides nature protection activities that include students' educational visits and volunteers hosting to support neighboring communities social and livelihood activities. Provides and promotes sustainable and responsible fishing and recreational fishing. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Tourists from USA and Europe</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must channel conservation and community development funds to other NGOs, since if they placed these funds in the company accounts it is treated as hotel income and taxed. • Too many fishers from Zanzibar and Pemba active in the Tanga negatively impacting local fishers catch and income, and MPRU wants to make all areas a marine park that would restrict all fishing. • Cost of tourism in the Tanga region is high due to poor accessibility, expensive transportation and flights, poor phone networks, poor roads, and limited electricity national grid connection • Tanga tourism and its attractions are not promoted. • Government fees for entry to marine parks, reserves, and conservation areas are too low to fund adequate surveillance and management services. MPRU charges USD \$20 for park entry. • Poor supply of freshwater in Subutuni area is a health challenge and makes home gardening a challenge. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>The owners are passionate about conservation and supporting community-based social and livelihood initiatives around the lodge, including restoring reefs; providing safe turtle nesting habitats; funding marine research and conservation projects; resorting and protecting mangroves; and facilitating marine patrols to monitor and enforce fishing and environmental regulations.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: One of few hotels actively engaged in marine conservation activities and community engagement in the Tanga region with a long history of programs and working closely with MPRU and the community. Sources foods products and other items locally and passionate in use of local spices. Actively raise funds for marine research & conservation and community projects.</p>	
<p>Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the hotel setup a foundation for Subutini marine conservation with community participation. 	

- Direct support to conservation activities with livelihoods impact e.g., replication of octopus closures in seven villages in Mkinga district.
- Co-financing community livelihood activities include skills training, technical support/technology, and access to market support.
- Explore carbon credit market for protected forest and coastal ecosystems like mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes.

- What they bring to a potential partnership:**
- Co-financing for joint conservation and community livelihoods activities.
 - Community products market access.
 - Local knowledge and community mobilization (trusted neighbor).
 - Share best practices and expertise in several marine conservation activities (coral reefs, mangroves, sea-turtle nesting, octopus closures, etc.).

- What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:**
- Grant funds to support marine conservation and community livelihood actions.
 - Technical expertise and capacity to help set a sustainable vehicle for marine conservation.
 - Connection to eco-resort peer-to-peer capacity building concept and engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihood initiatives.

Point of Contact: Simon Attwell, Director

Email: reservation@fisheaglepoint.com

<p style="text-align: center;">Labalaba Fanjove Island</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Songo Songo Island and Lindi Region</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Mafia-Kilwa</p>	<p>Website: https://www.labalaba.com/</p>
<p>Organization Description: Labalaba Fanjove Private Island lodge is owned by Selous Safari Company and is located south of Dar es Salaam. The island is part of the Songo Songo Islands archipelago which is composed of 22 reefs and four islands. The exclusive private island was established in 2018 in a lease agreement with Songo Songo village. Fanjove Island is one of Tanzania's most exclusive beach destinations surrounded by beautiful, powder-white, sand beaches and the crystal-clear water of the Indian Ocean with an enormous lagoon and 11 km of coral reef. The lodge has 10 villas, designed to minimize its environmental footprint with solar power employed for all the rooms, and the buildings are simple, stylish, and comfortable and building materials used are traditional, natural materials – sustainable wood, mukuti (palm leaves) and thatch. Access is by air to the neighboring island of Songo Songo, and a 30-minute boat transfer.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lodge offers marine and nature tourism including exclusive private island villas all built using only locally sourced materials. • The lodge is solar powered. • The lodge offers several marine based tourism activities include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Diving and snorkeling excursions ○ Kayaking ○ Dhow sailing ○ Bird watching - between November and March, the island is the destination for many migratory birds and has a rich diversity of bird life. • Provide nature and marine conservation programs and communities social and livelihood activities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Work with BMU and villagers to protect marine resources including prevention of illegal fishing. ○ Support marine patrols to protect extensive coral reefs by paying rangers, provided a patrol boat and 400 liters of petroleum per month. • Support community livelihoods activities include seaweed farming and value addition. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Already trained the community on seaweed farming. ○ Trained seaweed farmers on value addition in Zanzibar and Bagamoyo • Support community social services and activities, example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Support sport gears for football competitions ○ School repair and maintenance ○ Village requested support to build a fish market. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base: USA and Europe.</p>	

<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No clear community engagement framework by local government for investors in Songo Songo ward. • Seaweed farmers still need additional capacity building, and the lodge has limited resources. • Limited alternative livelihoods in the islands around Songo Songo other than fishing. • The hotel is forced to support marine protection and conservation because responsible public institutions are not nearby, they have limited resources, and they do not have trained rangers for enforcement of fishing regulations and patrols. • Occasional illegal fishing activities resulting in coral reef destructions. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Located in Songo Songo ward and occupying Fanjove island, the lodge is the only hotel in Kilwa district doing well and actively work with the community in marine conservation activities. Their business actively depends on sustainable marine conservation as most visitors' interest is on beach and marine sports. Have specific successful projects and programs for Songo Songo islands communities including social services support; seaweed farming support; sea turtle protection, and coral reef protection and restoration.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: See previous section above.</p>	
<p>Objective Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-finance establishment or ongoing projects of alternative livelihoods for Songo Songo island communities - farming and small industries (e.g. seaweed and coconuts). • Support the lodge to facilitate value addition training in Selous, Ruaha, Serengeti and Ngorongoro including basketry and weaving for Songo Songo island communities. • Support in establishment of FRZ to protect over 11 Kms of coral reef and create an FRZ. • Co-fund hands-on training courses on sea turtle protection to more communities in Songo Songo ward islands include knowledge of nest identification, translocation procedures, post-hatching excavations, and hatching codes of conduct in order to increase the survival rates of turtle nests. • Support to Songo Songo island marine conservation efforts and activities including education and patrols with community/BMU and other stakeholders' participation. Target activities could include: coral reef protection and restoration, sustainable fishing; rare fish and bird protection. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to co-finance agreed activities – as they are already financing community livelihoods projects and marine conservation activities. • Already have project implementation infrastructure in place. • Have local knowledge, community, and local government mobilization capacity as a reputable institution. • Technical support with experience in Songo Songo island and Kilwa marine conservation activities. • Potential to share best practices. 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant funds to support marine conservation actions. • Technical expertise and capacity to help set a sustainable vehicle for marine conservation – Kilwa Tourism Stakeholders Association recommended. • Capacity to engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods (e.g., investors in processing and marketing of communities' products, financing partners, etc.).
<p>Point of Contact: Xavier Marie, Owner</p>	<p>Email: xmarie@ciemarcopolo.com</p>

<p align="center">Fisheries Education and Training Agency (FETA)</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Fisheries, Aquaculture, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Tanzania</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: Tanzania Mainland Seascapes</p>	<p>Website: www.feta.ac.tz</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>FETA is a Government Institution under the MLF – Fisheries Sector. FETA was established on October 28, 2011 by merging two fisheries institutions; Mbegani Fisheries Development Centre (which was established in 1965) and Nyegezi Freshwater Fisheries Institute (which was established in 1967). FETA is fully accredited by the National Technical Education and has three boat building centers in Kigoma, Mwanza and Mikindani (Mtwara). Currently, FETA has five campuses of Mbegani (Bagamoyo-Coast Region), Nyegezi (Mwanza), Kibirizi (Kigoma), Mikindani (Mtwara), and Gabimori (Rorya, Mara). FETA has a unique role to play in Tanzania sustainable fisheries and marine resources utilization space based on its establishment mandate and performance over years.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <p>FETA plays a vital role Tanzania sustainable marine resources utilization as an engine of growth and employment in fisheries. Key activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of education and training in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fisheries science and technologies, aquaculture, fisheries management and allied fields. ○ Fish processing, value addition, quality assurance, and marketing. ○ Seaweed farming and value addition. ○ Coastal environmental resources management and conservation. • Provision of consultancy and extension services in fisheries, aquaculture, fishing vessels safety, and allied technologies. • Promotion of fish trade and aquaculture business. • Production of fishing boats, fishing gear, and aquaculture facilities. • Research on fisheries, aquaculture, and allied fields. 	

Stakeholders served/customer base:

- FETA's main clientele is the Tanzania private sector and they work through government, non-governmental, and development institutions to support the private sector (individual fishers, groups, cooperatives, and SMEs) in sustainable marine product utilization so as to increase income and contribute to marine conservation.
- FETA collaborated with different stakeholders and implemented several projects in capacity building, project implementation consultancy, and training and research. Partners have included:
 - IOC-Smartfish Programme
 - FAO
 - Larive International
 - UNDP
 - WWF
 - JICA
 - IFAD

Challenges to Operations:

Generally, FETA has limited financial resources to support the private sector and other stakeholders in fisheries and aquaculture. However, challenges of interest addressed by FETA and need improvement through training; provision of BDS; tools and equipment development and production; and end products development:

- Poor hygiene and sanitation in handling of fish throughout the whole fisheries value chain leading to spoilage.
- Inadequate fish handling, storage, processing facilities as well as lack of improved processing technologies.
- Seaweed production has increased tremendously with poor processing and no value addition – needed production of various seaweed products such as soap, jelly, carrageenan, shampoo, liquid soap, powder, and other products.
- Destruction of mangrove forest.
- Poor processing of mangrove honey and other fisheries resources.
- Inappropriate attitudinal, behavioral, and cultural conditions towards community-based management system.
- Poor recording and management of fisheries data.

Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:

FETA has resources (human and technical) to support most of the marine conservation and community livelihoods areas including:

- Providing education, research, and consultancy in marine resources management and sustainable utilization and trade.
- Working with communities, public institutions, and private sector in sustainable marine resources conservation and utilization.
- Producing and promoting improved technologies for marine resources utilization including production (e.g. seaweed farming, aquaculture), harvesting, processing, packaging, storage, and transportation.
- Possess practical curricula and professional trainers for training on sustainable marine resources utilization – farming/harvesting, processing and value addition.

<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: FETA has resources (human and technical) to support most of the marine conservation and community livelihood areas of interest to Heshimu Bahari and their collaboration can contribute to success of the Activity.</p>	
<p>Objective Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <p>Engage FETA to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support cooperatives to access fish processing facilities such as solar dryer, fish and sardine drying racks, and thiaroye smoking kiln. • Provision of training to fisheries stakeholders on improved processing, handling, packaging, labeling, marketing, and distribution. • Training seaweed farmers through cooperatives on production of various seaweed value added products such as soap, jelly, carrageenan, shampoo, liquid soap, and powder. • Provide technical support to coastal communities on mangrove forests-based beekeeping and honey-based product processing and marketing. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <p>Experts, training curricula, technology production capacity, network of potential co-financiers, presence in and relationships with local communities to foster buy-in, regulatory support, technical support, and use of their infrastructure (e.g., training facilities).</p>	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-kind grant for extending support to fisher groups, seaweed farmers cooperatives, coastal communities, and other stakeholders in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Accessing improved technologies in processing, handling, packaging, labeling, marketing, and distribution (fish, seaweed, and beekeeping). ○ Development and training on production of various seaweed and honey value added products such as foodstuff, cosmetics, include soap, shampoo, and powder.
<p>Point of Contact:</p> <p>Dr. Semvua Mzighani, CEO - FETA</p>	<p>Email:</p> <p>mbegani@feta.ac.tz; semvua.mzighani@feta.ac.tz</p>

CRBD Bank	
Sector Focus: Banking and Insurance	Geographic Focus: All of Tanzania
Seascope Focus: All	Website: https://crdbbank.co.tz/en
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>CRDB Bank was established in 1996 and is the largest commercial bank in Tanzania, with 254 branches, 6,000+ point of sales (POS) and more than 20,000 bank agents. Serving the East Africa region, CRDB provides a wide range of financial services to individuals, SMEs, and corporations with a driving purpose to improve livelihoods and deliver sustainable impact.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services include: (1) consumer banking; (2) business banking; (3) corporate banking; (4) institutional banking; (5) capital markets; (6) Islamic banking and; (7) bancassurance. • Examples of products include financial products to support local agribusiness; a dedicated credit line for climate adaptation technologies and practices; a credit guarantee facility to expand access to new borrowers; and a weather-indexed insurance product to help protect against losses from climate-related events. • Accredited with the UN Green Climate Fund (GCF) as a financial intermediary and executing entity for green projects that reduce or limit greenhouse gas emissions and adapt to challenges of climate change and its impact. CRDB is in the early stages of developing a new fund with the bank matching USD \$100 million from GCF for blue economy and climate adaptation funding. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With 254 individual bank branches in Tanzania, CRDB has an extremely large footprint over the local commercial banking market. • Through the diversity in products provided, they are seemingly able to capture a very large customer base, from traditional deposits to institutional banking. • By participating in a large climate adaptation fund with GCF, they will be able to broaden their reach even further to customers engaged in climate finance. 	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beyond challenges faced by a traditional commercial bank, CRDB does not currently have the knowledge/capacity to issue loans into the blue economy. Without this knowledge, it increases risk and makes them less likely to deploy these funds. • CRDB also has not conducted any feasibility/baseline studies on the blue economy in the communities they operate in, adding another layer of risk and making them more hesitant to deploy these funds. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Works with coastal community ANCOs and SACOs and interested in expanding financial offerings in the blue economy through their GCF co-funded climate adaptation fund.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: Not only have CRDB expressed interest in working within the blue economy, but they have also expressed explicit interest in working with Heshimu Bahari.</p>	

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- The Activity has several opportunities to engage with CRDB on the potential GCF blue economy climate adaptation fund that will deploy different types of climate finance in Tanzania:
 - Blue economy capacity building for CRDB local branches so they better understand blue economy financing opportunities as they are presented.
 - Feasibility studies/baseline studies for communities that may require blue economy financing to better understand local landscapes.
 - Connecting the CRDB-GCF fund with the DFC to understand if a loan guarantee is possible and necessary.
 - Application of blue economy technical assistance facility (through project grants) to further de-risk those CRDB-GCF investments.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Potential high volume of climate adaptation financing for blue economy financing fund and commercial loan products, for cooperatives and SMEs.
- Financial literacy and capacity training for fishery and aquaculture cooperatives, and SMEs.
- Extension reach and coverage across most of mainland Tanzania and Zanzibar.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Blue economy capacity building for CRDB Bank local staff and branches.
- New feasibility studies/already existing baseline surveys created by the project.
- Business development services and capacity building to prepare cooperatives and SMEs in project sites to receive banks financing.
- Connection with DFC for potential loan guarantee product on climate adaptation fund.
- Technical assistance facility for blue economy investments through climate adaptation fund.

Point of Contact: Lulu Mero, Senior Relationship Manager

Email: lulu.mero@crdbbank.co.tz

<p>Global Fund for Coral Reefs (GFCR)</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Marine Conservation, Financing</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Kenya and Tanzania & Global</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: All</p>	<p>Website: https://globalfundcoralreefs.org/portfolio/kenya-and-tanzania/, www.tanzania.wcs.org</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GFCR is a 10-year, USD \$625 million blended finance vehicle established through a coalition between United Nations agencies, financial institutions, and private philanthropy sources. It supports business models that can sustainably finance key conservation and development goals for coral reefs via two initiative funds. Technical assistance, capacity development, monitoring, and evaluation are provided via the grant fund, while the investment fund generates de-risked investment capital to maximize the impact of projects incubated by the grant fund. • Funded by GFCR, Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) is implementing the Miamba Yetu Sustainable Reef Investments program to support sustainable businesses and ventures that have a positive impact on coral reefs and the communities along the length of Kenya and Tanzania’s coasts – including the Zanzibar archipelago, focusing on the proposed Transboundary Conservation Area between southern Kenya and northern Tanzania. 	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Through their dual fund structure, GFCR can provide a full menu of financing options for its investors and their efforts towards coral reef conservation. The USD \$125 million grant fund, funded by donors, offers grant funding to support (1) financial structuring; (2) technical assistance; (3) capacity development; (4) development of policy; (5) background research; (6) monitoring and evaluation; (7) recoverable grants and (8) “blue” stimulus packages (in times of crisis). • The investment fund also has a wide range of investment options. On the concessionary capital side, guarantees, concessionary loans, and concessionary early equity investments are used to de-risk the overall investment. On the impact investor side, a combination of debt for SMEs, debt for start-ups, equity, loans, and bonds are used to fill the capital stack. • The types of investees GFCR pursues include: (1) eco-tourism; (2) sustainable fisheries and aquaculture; (3) MMAs with user fees; (4) blue carbon; (5) recycling; (6) water treatment; (7) alternative activities for subsistence and income; (8) and more. • Run by WCS, the Miamba Yetu program aims to offer USD \$6 million of GFCR grant support for businesses in Tanzania to further mobilize co-investments of over USD \$20 million over the next 8 to 10 years. This includes a first investment to Blue Finance, which involved a USD \$350,000 grant to support nature-based tourism initiatives, an underwater room operated by the Manta Resort, and MMA scientific and surveillance equipment for private sector-led MMA management. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GFCR has a global footprint for deployment of their wide range of financing options to “revenue generating projects” involved in coral reef conservation. Their grant fund is funded by donors, their investment fund is funded by concessionary debt providers and impact investors. • Specific to the Miamba Yetu program, stakeholders include those revenue generating businesses involved in coral reef conservation in Kenya and Tanzania. 	

<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <p>Lack of pipeline of bankable projects to invest that have connection to coral reef conservation. This narrow lens inherently makes it more difficult to find businesses with the interest and ability to meaningfully affect coral reef conservation.</p>	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>GFCR's core purpose is coral reef conservation, which is a subset of marine conservation.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: GFCR very closely aligned to the purpose of Heshimu Bahari, but they also (1) already have a close relationship with the Activity, as WCS is a subcontractor; (2) have a large pool of grant and concessionary finance, which the Activity could leverage through its marine conservation programming and; (3) have expressed issues around lack of pipeline, which the Activity is uniquely positioned to support in sourcing new coral reef conservation-focused investments.</p>	
<p>Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify coral reef conservation investment opportunities for GFCR and include them in any small island tourism investor forums, where the end goal would be to identify opportunities for investment in marine conservation for the small island tourism investors. • Co-finance marine conservation investments with GFCR through Heshimu Bahari's pool of grants. • Explore voluntary carbon credit scheme around mangroves they are working on together. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pool of USD \$250 million in coral reef financing across a wide range of financing tools. • Technical expertise from their staff around marine/coral reef conservation. • Ability to support in the due diligence of investment opportunities to better understand the viability of specific marine conservation investment opportunities. 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to act as a convening partner with small island tourism investors in Zanzibar interested in marine conservation and eco-resorts already engaging in private sector-led MMA management so they may serve as potential investment opportunities. • Grant fundings and the ability to co-invest in specific investment opportunities.
<p>Point of Contact: Global Fund For Coral Reefs</p>	<p>Email: gfcf@uncdf.org</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Kinasi Lodge</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Mafia Island and Pwani Region</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Mafia-Kilwa</p>	<p>Website: www.kinasilodge.com</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Kinasi Lodge is a boutique hotel on Mafia Island, approximately 100 km south of Dar es Salaam and A short ride across the island from the airport and the main town of Kilindoni, the lodge overlooks Chole Bay in Mafia Island Marine Park. This intimate and lovely resort, situated in an old cashew and coconut plantation, was established in 1995 and provides a luxury stay amidst stylish décor and magnificent natural surroundings of the protected marine park. The lodge is in the heart of the Mafia Island Marine Park so is ideal for diving, snorkeling and excursions.</p> <p>Kinasi works to involve business or profit-sharing partnerships with Mafia islanders, with skills development and entrepreneurial mentoring in agriculture and small business to progress a “partnerships4progress” model. The lodge supports extensive marine conservation, communities, social and livelihood projects since establishment. It partners with the MPRU and non-profits in a range of marine conservation programs and educational, sporting, and sustainable fishing programs with the communities in the Mafia Island.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lodge has 15 suites in coastal bandas and 2 double story villas all sited on the hilltop overlooking Chole bay and a private beach towards Chole, Juani and Jibondo islands in Mafia Island Marine Park. Villas prices starting at \$600 for a 3 days minimum stay • Provides boat rides, reef diving and snorkeling and kayaking around Chole Bay and Juani island. • Provide and promote sustainable and responsible fishing and recreational fishing 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Tourists from the United States and Europe</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited financing for non-business activities in Mafia due to reduced tourism caused by COVID-19 pandemic. • Need for improved promotion of Mafia's tourism attractions, and education and conservation activities in Mafia Island and surrounding communities. • Illegal fishing activities causing coral reef destruction and hampering tourism and coral reef restoration efforts 	

<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Kinasi tourism business depends to a larger extent on sustainable marine resources as such they have been involved for over 25 years in marine conservation projects such as working with stakeholders include Darwin Fund, MPRU, Chole Mjini Tree House Lodge, and Thanda Island in coral reefs protection, monitoring and restoration in Mafia Island waters and islands. This effort involves educating and working with Jibondo island, Juani island and Bweni communities on reef monitoring and restoration.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential:</p> <p>High: Over 25 years supporting marine conservation and community livelihood activities in Mafia Island and works closely with MPRU and the community. Actively raise funds for marine research, conservation and community projects, and high potential to engage and co-fund activities with Heshimu Bahari in Mafia Island.</p>	
<p>Objective Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support on-going Kinasi Lodge marine conservation activities in Mafia Island with MPRU, and the community including coral reef restoration, sustainable fishing and rare fish protection (education, patrols) • Support conservation activities with positive livelihood benefits (e.g., youth scuba diving and boat captain training, and seaweed farming in three Mafia islands). • Co-financing livelihood activities include skills training, processing value addition, technical support/technology, and market access and marketing support. Target products – seaweed, beekeeping/honey and fish. • Establish a business section in the MITO to support local entrepreneurs to develop business plans and access finance. Explore setting up a revolving fund for youth entrepreneurship projects. • Support the lodge efforts in promoting vanilla farming in Mafia through work with Vanilla NEI limited.com in training and extension for vanilla production. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Over 25 years' experience in supporting conservation and community development in Mafia Island, and active projects. • Funding networks for co-financing activities. • Community products market access. • Local knowledge and community mobilization. • Technical support in marine conservation (e.g., coral reefs, sea-turtle nesting, octopus closures). 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant funds to co-find marine conservation actions. • Technical expertise and capacity to help build capacity of MITO to promote Mafia Island, and support Kinasi Lodge and other hotels to advance community livelihood and entrepreneurship activities. • Capacity to engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods e.g. investors in processing and marketing of communities' products, financing partners.
<p>Point of Contact: Peter Byrne, Director</p>	<p>Email: peter@mafiaisland.com; peterbyrnetanzania@gmail.com</p>

Lazy Lagoon/Fox Safaris	
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: Tanzania (Bagamoyo, Pangani (under development), land safari sites)
Seascape Focus: #3 Bagamoyo	Website: https://www.lazylagoonisland.com/
Organization Description: Lazy Lagoon Island Lodge is a high-end 12 room boutique hotel operating outside of Bagamoyo on a small peninsula. The Lodge is part of the Foxes Safari Camps group, which owns and operates other boutique safari lodges in or near national parks in Tanzania, mainly on the mainland.	
Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operates as a boutique hotel for higher-end tourism interested in a marine nature and activity experience, with direct access to both the ocean and the lagoon. The mangrove forests of Lazy Lagoon form a private nature reserve. • Connected to the Lodge is the Foxes Foundation, which is the parent company's charity which focuses on community engagement and wildlife conservation. 	
Stakeholders served/customer base: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caters to a mid to higher-end tourist market, which focuses on tourists traveling from Europe and interested in eco/nature resorts and safaris. • Engages and supports the local communities through community development activities and engages with local BMUs to support beach cleanups and to prevent dynamite fishing. • There are also many small-scale fishers who fish the reefs around the Lodge, but most of what they catch is not of the quality or size that the lodge can buy. 	
Challenges to Operations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The biggest challenge the Lodge faces is they would like to engage in more MMA management and marine conservation actions, but they have limited capacity and funding. A new hotel manager was just hired, and while he has a background in some marine conservation and is interested in further engaging with it, they are interested in learning about best practices and approaches for successful community engagement and private-sector engagement in MMA management. • Local fishers are putting a high amount of stress on the reefs directly around the Lodge and the lagoon leading to overfishing. There was historically a lot of dynamite fishing, but this has slowed working with local authorities. • Illegal, unregulated tourism is taking place on the Lodge's land and even after speaking with local authorities, management cannot prevent it. The illegal tourism operators and squatters have cut mangroves, and often litter the beach and leave their trash without removing it. 	
Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:	

- From a business perspective, the Lodge would like to foster a healthy marine environment around the hotel (i.e., coral reefs, mangroves, etc.) to feature as an attraction and develop new experiences for their guests. They already provide opportunities for guests to donate to conservation and community development activities, but they are interested in developing activities like coral replanting that attract guests.
- From an impact perspective, the parent company, Foxes Safari Camps, has been engaging in conservation and community engagement efforts for several decades and would like to expand those efforts at this location.

Alliance/Partnership Potential:

High: While the Lodge has had only limited private sector-led MMA management in the past, they are very interested and motivated to accelerate their efforts in the future. This leaves a lot of potential for support from Heshimu Bahari in these efforts.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Include in the Eco-Resort peer-to-peer dialogues so other eco-resorts that are more advanced in their private sector-led MMA efforts may share best practices for sustainable island tourism management, private sector support for marine conservation, and community development.
- Expand marine conservation and community engagement activities in areas around the lodge, including coral restoration, community patrols, establishing fishery replenishment zones, engaging more effectively with BMUs, and supporting enterprises and resilient livelihoods.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Co-financing of marine conservation and restoration activities like coral replanting.
- Established relationships with the fishing villages and BMUs.
- Develop new activities for guests to participate in and donate to marine conservation and community engagement.
- Potential for private sector-led MMA management in an Activity-defined seascape.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Act as a convening partner with other small island tourism investors and eco-resorts already engaging in MMA management to share best practices.
- Grant funds/technical assistance to support the initiation and expansion of MMA management.
- Ability to connect with capital sources to finance marine conservation activities.
- Ability to help develop new environmental impact assessments (and other types of assessments/studies) that can be applied to their property.

Point of Contact: Robin Carlise, Manager

Email: lazy@safaricamps.info

<p style="text-align: center;">Mwani Zanzibar</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Seaweed Aquaculture</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Unguja</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: # 9 Eastern Unguja</p>	<p>Website: www.mwanizanzibar.com</p>
<p><u>Organization Description:</u></p> <p>Mwani Zanzibar Ltd is one of the leading seaweed products manufacturer and products development companies in Tanzania, based in Paje, Zanzibar. Started as an NGO in 2012, was transformed in 2019 into the company - Mwani Zanzibar ranked as Tanzania’s unique researcher and producer of high-quality seaweed based premium skincare cosmetics. Mwani Zanzibar employs seaweed farmers in Paje to supply quality seaweed.</p>	
<p><u>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main function is production of high-end cosmetics and skin care products based on seaweed farmed by Paje women for local and international markets. • Mwani Zanzibar’s status is officially carbon neutral, certified with Climate Partner. • Have a product line that they sell locally, with 13 SKUs, • Launched a new product recently in the USA with 4 SKUs (www.mwanizanzibar.com/collection). • Work with 10 seaweed farmers who receive over 900% more than regular seaweed farmers around the island, specifically NET 450,000 TZS. They are employed full time, and have full benefits (e.g., maternity, sick leave, and holiday leave). • Farm within an area that is approximately 5,000sqm with employed seaweed farmers. • Invests in an exclusive network of 180 input suppliers in Zanzibar and other places to supply quality inputs needed for its products include coconut oil and honey from mangroves. • Provides farming support from research and development, seeding and training programs, and is looking to expand the network as its operations expand. 	
<p><u>Stakeholders served/customer base:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mwani Zanzibar manufactures premium skincare products currently targeting Tanzania and USA markets. 	
<p><u>Challenges to Operations:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zanzibar is currently suffering from heavy power outages, whereby our production frequently stalls. • Lack of resources to produce quality seaweed and research on quality improvement and new seaweed-based products. • No official farmers and buyers framework (licensing or contract farming) on seaweed production and selling leading to lack of guarantee for quality seaweed supplies. They have to employ seaweed farmers to guarantee quality inputs and pay nine times the average income of a seaweed farmer. • The government role and support in seaweed business is limited. 	

Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:

Focused on local production of high-end cosmetics and skin care products based on seaweed farmed by Paje women for local and international markets, while providing employment to Paje and Zanzibar residents. The company is dedicated to increasing its impact and reach in environmental regeneration and community and currently. They invest in local production, in seaweed farmers and communities to increase productivity, quality and incomes and committed to minimizing environmental impact of seaweed production, and continuing to invest in a network of seaweed farmers to guarantee quality supplies and alternative livelihoods to coastal communities and reduce pressure on unsustainable fishing.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: Invests in local seaweed end-products, seaweed farmers and communities to increase productivity, quality, and incomes. They are committed to minimizing environmental impact of seaweed production and continuing to invest in a network seaweed farmer to guarantee quality supplies, provide alternative livelihoods to coastal communities, and reduce pressure on unsustainable fishing. A partnership could expand their production to benefit more people and/or increase incomes.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Co-financing and research on more seaweed products and sustainable production inputs in order to compete with brands worldwide.
- Support access to finance to invest into new production equipment and solar energy to expand production and benefit local communities through seaweed incomes and employment.
- Support the market expansion through local promotion campaigns and international expos to benefit the expansion of women seaweed farming workforce and a wider impact on Mwani Zanzibar supply chain.
- Use Mwani Zanzibar operations to promote investment in local quality seaweed final products processing facilities/businesses.
- Support to expand Mwani Zanzibar’s network of seaweed farmers in Zanzibar and to set up raw material supply chains locally and training of local communities.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Extensive expertise and experience in seaweed products research, production, and markets.
- Production facilities that employ women seaweed farmers and products.
- A network of over 180 input suppliers.
- Extensive expertise and experience in seaweed farming.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Co-financing livelihoods and environmental improvement activities.
- Access to finance support. A network/connection of potential investors and support institutions.

Point of Contact: Klaartje Schade, Director

Email: hello@mwanizanzibar.com

&Beyond/Mnemba Island Lodge	
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: Africa, South America, Asia
Seascape Focus: Eastern Unguja	Website: https://www.andbeyond.com/
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>&BEYOND operates 29 luxury lodges across Africa, Asia, and South America, each built to blend with their respective region’s pristine surroundings. Through their work, they also operate a foundation that drives impact among the wildlife, land, and communities that surround their hotels. By incorporating conservation and community engagement work in their business strategies, not only are they making a positive impact in the areas around their hotels, but they are also making an investment which improves guest experience.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • &Beyond operates the 12-room Mnemba Island Lodge on the eastern coast of Zanzibar, a luxury ‘eco resort’ that offers a premium hotel experience for high-end tourists. • As part of their actions for conservation and community engagement around the Mnemba Island Lodge, &Beyond also operates a private sector-led marine conservation area around their island and engages with local communities by providing education and health programs. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers are high-end tourists with Mnemba Island Lodge priced USD \$1,500 per-person per-night. • Stakeholders of their impact work include: (1) those operating in the blue economy in their managed MMA, such as local fisherman, scuba boats, and dolphin boats; (2) community members working with &Beyond in their MMA management efforts, such as the local rangers employed and; (3) community members &Beyond works with in their health and education programs. 	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The hotel is generally well operated and profitable, they do face challenges around other tourists coming to their protected reefs and damaging them. While this has been partially addressed through the creation of a separate artificial reef other tourists can visit and by rangers patrolling the area, it was expressed that this is still an ongoing issue. • The island itself is shifting due to erosion. The problem can be solved through planting more native trees; however, they are receiving resistance from the government to do so. • A high volume of dolphin and snorkeling boats operating in the area are stressing the local reef system and marine life. 	

Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:

The hotel directly engages in private sector-led MMA management as part of their broader corporate impact focus. This covers ranger programs, community engagement, scientific research, coral restoration/growing, and more.

Alliance/Partnership Potential:

High: &Beyond has already expressed an interest in working with Heshimu Bahari on a variety of fronts. Moreover, their interest in partnership is highlighted through (1) their PSSA interview follow-up meeting, which was quite lengthy and outlined all the areas for potential partnership from their perspective and; (2) their participation in the first Zanzibar Small Island Investors Forum on August 31, 2023, where they presented their model and served as a 'best practice' for other small island tourism investors interested in marine conservation.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Include &Beyond in the Small Island Tourism Investors Forum and Eco-Resort peer-to-peer dialogues for sharing best practices of sustainable island tourism management, private sector-led MMA management and marine conservation and community development.
- Further develop private sector-led MMA management, marine conservation, blue economy enterprise development, and community engagement efforts such as:
 - Accelerate their MMA management ranger training program (in partnership with the marine conservation department, under the Ministry of Blue Economy and Fisheries). The impact of this training program acceleration could go past just their local MMA.
 - Support their initiative to train women tourism guides, part of which involves helping them obtain drivers licenses and diving qualifications.
 - Train boat captains (such as the dolphin boats operating in and around the MMA &Beyond manages) on marine conservation principles and best practices.
 - Support their "hustle economy" program, which will provide small grants for local enterprises. Specifically, &Beyond requested support from the Activity in recruiting facilitators and supporting the entrepreneurs.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Decades of experience operating private sector-led MMA management, and programs that align well with the Activity’s objectives.
- Willingness to serve as a leader to showcase “best practices” for other small island tourism investors interested in marine conservation to adopt.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Ability to serve as a convening party for other small island tourism investors to drive further impact in marine conservation.
- Grant funding to support and accelerate &Beyond’s private sector-led MMA management and community engagement efforts.

Point of Contact: Dr. Andrew Venter, Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Africa Foundation

Email: andrew.venter@africafoundation.org.za

SEAF	
Sector Focus: Investment Management and BDS	Geographic Focus: Arusha, Morogoro, Dodoma and Dar Es Salaam
Seascape Focus: All	Website: https://ceed-global.org/blog/tag/tanzania/
Organization Description:	
<p>SEAF is an SEC-registered global impact investment management company located in Washington, D.C, with 15 offices in Central and Eastern Europe, Latin America, the Caribbean, Asia, the Middle East, North Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa. SEAF in 2006 founded the Center for Entrepreneurship and Executive Development (CEED global) to support growth stage entrepreneurs through business training, mentoring, and networking to build local entrepreneurial ecosystems. SEAF entered Tanzania in 2017 with a grant from the USDA Food for Progress program, the center initially served SMEs in the agribusiness sector.</p>	
Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develops and connects entrepreneurs who want to grow as leaders, build their companies and give back to their community. • Provide the knowledge and support that help generate long-term social, economic, and environmental sustainability for SMEs throughout the value chain. • SEAF has 37 active members and another 92 enterprises and entrepreneurs who regularly engage with the community and programming. • New Daraja Impact program funded by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation supports Tanzanian enterprises that have a positive impact on women and youth, by providing investment capital and technical assistance to foster growth, resilience, and financial sustainability. 	
Stakeholders served/customer base:	
<p>Focus on entrepreneurs with growth potential based in Arusha, Morogoro, Dodoma and Dar Es Salaam but also looking for opportunities in other regions.</p>	
Challenges to Operations:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too risky to support private sector SME growth and investment in fisheries - supported four businesses in the marine sector – fish farming in the lake zone area - seems to be less familiar with the fisheries and marine sectors). • Willingness to pay for BDS is an issue for most SMEs in Tanzania, though they will pay for business plans that help with bank financing and if required to compliance with tax authorities. • Default rate was limited but rose especially during and after COVID 19 – 80-90% companies had a hard time with large drops in revenue. 	
Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:	

Supporting women entrepreneurs has been a major focus and 59% of the enterprises with CEED membership are women-led. Not much on marine conservation but SEAF focused on impact investments and adherence to environment and nature protection effects in addition to financial gains is a key factor in its support.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: Strong potential alignment in terms of the catalytic fund supporting growth SMEs and interest in coastal/marine. Doesn't have presence yet in seascapes, outside of Dar es Salaam and would need support to build capacity.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Identification of SMEs and opportunities for SEAF to invest in.
- Co-investment in businesses through catalytic grants.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Catalytic funding (grants/loans).
- Post investment technical assistance.
- Expertise in setting up and running a fund in Tanzania (offshore).
- Support SME growth connected to youth and women livelihoods.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- A pipeline of growth SMEs operating or engaging in target seascapes that support youth and women livelihoods, value chain enhancement and marine conservation.
- Co-financing/de-risking financing.
- Technical assistance.

Point of Contact: Atiba Amalile, East Africa Director

Email: aamalile@ceed-tanzania.org

Mizizi	Logo N/A
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: Zanzibar
Seascape Focus: #7	Website: n/a
Organization Description:	
<p>Mizizi is a real estate developer and hotel operator in Zanzibar. While they do not have a website, it is unclear on the size and scope of the organization. From our conversations with their representative Sally Beck, we know they are setting up a “health resort” off the coast of Pemba and have other residential real estate developments around Zanzibar. They also have a foundation, the Mizizi Foundation, which seems to be partially funded by the business and has a variety of community development focus areas (nutrition, WASH, education, etc.).</p>	
Point of Contact: Salley Beck	Email: sally@sallybeck.co.uk
Tullia Pamunda	
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: Zanzibar
Seascape Focus: #4	Website: https://www.tuliagroup.com/tulia-pamunda/
Organization Description:	
<p>Tulia Pamunda Island is an exclusive island resort with overwater and coral on Pamunda Island on the southwest coast of Zanzibar (Unguja). Tulia Pamunda Resort is a high-end luxury property and offers a multitude of amenities including a luxurious spa and sauna world, its own traditional Elias jewelry workshop, helicopter and boat transfers, and a host of sporting activities both inside the resort and on the ocean.</p>	
Point of Contact: Lukas Sinogl	Email: GM@tuliazanzibar.com
Paradise and Wilderness Group	 PARADISE & WILDERNESS <small>Hotels · Resorts · Lodges · Camps · Safaris · Aviation</small>
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: All of Tanzania
Seascape Focus: #7	Website: https://paradise-wilderness.com/
Organization Description:	
<p>The Paradise and Wilderness Group is a Dutch family-owned hospitality business and one of the leading travel, hotel, and safari companies in Tanzania and Zanzibar.</p>	
Point of Contact: Bert Schoonvelde, CEO, and owner	Email: bert@hotelzanzibar.com
Organization(s) Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:	

Each small island tourism investor is either planning to or currently developing a hotel on an island off the coast of Unguja/Pemba.

Stakeholders served/customer base:

- All are appealing to high-end tourists; generally, those willing to pay higher than average prices for their tourism excursion.
- Mizizi specifically can be considered a “health resort,” meaning their customers are people interested in the “natural healing” services the hotel will offer.

Challenges to Operations:

- All face the inherent challenges with opening a hotel in Zanzibar, including high taxes, government bureaucracy, challenges with local infrastructure (especially on Pemba Island).
- Specific to Tullia Pamunda, their representative expressed a challenge around an intertidal area that is perceived to have a negative value to the hotel, and they would like to renovate.

Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:

All three investors attended the first Zanzibar Small Island Tourism Investors Forum on August 31, 2023. The purpose of the event was to start the conversation around how these small island tourism investors can incorporate marine conservation into their operations.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: These investors attended the small island investor dialogue meeting and expressed some interest in exploring marine conservation in their planned island operations. Since each operates in a target seascape, there is an opportunity to engage them early in the development of their operations, when possible, to initiate actions towards marine conservation.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Include investors in any discussions with other small island tourism investors and existing eco-resorts to share best practices on marine conservation, MMA management, etc.
- Engage investors to initiate baseline environmental and marine conservation assessments and initiate marine conservation activities early in the operation of their hotels on small island.
- Connect with investors with other capital sources, if interested, to co-fund marine conservation and community livelihood activities (i.e., GFCR).

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Opportunity for partnership to drive marine conservation efforts with the private sector in Activity-defined seascapes.
- Upcoming or ongoing investments in the development of hotel and resorts infrastructure and operations on small island in priority seascapes in Unguja and Pemba.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Act as a convening partner with other small island tourism investors, eco-resorts, and government to share best practices on marine conservation in island environments.
- Co-funding and technical assistance to support the initiation and expansion of marine conservation and community engagement activities.
- Ability to connect with capital sources to finance marine conservation activities.

<p align="center">Tanga Cooperatives Deep Sea, Tanga UWAWABIMA, Pangani</p>	<p align="center">Logo N/A</p>
<p>Sector Focus: Fisheries</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Tanga region</p>
<p>Seascope Focus: #1 Tanga (TACMP); #2 Pangani (USTASAKI CFM)</p>	<p>Website: N/A</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UWAWABIMA is based in the Kipumbwi and Pangani Districts. Members are involved in the fishing and processing of dagaa, selling up to 50 tons of each week mainly to Congo traders and, to a more limited extent, Zambian traders via local agents. • Deep-Sea Cooperative Society based in Tanga City, whose members generally rent small boats to fish in the local waters and sell the fish to several traders in the deep-sea fish market who then sell onto the Tanga market and Dar es Salaam ferry market. 	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <p>Both cooperatives provide the following services and functions for its members:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinate fishers and traders’ activities in fish markets, include collection of levies, in collaboration with local government fisheries officers and BMUs in enforcing fishing regulations. Collaboration includes monitoring fishing activities at sea and inspection of fish at port before selling and report any abuse/use of illegal fishing methods – dynamite, poison, illegal nets, etc. • Provide a forum for dialogue between fishers and the government on the Kipumbwi/Deep Sea fish markets operations – sanitation, fish selling/auction, auxiliary service arrangements. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Small-scale fishers, traders/buyers, service providers – boat owners, food vendors in the Tanga and Pangani regions.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited ownership of equipment, including boats, forces fishers to pay for daily boat rentals, and the lack of formal financing means they take informal loans with unfavorable terms for boat rentals and other fishing equipment and inputs. • Poor and inefficient processing methods leads to low prices and high wastage especially for dagaa fish (Swahili for “anchovy”), a key species for the region, which artisanal processors dry using firewood collected from mangroves and local forests leading to deforestation. • Poor or non-existent post-harvest value chain infrastructure, such as cold chain, ice production and reefer transportation, limits access to more distant and higher value markets and leads to post-harvest waste and low prices paid to small-scale fishers. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>Interest in increasing the income of members and working with fishers to take an active role in the prevention of and reporting to relevant authorities (fisheries officers, MPRU and BMUs) of illegal fishing methods and fishing in FRZs.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: The two cooperatives are key private sector stakeholders in the fisheries sector in Tanga (#1) and Pangani (#2), offering Heshimu Bahari engagement with over 80 small-scale fisher and trader</p>	

members. Strong cooperatives with functioning management are important to support value addition, access to finance and sustainable fisheries as working with individual small-scale fishers can be complicated, expensive, and ineffective. These cooperatives can play a key role in building awareness and buy-in from local fishers for adopting sustainable fisheries, and engaging with fisheries officers, MPRU and BMUs in monitoring and compliance activities including reporting illegal fishing.

Objective 3: Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- BDS support for fisher cooperative management and members on financial management and literacy; business planning; proper fish handling and processing practices, and other relevant practices.
- Connect cooperatives with cost-effective financing from several sources including the Tanzania Agriculture Development Bank (TADB), WCS Blue Financing Association/Groups program, and commercial finance partners like CRDB and Equity Bank.
- Increase access to better markets through value chain inputs, such as inputs to improve product quality and cold storage linkages, and by connecting cooperatives to companies that offer inputs.
- Engage cooperatives in sustainable fisheries management and FRZ initiatives to protect local fish stocks and reduce IUU fishing, with the long-term goal of increasing buy-in by demonstrating the resulting increased incomes.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Engage cooperative members in partnership activities with Heshimu Bahari and build commitment and buy-in from members to support sustainable fisheries.
- Bring expertise and knowledge of local fishing sector context.
- Contribute co-funding and resources (staff time, facilities etc.) to capacity building activities for members.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Provide grant funding, capacity building and facilitate partnerships to improve post-harvest handling, improve quality and increase access to markets.
- Connect with the Activity's, government and other donor/NGO fisheries management activities, and support cooperatives for long-term behavior change initiatives around sustainable fisheries and FRZ management.

Point of Contact:

- Saidi Issa, Chairperson - UWAWABIMA
- Rashidi Saidi – Chairperson, Deep Sea Cooperative

Email:

- wavuikipumbwi@gmail.com
- ushiwade@gmail.com

<p align="center">Tanga Tourism Network Association (TATONA)</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Tanga</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Tanga (TACMP)</p>	<p>Website: http://www.tangatourism.org/</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TATONA is an umbrella organization representing key tourism businesses in Tanga region with keen interest in sustainable MMAs for hotels' sea food supply, recreational fisheries, and other beach/sea sports and eco-tourism activities. • Has 20+ active members that include Tanga region hoteliers, tour operators, restaurant owners, transporters, and crafts people. TATONA members provide a sector that is an important market for marine products, community livelihood activities. 	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused on the development of Tanga tourism to boost the region's economic development that is culturally sensitive, socially responsible, ecologically friendly, and environmentally sustainable. Have a tourism promotion office with information center in Tanga City. • Carry-out regular advocacy engagement with key tourism sector stakeholders and regulators includes MPRU and local government. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Tourists, hoteliers, tour operators, restaurant owners, transporters, crafts people, MPRU and other government institutions.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited effort by the government to promote and support Tanga's tourism sector in coastal and marine areas when compared to inland regions in mainland Tanzania. • Comparatively high cost for tourists to visit the region compared to other destinations as result of limited flights, expensive hotels and transportation, and unfavorable government policies. • Poor infrastructure connected with marine parks, communication networks, and transportation networks create hurdles for tourism-focused businesses to improve their services. Furthermore, limited accessibility to communication networks and the national electricity grid, along with expensive transportation to and from the region present additional barriers to sector growth • Business closures by many tourism investors and hotel operators due to the COVID-19 economic downturn and generally burdensome government fees. • Moreover, inadequate marine conservation efforts have resulted in the destruction of mangrove forests and depletion of fisheries from illegal and overfishing, lowering the overall attraction value of coastal and marine sites. 	
<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Given TATONA's focus on developing a culturally sensitive, socially responsible, and environmentally sustainable tourism sector, there is opportunity for Heshimu Bahari to work with TATONA to promote investment in Tanga and Pangani tourism sectors as a vehicle for sustainable marine conservation and the region's economic development. 	

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: Umbrella organization representing key private sector actors in Tanga tourism sectors, important in mobilizing tourism stakeholders for marine conservation and related activities.

Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Hold public-private dialogues involving TATONA, investors, HAT, MPRU, MNRT, TTB, MLF, WCS and others to discuss and establish the enabling environment for private investment in marine conservation. This includes marine park fees, demarcations of parks, PPP and regulatory environment for marine parks, MMA, and tourism investment.
- Organize a Tanga and Pangani tourism promotion forum to showcase Tanga region tourism attractions and mobilize various tourism stakeholders and eminent persons to support wider promotion of Tanga tourism especially relevant public institutions, tour operators and aviation industry, local and international tourism investors. The forum will support the development of a strategy and action plan to develop Tanga tourism with a strong steering committee to oversee implementation.
- Support TATONA tourism marketing activities including strengthening the effectiveness of the TATONA Tanga tourism information and marketing center located in Tanga City.

What they bring to a potential partnership:

- Co-organize policy dialogues and tourism promotion forum for Tanga and Pangani.
- Mobilize members for marine conservation, dialogues, tourism investments and promotion activities.
- Bring on ground experience and tourism sector knowledge sector.

What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:

- Engage partners to support promotion of investment in Tanga tourism including government agencies, financing partners, etc.
- Support in convening association meetings for advocacy and policy engagement on MMA investment, and the tourism promotion forum.
- Potential grant to TATONA to strengthen tourism marketing activities.

Point of Contact: Joseph Ngonyo – TATONA President

Email: gm@tangabeachresort.com

<p style="text-align: center;">Ten Degrees South</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Mtwara Island and Pwani Region</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #12 Mtwara</p>	<p>Website: www.tendegreessouth.com</p>
<p>Organization Description: Ten Degrees South Lodge, located on the Western Indian Ocean, opened in 1997 in Mikindani, one of the Swahili coast's historic trading towns and once the administrative capital of the Mtwara region in southern Tanzania. It is a small lodge with a view across Mikindani Bay and offers accommodation and a restaurant. Guests and visitors have discovered its tranquil, calm environment and explored the beaches and underwater wildlife of the Indian Ocean; the local beach is a short walk away. The lodge owns and operates a dive and marine research and education center that offers a range of diving activities and exploration of the pristine coral reefs of Mikindani Bay.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The organization offers marine and nature tourism services, including reef diving and snorkeling on Mikindani Bay. • They own and operate an eco2 diving, marine research, and education center that offers various diving activities and exploration of the pristine coral reefs of Mikindani Bay. • The company runs several marine conservation, community social, and livelihood projects in partnership with the Tanzanian Marine Parks (MPRU) in and around MBREMP-Mtwara. • Dive holidays are available starting from \$410 per person, with five days of sharing. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>Mainly eco and nature tourists from USA and Europe.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illegal fishing activities result in coral reef destruction and is a setback to tourism business and coral reef restoration efforts. This includes sea turtle poaching. • Very limited tourism activities in Mtwara region with few hotels active. Despite Ten Degrees South doing very well, in general, Mtwara tourism and its attractions are not yet adequately promoted and other hotels and businesses in Mtwara are struggling and so their contribution to conservation efforts is little. Needed to create a conducive environment for Mtwara tourism stakeholders to grow and tourism to develop. • Fishers do not have education on fishing regulations/laws before getting licenses. • Limited basic sea turtle and marine conservation education to fishers and coastal communities – a challenge to tourism attractions and business. • Limited supervision of seaweed farming regulations include farmers destruction of reefs by farmers 	

<p>Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:</p> <p>The lodge is located on the shores of the Indian Ocean at Mikandani Bay, Mtwara and depends on marine resources for business. The lodge runs several marine conservation projects: community social and livelihood projects since establishment and partners with MPRU in marine conservation activities in and around MBREMP. Passionate in marine conservation and community livelihoods activities. It has sea turtle protection and hospital projects; coral restoration project; and community livelihood projects.</p>	
<p>Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):</p> <p>High: Passionate in marine conservation and community livelihood activities. Its sea turtle protection and hospital, coral restoration, community livelihood projects; and efforts to create a FRZ in Mikindani Bay, fits well in many activities of Heshimu Bahari. Use own funds and actively raise funds for marine research, conservation, and community projects.</p>	
<p>Objective Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct support to conservation activities with livelihood impact includes coral restoration project and creation of FRZ in Mikandani Bay. • Direct support to other conservation activities includes sea turtle protection and hospital projects and school and community environment/ marine conservation training programs. • Co-financing community livelihood activities include skills training, technical support/technology, and access to market support. 	
<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding networks/financing and working with volunteers and academic institutions, • Ongoing activities, good relations with government institutions, local knowledge, and community mobilization, • Technical support with experience in several marine conservation activities (coral reefs, sea-turtle nesting, etc), • Share best practices. 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant funds to support marine conservation actions. • Technical expertise and capacity to help set a sustainable vehicle for marine conservation. • Capacity to engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods (e.g., investors in processing and marketing of communities' products, financing partners, etc.).
<p>Point of Contact: Laurent B., Director</p>	<p>Email: lbedoure@gmail.com</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Thanda Island</p>	
<p>Sector Focus: Tourism, Fisheries, Alternative Livelihoods</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Mafia Island and Pwani Region</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #1 Mafia-Kilwa</p>	<p>Website: www.thanda.com</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>Thanda Island is an exclusive private island located in Shungimbili Island Marine Reserve that has an exclusive villa accommodation with five suites and two traditional open-air Tanzanian bandas (beach chalets) and offers exclusive choice of water and marine activities. Established in 2016, Thanda Island occupies Shungimbili Island to the west of Mafia Island on a lease from MPRU and supports extensive marine conservation, and has supported community livelihoods projects since establishment.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The hotel offer marine and nature tourism including exclusive private island villa and beach chalet accommodation. • Provides boat rides, reef diving, snorkeling and kayaking around Shungimbili Island and Mafia Island widely regarded as having the most spectacular reefs for diving and snorkeling in sub-Saharan Africa. • Provide nature and marine conservation programs and communities social and livelihood activities that include educational, sporting and sustainable fishing programs with the communities in the Mafia Island. • Supports MPRU in marine patrol and manages MPRU patrol outpost. • Thanda's Star for Life program is being taught in six primary and two secondary schools on Mafia Island. • Provide and promote sustainable and responsible recreational fishing. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p> <p>USA and Europe.</p>	
<p>Challenges to Operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The hotel is forced to look for and support marine protection and conservation of Shungimbili island marine reserve and nearby Mafia Island Marine Park areas as MPRU has limited resources to manage these activities. • Illegal fishing activities results in coral reef destruction. • Despite Thanda doing very well, in general, Mafia tourism and its attractions are not yet adequately promoted and other hotels and businesses in Mafia are struggling and so their contribution to conservation efforts is limited. • Need to create conducive environment for Mafia tourism stakeholders to grow and tourism to develop. 	

Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:

Thanda Island partners with MPRU on a range of marine conservation and educational programs including the Ropes of Hope restoration of the coral reef project. These include research conservation initiatives associated with the marine reserve and Mafia Island Marine Park; include a conservation project for the restoration of the Shungimbili Island coral reefs in collaboration with local conservation partners and protection of marine turtles and rare fish.

Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):

High: Dedicated to marine conservation and community livelihoods activities. One of few hotels on Mafia Island actively engaged in marine conservation activities, community engagement, youth empowerment, and environmental education.

Objective Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:

- Support the hotel efforts in Mafia island marine conservation with MPRU, community and other stakeholders' participation. Target activities – coral reef restoration, sustainable fishing and rare fish protection (education, patrols).
- Direct support to conservation activities in Mafia islands:
- Adequate resources to MPRU and local fisheries department of the government for protection activities.
- Financing conservation efforts (e.g., coral restoration and eDNA research/assessment of marine biodiversity for protection and monitoring).
- Support education efforts to reduce dependency on marine resources and provide opportunities for alternative livelihoods.
- Co-financing community livelihood activities include:
 - Skills training, processing/value addition technical support/technology, and access to market support (market creation - advertising/promotion and related marketing activities).
 - Support business start-ups through skills and entrepreneurship training and financing arrangements.
 - Target products and businesses – horticulture, beekeeping/honey, poultry, coconut, fish processing and distribution, and retail businesses.

<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-finance and funding networks for co-financing agreed activities - community livelihoods projects, and marine conservation activities. • Already has project implementation infrastructure in place; • Have local knowledge, community, and local government mobilization capacity as trusted/reputable institution. • Technical support with experience in several marine conservation activities (coral reefs restoration, marine ecosystem/biodiversity assessment, etc), • Share best practices. 	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grant funds to support marine conservation actions. • Technical expertise and capacity to help set a sustainable vehicle for marine conservation • Capacity to engage other partners to support conservation and community livelihoods (e.g., investors in processing and marketing of communities products, financing partners , etc.)
<p>Point of Contact: Antigone Meda, Manager</p>	<p>Email: antigone@thandaisland.com</p>

<p>YP Investment Limited</p>	<p>Logo N/A</p>
<p>Sector Focus: Fisheries</p>	<p>Geographic Focus: Lake Victoria and Dar es Salaam</p>
<p>Seascape Focus: #4, #5, #6, #7, #8, #9</p>	<p>Website: N/A</p>
<p>Organization Description:</p> <p>A cold storage company founded in 2019 near Lake Victoria provides ice flakes to small-scale fishers and cold storage facilities that allow fishers to sell fish to more distant markets and get a higher price. Expanding to Dar es Salaam, investing in small reefer cars to provide transportation services, and expanding into tilapia processing.</p>	
<p>Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Currently has the capacity to supply 100 tons of ice flakes in 24 hours for small-scale fishers in the lake region and is one of the only independent suppliers of ice not connected to fish buyers. • Lake Victoria facility can store 24 tons of fish per cycle, , which allows fishers to maintain quality and sell fish to more distant markets at a higher price versus selling to local low value markets on non-shipping days. • Expanding to Dar es Salaam, setting up a cold storage facility and purchasing a fleet of reefer trucks that can transport fish from sites around the capital to the facility and to deliver to buyers. 	
<p>Stakeholders served/customer base:</p>	

Small-scale fish farmers and fishers in Lake Victoria region, and around Dar es Salaam.	
Challenges to Operations:	
Cost of financing is a major issue as they try to expand their operations into new locations with very high interests.	
Interests Connected with Marine Conservation:	
Supporting small-scale fishers to improve quality and access to markets to earn increased incomes. Have expressed they are interested in sustainable fisheries, expanding into the aquaculture sector, and approaching impact-oriented investors to source capital from for further expansion. Also interested in more sustainable practices, like using solar to reduce its carbon footprint though the cost of financing is too high.	
Alliance/Partnership Potential (high/medium/low):	
Medium-High: the company is expanding to Dar es Salaam and showed interest in other coastal areas of mainland Tanzania and followed up with the team to conduct site visits in the Tanga area. Cold-storage solutions are a major issue for small-scale fishers and cooperatives, and they are one of the only companies identified looking to provide solutions to small-scale fishers. As the company is only just expanding into mainland Tanzania, Heshimu Bahari should conduct additional follow-up and due diligence on the company's products and expansion plans.	
Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari:	
Provide small-scale fishers and cooperatives access to cold storage solutions to increase access to markets, improve quality and reduce loss, and create more efficiency, productivity, and profitability of artisanal fish value chains while simultaneously improving livelihoods and reducing pressure on marine ecosystems in mainland Tanzania seascapes.	
What they bring to a potential partnership:	What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand and provide cold storage solutions and reefer transportation for small-scale fishers and cooperatives in Dar es Salaam and other seascapes along the mainland coast. • Improve quality and access to higher value markets for small-scale fishers and cooperatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect and socialize YP investment to fisher cooperatives along the coast in mainland Tanzania in need of cold storage solutions and provide training and capacity for these fishers to improve quality. • Support YP investment to connect with more affordable financing options to expand the cold storage solutions. For example, SEAF could provide a grant that could support interest rate and further expansion. • Connect with different market players, future business partners and consultants.
Point of Contact: John Paul Chenge, Managing Director	Email: investmentyp@gmail.com

Zanzibar Association of Tourism Investors (ZATI)	
Sector Focus: Tourism	Geographic Focus: Zanzibar
Seascape Focus: All Zanzibar Seascapes	Website: https://zati.or.tz/wp/
Organization Description: <p>ZATI is a non-governmental, non-religious, and non-political membership-based organization, established in 2003 to represent the interests of all tourism investors in Zanzibar. 24 members that include hotels, cafés, souvenirs shops and companies outside direct tourism- insurance, hospitals, etc. Purpose is to create better conditions for its members and make decision-makers see the exciting potential in Zanzibar’s tourism industry.</p>	
Organization Functions, Operations, Products, and Services: <p>ZATI represent the interests of all tourism investors in Zanzibar and the main functions include: monitoring legislation and regulations in the tourism industry in order to ensure that policies and business conditions are designed to ease the operation of tourism-related businesses and new investments; advising and cooperating closely with the government in formulating policies and development programs relating to the tourism industry as well as in formulating strategies for promoting tourism and maintaining standards of professionalism, responsibility, and sustainability.</p>	
Stakeholders served/customer base: <p>Zanzibar tourism services providers, including hotels, cafés, souvenirs shops, along with companies outside direct tourism- like insurance and hospitals; and Government of Zanzibar and public institutions connected to tourism.</p>	
Challenges to Operations: <p>Areas of interest for advocacy and need improvement include safety and security; policies and taxation; infrastructure and utilities – e.g., poor safety of Zanzibar roads; promoting sustainable and responsible tourism; skills development; and destination marketing.</p>	
Interests Connected with Marine Conservation: <p>ZATI has an environmental committee chaired by Chumbe Island Park.</p>	
Alliance/Partnership Potential (High/medium/low): <p>Medium-High: ZATI can be an important channel for communicating and disseminating Heshimu Bahari activities to tourism investors and operators in Zanzibar.</p>	
Objective 3 Opportunities for Alignment with Heshimu Bahari: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity to serve as a convener of tourism stakeholders and a disseminator of information to private sector tourism stakeholders in Zanzibar (among their members, mainly hotels and small island tourism investors). • Opportunity for ZATI to support in the organization of trainings for government agencies, tourism private sector stakeholders, and others, with a specific focus on the gender lens investing (GLI) training Heshimu Bahari is mandated to implement. 	

<p>What they bring to a potential partnership:</p> <p>Convening power and ability to disseminate information to tourism investor network</p>	<p>What Heshimu Bahari brings to a potential partnership:</p> <p>Supporting their members with better marine conversation tools to support their interests if needed</p>
<p>Point of Contact: Greta Stålnacke, Director</p>	<p>Email: info@zati.or.tz</p>

ANNEX 4. PARTNERSHIP CONCEPT PRIORITIZATION SCORECARD

AREA	CRITERIA	DEFINITION	LOW = 1	MEDIUM = 3	HIGH = 5
Business Value (BV)	Addresses a core business priority	To what extent does the concept contribute to business goals or remove key bottlenecks of risk	Low	Moderate	High
	Improves license to operate	To what extent does the concept strengthen the reputation of the business or private sector entity?	Low	Moderate	High
Development Value (DV)	Alignment	To what extent does it align with the Heshimu Bahari's seascapes	1	1-2	3+
	Impact	To what extent will the concept contribute to Activity key results	Low	Medium	High
	Sustainability	How likely will the results of this PSE/partnership concept last?	More of a one-off	Some potential for sustainable results	High potential for success and replication
Feasibility (F)	Complexity	What is the relative ease to move this concept from idea to implementation	Achieving results will be difficult (high # partners, several dependencies, unpredictable operational context)	Moderate level of difficulty	Pathway to implementation and results is relatively easy
	Staff effort	How much Activity and partner (s) staff effort would be needed for the engagement to succeed?	Low confidence	Moderate confidence	High confidence
	Time horizon	How much time would the engagement need to start to deliver meaningful results?	5+ years	3-4 years	1-2 years

ANNEX 5. INTERVIEW GUIDE TEMPLATE

Overview and Background Research

COMPANY PROFILE	
Name & Title of Interviewee/s	
Geographic focus	
Organization Type	
Sector	
Main business functions, operations, products, or services	
Main customer base, what markets does it serve	
Interests and business strategies related to marine protection, fisheries and/or coastal livelihoods	
Prior USAID or development donor experience	

Interview Questions

These are semi-structured interviews, so the interviewer may ask additional follow-up questions and skip over some pre-entered questions. Please record any supplementary questions for reference during analysis. If there is an opportunity to interview in-person, be sure to print off a copy to facilitate notetaking during the meeting.

1. What are your company/organization's interests or priorities in marine conservation, fisheries production and/or coastal communities?
 - a. *Note: tailor based on company and the organization profile, and ask the following:*
 - i. What are your primary products and services?
 - ii. What markets do you serve/where do you operate?
 - iii. *If applicable: for private sector led MMA stakeholders...what is the key to success in private sector led MMA management?*
2. What are the greatest challenges or obstacles to your business operations and/or long-term growth?
 - a. What challenges or obstacles do you anticipate in the future?
 - b. What challenges does your company/organization face in addressing these interests and priorities?
3. What are the key barriers for your sector to engage effectively in marine conservation, sustainable fisheries and/or coastal livelihood development?
 - a. *If relevant follow-up on what are the main regulatory barriers?*
 - b. *If relevant, follow-up question on main barriers to investment in tourism and/or fisheries?*
 - c. *If relevant, follow-up on value chain and market barriers for fisheries/seafood?*
4. What are the main challenges with sourcing sustainable seafood products?
 - a. *If relevant follow-up, do you source locally, or are interested in sourcing? If yes, what products? What are the main challenges with sourcing local?*
5. What roles do you think your company and other businesses are best positioned to play in MMAs, sustainable fisheries and/or coastal livelihood development (pick based on sector)?

6. How can the USAID Heshimu Bahari Activity support your business and your sector to address challenges/obstacles and contribute to marine conservation, sustainable fisheries management and/or sustainable value chains?
 - a. *If relevant, follow-up question on how can the project support investment in MMAs/sustainable fisheries or value chains?*
 - b. *What incentives are needed?*
7. How can the USAID Heshimu Bahari Activity support your business and your sector to engage with coastal communities more effectively?
 - a. *What are the priorities for improving engagement with coastal communities? Access to technology, coordination, BDS services, skills development, providing incentives, etc.*
8. How do you engage with women and/or youth in your business activities and/or supply chain relationships?
 - a. What gender-related challenges impact your business or your segment of the sector (or supply chain)?
 - b. What opportunities do you see in strengthening women and youth's roles in your supply chain or organization, or in your sector?
9. Have you ever engaged or partnered with USAID or other donors in the past? How was the experience?

Closing and Recommendations

1. Is there anything else you think we should consider related to engaging the private sector in MMA and sustainable fisheries management?
2. Are there other companies or organizations that you would recommend we speak with?
3. If we have any follow-up questions, can we reach back out to you?

Debrief (to be completed after the interview)

REFLECTIONS	
How does this company conceptualize and talk about MMAs, sustainable fisheries or coastal livelihoods?	
Do they seem like a leader with strategies and interest in MMAs, sustainable fisheries/value chains, or coastal livelihoods issues?	If yes, describe.
What is the extent of alignment with the Heshimu Bahari's objectives?	Low Medium High Why?
How could the project help this company?	(e.g., convening, community engagement, co-financing, technical advising, etc.)
What resources/assets could this company bring to a partnership?	(e.g., market access, investment, application of frameworks)
What are some risks and assumptions to engaging with this company?	(e.g., seen as greenwashing, fraught community relations, etc.)

ANNEX 6. PSE SECTOR ANALYSES

Tourism

Why Target?	Challenges to Address	Potential Intervention Areas	Relevant Actors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to serve as direct investors in MMA management, community resilience building, and other conservation efforts • High-level of investment and strong presence in target seascapes • History of successful partnerships in MMA strengthening both in Tanzania and globally 	Limited Profitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable marine tourism promotion • Facilitate grants and impact investment to co-fund marine conservation • Advocacy for improved infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hotel/tourism associations • Tour companies and hotel operators • Government • Transport services providers • Banks, funds, and other financing institutions
	Unfavorable Enabling Environment for Private Sector MMA Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen advocacy skills and activities of tourism associations • Support relevant studies/research for PPP in MMA management • Engage government, associations, investors, and leading hotels in dialogue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourism associations • Tour companies and hotel operators • Government institutions • Relevant investors
	Lack of Knowledge and Resources for Marine Conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-to-peer training on marine conservation and communities • Share best practices on successful eco-resorts and private sector MMA • Co-fund conservation and community reliance activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government institutions • Hotel/tourism associations • Leading eco-resorts • Relevant investors

Fisheries

Why Target?	Challenges to Address	Potential Intervention Areas	Relevant Actors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct impact on marine biodiversity and critical livelihood in coastal communities • Opportunity to improve quality and value in fishery value chains to increase resilience of fishers and communities • Seafood companies could offer market access and financial resources to co-invest in value chain improvements and sustainable fisheries 	Low Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve cooperatives organization and technical support • Introduce improved fishing, processing, and storage practices • Improve access to appropriate technologies and equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperatives • NGOs • Fish traders and seafood processors • Government • Processing and cold chain technology providers
	Lack of Financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen cooperatives business and financial literacy skills • Engage financial institutions to offer tailored loans to cooperatives and SMEs • Explore additional sources of finance like community revolving funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local banks and MFIs • SEAF, GCF, GFCR, and others • Cooperatives • Seafood processors • SMEs
	Lack of Reliable Markets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage buyers and processors interested in quality fish products • Increase fishers and traders' access to technology, finance, and skills • Engage cold chain operators and advanced markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large seafood buyers and processors • Supermarkets • Cooperatives • Banks and financing institutions • Government • Cold chain companies

Seaweed

Why Target?	Challenges to address	Potential intervention areas	Relevant actors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunity of alternative livelihood for coastal communities and reduce pressure on overfished wild-caught fisheries • Potential for blue carbon • Large number of women involved in farming • Potential for increased employment for coastal communities in value-addition SMEs 	Low Productivity Conflict with fishers and tourism sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve organization and business acumen of farmers in cooperatives, groups and clusters • Introduce new practices, value addition technologies, increase access to drying tech, and sustainable inputs (e.g. bio-degradable ropes) • Engage public and private stakeholders to improve land-use and access to adequate land for seaweed farming – surveys, EIAs, etc 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seaweed farmers and cooperatives • NGOs (MSOAPO, MITO, etc) • Local companies (C-WEED, etc) • Buyers • Government (FETA, LGAs, etc) • Drying technology providers (FETA)
	Lack of Financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen business and financial literacy skills of cooperatives • Engage banks to offer loans for improving quality of product • Explore additional revenue streams via carbon credits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local banks (CRDB, TADB) • GCF, GFCR and other co-funders • Seaweed cooperatives • Off takers/buyers
	Global Competition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage buyers interested in differentiating seaweed products • Support SMEs investment in seaweed-based products manufacturing • Collaborative research on non-carrageenan products • Increase farmers access to technology, finance and skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large buyers and off takers (Cargil, bioplastics, etc.) • Seaweed cooperatives • Banks and financing institutions • Government • Intl. incubators/NGOs

Aquaculture

Why Target?	Challenges to Address	Potential Intervention Areas	Relevant Actors
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take pressure off overfished wild-caught fisheries and provide a food source • Opportunities for supplemental or diversified livelihood opportunities in coastal communities • Large number of youth and women involved in the sector • Potential for blue carbon and restoration of coastal habitats 	Low Profitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage private sector to improve access to quality seed and extension services • Introduce new practices and increase access to value addition technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaculture farmers and cooperatives • Local companies and international buyers • Government • Aquaculture technology providers
	Lack of Space and Conflict with Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage public and private stakeholders to improve access in appropriate areas for production • Introduce new practices and technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public institutions • Aquaculture technology providers • NGOs
	Lack of Financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage banks to offer loans for improving quality of product through access to appropriate technologies and equipment • Explore and support additional sources of finance like community financing programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offtakers/buyers • Local banks • Fisher cooperatives • MFIs • BDS providers
	Limited Access to Higher Value Markets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage buyers and processors interested in quality fish products • Increase fishers and traders' access to technology, finance, and skills • Engage cold chain operators and advanced markets (e.g., supermarkets) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large buyers and offtakers • Supermarkets • Farmer cooperatives • Banks and financing institutions • Government • Technology providers

Finance

Why Target?

- Can develop finance vehicles that bring private capital to blue economy sectors and marine conservation efforts
- Ability to provide capital investments, working capital, and credit solutions
- Knowledge and guidance to help SMEs scale in blue economy sectors

Challenges to Address	Potential Intervention Areas	Relevant Actors
Financial Institutions Low Internal Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide financial institutions with capacity training and technical assistance on the blue economy • Engage financial institutions to develop specific blue economy loan products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SEAF-CEED • NGOs • CRDB, Equity Bank • TADB • Blue economy companies
SMEs Lack Collateral	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen business and financial literacy skills of blue economy SMEs seeking debt financing through BDS and/or financial support to make them investment ready • Create incentives and mechanisms to link SME financing with sustainable fisheries and marine conservation • Engage with financial institutions to unlock more marine conservation-conscious blue economy financing and guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local banks, incubators, and BDS providers • DFC-DCA first-loss guarantee • GCF, GFCA and other co-funders • SEAF-CEED • NGOs
Limited Studies/Assessments Conducted on Blue Economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support financial institutions in conducting several different types of assessments for loans, such as environmental assessments, feasibility studies, and landscape analyses • Link financial institutions with the actors necessary for conducting the relevant studies/assessments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banks and other financing institutions (e.g., UNDP, GCF) • Government (e.g., NEMC, TIC, MIIT, ZIPA) • International and local incubators/NGOs • Private contractors/consultants

